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Hydrodynamic Modeling of Heating Processes in Solar Flares

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ABSTRACT

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This thesis examines the heating of the solar atmosphere due to energy release in solar flares. A one-dimensional hydrodynamic model, which solves the equations of conservation of mass, momentum, and energy along a magnetic flux tube, is described in detail and employed to study the dynamic response of the solar atmosphere to large amounts of energy release from the magnetic field.

A brief introduction to the solar atmosphere and solar flares, from both observational and theoretical perspectives, is given. Then, the hydrodynamic model is described, along with derivations of energy deposition due to a beam of highly energetic electrons colliding with the ambient atmosphere (and their implementation in the model is explained). Using this model of heating along with RHESSI-derived parameters of observed flares, the sensitivity of the GOES flare classification to the parameters of the electron beam (the non-thermal energy, the power-law index of the electron distribution, and the low-energy cut-off) are examined, and clear correlations are determined.

Next, the response of the atmosphere to heating due to isoenergetic beams of electrons are studied, to elucidate the importance of electrons at different energy. It is found that at high total energy fluxes, the energy of individual electrons are unimportant, but that at lower fluxes, lower energy electrons are significantly more efficient at heating the atmosphere and driving chromospheric evaporation than high energy electrons. It is also found that the threshold for explosive evaporation is strongly dependent on the cut-off energy, as well as the beam flux.

A case study of a well-observed flare is performed. The flare, a C-class flare that occurred on 28 November 2002, was modeled for various cases of heating due to a beam of electrons, *in situ* coronal heating, and a hybrid model that combines both forms of heating. It is found that the observation of X-ray source heights seen with RHESSI are most consistent with a hybrid model. The results indicate that the energy must be partitioned between thermal and kinetic energy, and the implications are discussed.

This work is then summarized, and future avenues of research are discussed. Improvements that can be made to the model, the forward modeling of emission, and comparisons to observations are discussed.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The Sun

As the only star which can be spatially resolved, the Sun is and has been one of the most important astrophysical objects to study. The Sun is classified as a G2V star, that is, a G2 class dwarf star, around the middle of its lifetime on the main sequence. It is a Population I star, meaning that it has a fairly high metallicity (abundance of elements higher than helium), and was formed from the remnants of previous generations of stars.

In the core of the Sun, at around 15 million K (MK), the Sun is fusing hydrogen into helium predominantly through the proton-proton chain, whereby four protons are converted into a helium-4 nucleus, releasing energy. The energy will be released primarily in the form of γ -rays, which despite having extremely high energy, have an extremely short mean-free path in the core of the sun. They will take approximately 10^5 years to escape the Sun, losing energy through scattering as they proceed outwards.

Above the core is the radiative zone. Fusion is confined to the core because the temperature and density drop significantly outside of

it. This region is characterized by the primary means of energy transport: the scattering of radiation. The plasma in this region constantly absorbs and reemits the photons trapped here, which slowly escape via a random walk process.

Above the radiative zone is the convection zone, where heat is transported primarily through convective bubbles (see Figure 1-1). Near the transition between the radiative and convection zone (the tachocline) the plasma is heated until it can rise buoyantly towards the surface of the Sun. Beneath the convection zone, the Sun rotates as a rigid body. However, above this region, the plasma begins to rotate differentially (varying primarily by latitude and slightly with depth). The currents that are generated due to this differential rotation are thought to be the source of the magnetic field in the Sun (along with other factors like meridional flows).

1.2 The Solar Atmosphere

The study of the solar atmosphere has been an extensive field of research for more than a hundred years. A number of phenomena have presented themselves that have broadened our understanding of the Sun and of plasma physics in general: from the extreme temperature of the

Figure 1-1: A high resolution image of the photosphere, as seen by the National Solar Observatory. The bubbles in the image are the convective bubbles, rising buoyantly from the convection zone beneath the surface. The darker plasma is cooler and falling downwards, while the brighter plasma is hotter and thus rising due to convection. The darkest region is a sunspot, where a strong magnetic field prevents material from moving inwards, and is thus much cooler than the surrounding plasma (about 4,000 K compared to 5,800 K). Image courtesy of National Solar Observatory/AURA/NSF.

corona, the outflow of the solar wind (both fast and slow), the eruptions of coronal mass ejections, the periodic nature of the solar cycle, and solar flares, among many others. Behind all of these phenomena lies the magnetic field and its interaction with the plasma in the atmosphere.

The solar atmosphere is composed of four regimes (in order of radial distance): the photosphere, the chromosphere, the transition region, and the corona. Figure 1-2 shows these four regimes, as seen by the Solar Dynamics Observatory's Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (SDO-AIA; Lemen et al. 2012 [101]) on 29 April, 2014.

The top left image in Figure 1-2 shows the solar photosphere, in 4500 Å light, primarily from continuum emission around 5,800 K. The photosphere is also referred to as the surface of the Sun, defined as the region where the optical depth of visible light becomes opaque (*i.e.*, $\tau \approx \frac{2}{3}$). The black regions in the image are known as sunspots, regions of strong magnetic fields rising through the surface, which inhibit convection from the surrounding photosphere, and therefore remain at a lower temperature than the rest of the surface. Sunspots are short-lived on the Sun, generally lasting a few hours to a day, although corresponding starspots on other stars have been seen to last for several years (Berdyugina 2005 [15]).

Figure 1-2: The four layers of the solar atmosphere, as seen by SDO-AIA on 29 April, 2014. *Top Left:* The solar photosphere (surface), seen in 4500 Å light, primarily from continuum emission, around 6×10^3 K. *Top Right:* The solar chromosphere, lying above the photosphere, seen in 304 Å light emitted primarily from He II, around 8×10^4 K. *Bottom Left:* The transition region and lower corona, seen in 171 Å light emitted primarily from Fe IX, around 6×10^5 K. *Bottom Right:* The solar corona and flaring regions, seen in 193 Å light emitted primarily from Fe XII and Fe XXIV, around 1×10^6 and 2×10^7 K, respectively.

The top right image in Figure 1-2 shows the solar chromosphere, in 304 Å light, emitted primarily from He II ions (*i.e.*, singly ionized helium) at around 80,000 K. The chromosphere is so named because its spectrum is dominated by emission lines of many different colors (the strongest of which is the red H α line). In this region, the plasma density begins to decrease from photospheric values, while the temperature falls to about 3,800 K (called the temperature minimum) before rising to values exceeding 30,000 K. Although the density is lower here, the chromosphere remains dense enough that it is optically thick.

The bottom left image in Figure 1-2 shows the solar transition region and lower part of the corona, in 171 Å light, emitted primarily from Fe IX ions, at around 6×10^5 K. The transition region is defined as the layer where thermal conduction provides a source of energy, rather than acting as a sink of energy in the corona. It is marked by an extremely sharp rise in temperature of around two orders of magnitude and a similar decrease in the plasma density. The height of the transition region varies, in general, although it is roughly around 2,000 - 3,000 km above the surface, and no more than 100-500 km in extent.

Finally, the bottom right image in Figure 1-2 shows the solar

corona, as well as flaring regions in the corona, in 193 Å light, emitted by Fe XII and Fe XXIV ions at around 1 and 20 MK, respectively. The corona is characterized by extremely high temperatures (> 1 MK) and low densities ($\approx 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-3}$), so that it is optically thin. Due to the extremely large temperature, hydrogen and helium, the primary constituents of solar plasma, are fully ionized here, so that the electron and ion densities are approximately equal. Due to the high degree of ionization, the corona is a very good electrical conductor. Further, the magnetic field here is extremely strong compared to the gas pressure, so that the plasma is strongly confined to magnetic field lines (see below for more). The bright regions in the corona are termed active regions, where the magnetic field is strongest and the temperature is highest. These regions are comprised of individually resolvable structures called coronal loops, and are the sites of phenomena such as solar flares and coronal mass ejections.

Nearly all of the phenomena of interest to solar physicists are related to the magnetic field of the Sun. Beneath the surface, the convective zone, from about 0.7 to 1 solar radii, rotates differentially with latitude, so that currents generate magnetic fields in large flux tubes. These flux tubes can rise above the surface due to buoyant

forces, creating sunspots (as in Figure 1-3, which shows a magnetic map of the solar surface). The generation of the magnetic field at the solar interior is believed to be a dynamo process, which is beyond the scope of the current work (see Ossendrijver 2003 [124] for more information).

Recently, the Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory (STEREO) spacecraft have given an unprecedented view of the structure of the magnetic field in the solar atmosphere (Howard et al. 2008 [80]). Using two spacecraft, one drifting ahead and one lagging behind the Earth in its orbit around the sun, STEREO can build stereoscopic images of the corona. The two spacecraft each see the Sun from a different vantage point, so that 3D maps of the atmosphere can be constructed. By mapping the coronal loops, researchers can reconstruct three-dimensional maps of the coronal magnetic field (e.g., Aschwanden et al. 2009 [10]).

One difficulty that remains is determining the strength of the coronal magnetic field. In general, active regions have temperatures on the order of $\approx 3 - 4 \times 10^6$ K (an unsolved problem known as the coronal heating problem, see Klimchuk 2006 [88]), so that spectral lines emanating from these regions are strongly thermally broadened. Thus, Zeeman splitting of spectral lines cannot be used, in general, to measure the strength of the magnetic field in the upper atmosphere. Infrared

Figure 1-3: The photospheric magnetic field as measured by SDO-HMI on 29 April, 2014. The black areas are regions of South polarity magnetic field, while the white areas are North polarity. Note that the areas with strong magnetic fields correspond to the active regions in Figure 1-2.

polarimetry may allow for direct measurements of the field in the future (*e.g.* Tomczyk et al. 2010 [141]).

Other properties of the magnetic field, however, can be readily deduced. Define the plasma β parameter as the ratio of the gas to magnetic pressure:

$$\beta = \frac{P_{gas}}{P_{mag}} = \frac{16\pi k_B n T}{B^2} \quad (1.1)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, n is the density, T is the temperature, and B is the magnetic field strength. A low β value implies that the magnetic field dominates the gas pressure, so that particles in the plasma will be strongly confined by the magnetic field. Although it is difficult to directly measure the field strength in the corona, observations of magnetic loops in the corona for many years have strongly indicated that the corona is a low- β plasma (Reidy et al. 1968 [132]; Dulk & McLean 1978 [47]; Gary 2001 [65]). Figure 1-4, taken from Gary (2001 [65]), shows the plasma β as a function of height above the solar surface, showing the transition from high- to low- β that occurs within the chromosphere.

One consequence of a low- β plasma and a near-perfect conductivity is that the field lines are said to be “frozen in” to the plasma. The

Figure 1-4: The plasma beta as a function of height above the solar surface. The left- and right-hand side limits are for magnetic field lines originating from an active region of 2500 G and a plage of about 150 G, between which most coronal field lines should be contained. See figure 1-2 and the accompanying text for more information on the layers of the sun's atmosphere. Taken from Gary 2001 [65].

induction equation of ideal magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) gives the following relation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{B} \quad (1.2)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field, \mathbf{v} is the plasma velocity, and η is the magnetic diffusivity, which is small in the strongly conducting regime ($\propto 1/\sigma$, i.e., inversely proportional to the conductivity). Because the corona is highly ionized and extremely hot, the conductivity becomes extremely large, so that the induction equation in the corona reduces to:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (1.3)$$

From this relation, Alfven showed the magnetic flux in a bounded surface will be conserved, that is, the magnetic field lines move with the plasma, so that the flux is effectively frozen to it (called the frozen-in flux theorem, Alfven 1943 [2]). The derivation is as follows. Consider some surface S moving with the magnetic field bounded by a curve C . The magnetic flux is defined as:

$$F = \int_S \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (1.4)$$

so that the time derivative (change of bounded magnetic flux) is

$$\frac{dF}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \int_S \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (1.5)$$

The equation must then be split into two parts due to changes in \mathbf{B} and motions of the curve C . Changes due to the magnetic field can be written as:

$$\int_S \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \quad (1.6)$$

Consider a small section $d\mathbf{l}$ of the curve C . If the curve is moving at speed \mathbf{v} , then $d\mathbf{l}$ sweeps out an area $\mathbf{v} \times d\mathbf{l}$ in a given time, so that the change in magnetic flux due to this is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_C \mathbf{B} \cdot (\mathbf{v} \times d\mathbf{l}) &= \int_C d\mathbf{l} \cdot (\mathbf{B} \times \mathbf{v}) \\ &= - \int_S \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot d\mathbf{S} \end{aligned} \quad (1.7)$$

where Stoke's theorem has been used to convert the line integral to a surface integral. Finally, the total change in magnetic flux is the sum

of these two integrals:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dF}{dt} &= \int_S \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \cdot d\mathbf{S} - \int_S \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot d\mathbf{S} \\
&= \int_S \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \right) \cdot d\mathbf{S} \\
&= \int_S \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \right) \cdot d\mathbf{S} \\
&= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{1.8}$$

where Equation 1.3 has been used to simplify the integral. The result is thus established: the magnetic flux in a bounded surface is conserved in a perfectly conducting plasma. The solar corona is nearly a perfect conductor, so this result holds there (although not necessarily lower in the atmosphere where diffusion may play a role in determining sunspot lifetime, Bradshaw & Hartigan 2014 [20]).

Thus, the plasma is strongly confined to magnetic flux tubes in the atmosphere. It can also be shown that the thermal conductivity parallel to the magnetic field far exceeds the conductivity perpendicular to the field by a factor of around 10^8 (Goedbloed & Poedts 2004 [66]). Thus, there is little cross-field interaction and the plasma is confined to coronal loops which can also be considered as thermally isolated structures.

Coronal loops, then, can be considered the basic structure of the corona, a local manifestation of the magnetic field lines. Researchers classify coronal loops in terms of their temperatures, or, correspondingly, in terms of the wavelengths of light they emit. For example, Reale (2010 [130]) lists three basic types: cold ($10^5 - 10^6$ K, seen in UV lines), warm ($10^6 - 1.5 \times 10^6$ K, typically seen in EUV lines), and hot ($> 2 \times 10^6$ K, typically seen in X-rays and hot EUV lines) loops, to which perhaps should be added flaring loops ($\geq 10 \times 10^6$ K). Reale suggests that the different types of loops may be governed by different regimes of physics, and hence the distinctions are not arbitrary. Loops can extend over lengths from 10^8 cm to well over 10^{11} cm (*e.g.*, trans-equatorial loops). Loop temperatures can vary between 10^5 K to a few 10^7 K in flaring loops. Loop densities have been observed from roughly 10^8 cm⁻³ to over 10^{11} cm⁻³ in the hottest loops (Reale 2010 [130]).

Coronal loops are often assumed to be semi-circular structures. Loop lengths are calculated under this assumption using the foot-point to foot-point distance (also assuming the loop is not inclined relative to the line-of-sight). However, as Reale (2010 [130]) points out, loops often deviate from this shape, and determining their exact lengths can be difficult. For example, the early study of Berton & Sakurai (1985

[16]) found fairly large deviations from semi-circular shapes with apices shifted towards one of the foot-points, which they suggest is due to one foot-point having a more concentrated magnetic field than the other (a general property of active regions). The STEREO (Kaiser *et al.* 2008 [86]) mission is giving new insights into the problem: the perspective from each of the STEREO satellites allows observers to reconstruct the three-dimensional geometry of coronal loops (*e.g.*, Feng *et al.* 2007 [55], Aschwanden & Sandman 2010 [11]).

Similarly, the cross-sections of coronal loops are generally assumed to be constant in area and circular in shape. Observationally, the cross-sections of coronal loops have been found to have little variation (< 30%) along the length of the loops (Klimchuk *et al.* 1992 [89]); what little variation exists may be due to twisting of magnetic field lines. On the contrary, Malanushenko & Schrijver (2013 [110]) provide evidence that cross-sections of coronal loops may not be circular, and likely do vary along the length, suggesting that there may be a selection bias towards loops of constant cross-section.

1.3 Solar Flares

Solar flares were observed for the first time simultaneously and independently by R.C. Carrington (1859 [33]) and R. Hodgson (1859 [77]), during the white light event of September 1, 1859 (now referred to as the Carrington event). Hodgson wrote: “I was suddenly surprised at the appearance of a very brilliant star of light, much brighter than the sun’s surface, most dazzling to the protected eye, illuminating the upper edges of the adjacent spots and streaks, not unlike in effect the edging of the clouds at sunset...” Modern analysis of the event suggests that it was the most intense magnetic storm ever recorded, bright enough in white light to equal that of the solar surface (Tsurutani et al. 2003 [144]).

Since then, solar flares have been studied in great detail. They are characterized by extremely large releases of energy (up to 10^{33} erg), with emission across the entire electromagnetic spectrum, from radio to γ -rays. Flares are generally thought to be caused by the rapid release of energy previously stored in the magnetic field, through a process called magnetic reconnection. The magnetic energy is converted into either kinetic energy (*i.e.*, accelerated particles) or thermal energy (*i.e.*, *in situ* heating), or perhaps both. Chapter 5 will address this further.

Flares are generally classified by their X-ray flux as observed by the Geostationary Orbiting Environmental Satellites (GOES), although there are alternate classification schemes based on their brightness in the $H\alpha$ and radio bands. Figure 1-5 shows an example of how flares are classified with GOES. In general, smaller flares occur much more commonly than the largest flares, following a power-law distribution of energies (Hudson 1991 [81]).

1.3.1 Observational Properties

Emission in flares occurs across the entire spectrum, with the majority at optical and ultraviolet frequencies (Woods et al. 2006 [155]), while X-ray emissions comprise around 10% (Thomas & Teske 1971 [140]). Hard X-rays (HXR), which only comprise a small amount of the radiative energy in flares, are primarily due to non-thermal bremsstrahlung, so they have become an important diagnostic for particle acceleration and determining the properties of electron beams in flares (*e.g.*, Holman et al. 2003 [79]). The largest flares even emit at γ -ray frequencies, with a combination of radiation due to bremsstrahlung, nuclear annihilation lines, nuclear formation lines, and the decay of exotic particles such as pions (Ramaty & Murphy 1987 [129]). At longer

Figure 1-5: The GOES data for 11 April, 2013. There are three flares labeled, in terms of their peak flux in the 1-8 Å channel (red). The largest, labeled M6.5, has a peak flux of $6.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ W m}^{-2}$. Flares are thus classified in the 1-8 Å channel in decreasing decades as X-class ($> 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-2}$), M-class ($> 10^{-5} \text{ W m}^{-2}$), C-class ($> 10^{-6} \text{ W m}^{-2}$), B-class ($> 10^{-7} \text{ W m}^{-2}$), and A-class ($> 10^{-8} \text{ W m}^{-2}$).

wavelengths, flares are accompanied by radio and microwave emission, due to gyroradiation as energetic electrons spiral around the magnetic field lines (Bastian et al. 1998 [12]).

Solar flares can be characterized by three phases in their temporal evolution: the pre-flare, impulsive, and gradual phases. In the pre-flare phase, the soft X-rays (SXR) begin to brighten in about 90% of flares about 3 minutes before the HXR burst (Veronig et al. 2002 [147]). Non-thermal line broadening is also observed before the start of a flare, thought to be due to turbulent changes in the active region before flare onset (Harra et al. 2001 [72], Harra et al. 2009 [73]). Small X-ray brightenings are also observed co-temporally with the onset of coronal mass ejections (CMEs) in some flares (Harrison et al. 1985).

A few minutes after the precursors, the impulsive phase begins, characterized by sharp, intense brightenings in HXR, radio, white light, and γ -rays. During this phase, there is a strong HXR burst observed near the chromospheric foot-points of the flaring loop. For example, Figure 1-6 (taken from Lin et al. 2003 [105]) shows the time evolution of X-rays observed with RHESSI and GOES during an X-class flare that occurred on 23 July 2002 (left), along with the SXR (black contours) and HXR (white contours) sources overlaid on an $H\alpha$

Figure 1-6: An example of a strong HXR burst during an X-class flare, observed with RHESSI. *Left:* The light curves in various X-ray energy bands observed with RHESSI and GOES, showing the impulsive nature of the HXR source when compared to the gradual evolution in the GOES SXR bands. *Right:* RHESSI sources overlaid on an $H\alpha$ image taken by Big Bear Solar Observatory. The HXR sources (white contours) are confined near the base of the loop, in the chromosphere, whereas the SXR source (black contours) is found near the loop-top in the corona. Images taken from Lin et al. (2003 [105]).

image taken by Big Bear Solar Observatory (right). Note that the HXR burst is intense and short-lived compared to the gradual SXR emission, and that the HXR source is strongly confined near the base of the loop, while the SXR emission is near the loop-top.

During the impulsive phase, many flares are observed to have a correlation between the HXR burst and the rise of the SXR emission. Specifically, the flux of the HXR burst is empirically determined to correlate with the derivative of the SXR flux (or equivalently, the integral

of the HXR flux is correlated to the SXR flux):

$$F_{HXR} \propto \frac{d}{dt} F_{SXR} \quad (1.9)$$

This correlation is the well-known Neupert effect in solar flares (Neupert 1968 [121]; Dennis & Zarro 1993 [42]). This relation is found to hold in the majority of flares ($\approx 75\%$, Veronig et al. 2002 [147]), although not all. Figure 1-7 shows an example flare that clearly demonstrates the Neupert effect (taken from Dennis & Zarro 1993 [42]).

During the impulsive phase, energy released from the magnetic field is deposited in the lower atmosphere, near the top of the chromosphere. It is unknown whether the energy is carried by a beam of accelerated particles (the thick-target model; Brown 1971 [25]; Lin & Hudson 1976 [104]) or transported via thermal conduction following *in situ* heating of the corona (Smith & Auer 1980 [136]; MacNeice 1986 [108]), or a combination of both mechanisms. However, once the energy is delivered to the chromosphere and it is heated, its pressure begins to rise ($\propto nT$), driving an upward expansion upwards. This expansion, termed chromospheric ablation (or, perhaps less correctly but more commonly, evaporation), forces material back into the corona, causing a drastic increase in density and thus radiation (Antiochos & Stur-

Figure 1-7: An example of the Neupert effect in a solar flare. The top plot shows the light-curve of the SXR emission observed with GOES, while the middle plot shows the time derivative of that light-curve. The bottom plot shows the light-curve of the HXR burst in that same flare. Note the clear relation between the SXR derivative and the HXR light-curve. Plots taken from Dennis & Zarro (1993 [42]).

rock 1978 [3]; Fisher et al. 1985a,b [57, 58]). This pressure expansion will simultaneously cause a down-flow of material in the chromosphere, due to momentum conservation, which is referred to as chromospheric condensation (Fisher et al. 1985c [59]).

The flare then transitions into the gradual phase, marked by the slow decay of SXR radiation (see Figure 1-6). During this phase, arcades of loops continue to fill and brighten as magnetic reconnection proceeds. Figure 1-8 shows the arcade that formed during the Bastille Day X-class flare as an example. In general, successive outer loops reach higher altitudes (Gallagher et al. 2002 [63]) and are hotter than the inner loops (Tsuneta 1996 [142]; Forbes & Acton 1996 [62]).

During the gradual phase, the loops begin to cool and drain material, resulting in a slow decrease in the SXR, EUV, and microwave emission (Culhane et al. 1970 [37]). The loops cool initially by thermal conduction, which transports energy from the corona towards the chromosphere, resulting in weak upflows back into the corona (Cargill et al. 1995 [29]). Thus, the temperature begins to fall while the density continues to rise, which eventually leads the cooling to transition into a regime dominated by radiation (e.g., Aschwanden & Alexander 2001 [7]), and enthalpy-driven cooling (Bradshaw & Cargill 2010 [18]).

Figure 1-8: An example of the formation of an arcade of loops. The image shows the arcade of loops that formed in the Bastille Day X5.7 flare of 14 July 2000, as seen with TRACE. As the flare proceeded, the arcade moved outwards, both east and west.

1.3.2 Solar flare heating

The energy release in solar flares has been poorly understood for a long time. They release up to 10^{33} erg of energy over time-scales of just a few minutes. In the solar atmosphere, the only plausible source of energy is the magnetic field (magnetic energy density $E_B = B^2/8\pi$). However, as Golub & Pasachoff (2010 [67]) note, the diffusion time for magnetic fields in the corona is greater than 10^{10} seconds, many orders of magnitude longer than a typical flare duration.

The leading theory is that flares are driven by a process called magnetic reconnection. Magnetic reconnection, a process found in nearly all magnetized plasmas throughout the universe, is “a topological restructuring of a magnetic field caused by a change in the connectivity of its field lines,” (Priest & Forbes 2000 [128]). Figure 1-9 shows the general idea of reconnection: a large spatial gradient formed between oppositely-directed field lines facilitates a breaking and reconnection of the field lines in a thin diffusion region that forms as the field lines come together (a small magnetic diffusivity coupled to a large gradient leads to diffusion and subsequent reconnection). The field reconfigures into a lower energy state, and excess magnetic energy is converted into thermal (*in situ* coronal heating) and kinetic energy (particle acceler-

Figure 1-9: The basic scheme of magnetic reconnection. (a) Initially, oppositely-directed magnetic field lines that are independent of one another are somehow pushed together. (b) A short while later, a small diffusion region with a very strong magnetic gradient forms between the field lines. (c) The field lines break and reconnect with other lines into the lowest energy state, releasing excess energy as thermal and kinetic energy in the plasma. Taken from Priest & Forbes 2000 [128].

ation) in the plasma. Further, because the topology of the field has changed, particle trajectories and thermal conduction paths are also changed (Priest & Forbes 2000 [128]).

Aschwanden (2006 [6]) notes a couple features of the corona that lend themselves to magnetic reconnection. First, the solar dynamo is constantly generating magnetic flux, which rises through the convective zone and emerges from the surface. Secondly, the differential rotation (which varies with both latitude and depth) and convective motions continually wrap up magnetic field lines. These factors lead to fields in the corona becoming increasingly stressed, which cause the field to adjust itself with changes in connectivity (see, for example, Parker 1988

[125]). The study of magnetic reconnection is an active field of research in the observing, experimental, and theoretical communities (see Yamada *et al.* 2010 for an excellent review of our current knowledge).

In the 1990s, many observations with the Yohkoh satellite began to firmly establish the presence of many important features of reconnection in flares. There were many observations of null points and their motions (Tsuneta *et al.* 1992 [143]; Aschwanden *et al.* 1996 [8]), HXR sources above the loop-top (Masuda *et al.* 1994 [113]), in-flows (Yokoyama *et al.* 2001 [157]), out-flows (McKenzie & Hudson 2001 [115]), magnetic field relaxation (Sui & Holman 2003 [137]), and cusp features (Acton *et al.* 1992 [1]; Doschek *et al.* 1995 [45]).

At present, it is not clear how the energy released by reconnection is partitioned between thermal and kinetic energy. However, there are a number of observations that shed light on this problem. For example, Krucker *et al.* (2008 [95]) demonstrate the presence of non-thermal electrons in the corona during the impulsive phase of flares, and that a large fraction will be accelerated (perhaps up to 100%: Krucker *et al.* 2010 [97]). The proportions are currently unknown, but a new way by which the partition of energy might be estimated is discussed in Chapter 5.

There are two primary models of energy release in solar flares: the collisional thick-target model (Brown 1971 [25]) and the thermal conduction front model (Smith & Auer 1980 [136]). In the former, magnetic energy is converted into the kinetic energy of a beam of accelerated particles from the reconnection region near the loop-top that stream through the loop towards the chromosphere. The particles deposit all of their energy through Coulomb collisions with the ambient plasma, ultimately heating the chromosphere to extreme temperatures. In the latter model, the magnetic energy is converted into thermal energy and deposited *in situ* in the corona, causing a large temperature increase that sets up a thermal conduction front. The front propagates down the loop and loses its energy by diffusion in the lower parts of the atmosphere. At present, it is not clear if one, both, or neither of these models contributes to the driving mechanism for solar flares (although some observational signatures such as fast time spikes in HXR spectra cannot be readily explained by thermal conduction alone). Each possibility is investigated in detail in the course of the research presented here and firmer conclusions are reached in light of new evidence.

1.3.3 Chromospheric Evaporation

As energy is deposited in the chromosphere either through precipitating particles or thermal conduction, the chromospheric temperature begins to rise. The chromosphere is an efficient radiator, due to its high density ($I \propto n^2$), but its optical depth means that it will absorb a large amount of energy before it can be radiated away. In consequence, the temperature and the pressure rise dramatically ($P = nk_B T$). The rise in pressure drives an expansion of material upwards into the corona, through a process called chromospheric evaporation or chromospheric ablation (Hirayama 1974 [76]; Antiochos & Sturrock 1978 [3]).

Numerical simulations have shown both particle beam-driven heating (MacNeice et al. 1984 [109]; Nagai & Emslie 1984 [120]; Mariska & Poland 1985 [112]) and thermal conduction heating (Nagai 1980 [119]; MacNeice 1986 [108]; Fisher 1986 [56]) lead to chromospheric evaporation. Fisher et al. (1985a,b,c [57, 58, 59]) showed that for energy fluxes below approximately 10^{10} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻², the flows will be gentle (a small amount of material moving slowly) because the energy input does not much exceed the radiative losses in the chromosphere. For heating rates above that amount, the pressure increase causes an explosive up-flow of material, leading to flows exceeding a few hundred

km sec⁻¹, and increasing the coronal density by a couple orders of magnitude. Chromospheric evaporation is examined in this thesis in detail in Chapter 4.

Many observations have confirmed the rise in chromospheric pressure, the increase in coronal density, and the extreme flow speeds. For example, observations of highly blueshifted Ca XIX, Fe XXV, and Fe XXVI lines were reported in a number of early studies with the Solar Maximum Mission (Antonucci et al. 1982 [5]; Antonucci & Dennis 1983 [4]; Doschek 1990 [44]). Modern satellites confirm that highly ionized lines are strongly blue-shifted in flares, and that higher temperature lines are more strongly shifted than cooler ones, while the coolest lines tend to be red-shifted (Milligan & Dennis 2009 [118]; Milligan 2011 [117]; Doschek et al. 2013 [46]). Czaykowska et al. (1999, 2001 [39, 38]) thoroughly examined these flows and their time evolution in the late phase of flares, showing clear evidence of evaporation and reconnection. The red-shifted lines are evidence of chromospheric condensation: pressure waves moving downwards to balance the momentum of the upward flows (Fisher et al. 1985c [59]).

1.3.4 Solar Flare Cooling Phase

After the initial heating in a flare, thermal conduction fronts develop that dissipate energy near the chromosphere. Initially, before significant chromospheric evaporation raises the coronal density, radiative losses in the corona are small, and so cooling is dominated by thermal conduction. The time-scale over which thermal conduction acts can be written as:

$$\tau_C \approx \frac{3k_B n L_T^2}{\kappa_0 T^{5/2}} \quad (1.10)$$

where κ_0 is the Spitzer conductivity coefficient. For low densities and high temperatures, this time-scale is small, so that energy transport is dominated by conduction. However, as thermal conduction carries the heat away and chromospheric evaporation increases the coronal density, this time-scale will start to increase and thermal conduction will become less and less efficient.

Eventually, as the coronal density rises, so do the radiative losses ($\propto n^2$), which dominate the cooling at later times. If the radiative losses are approximated as a power-law:

$$\Lambda = \chi T^\alpha \quad (1.11)$$

for some constant χ and index α in a given temperature range (Rosner et al. 1978 [134]), then the radiative time-scale can be written as (Klimchuk et al. 2008 [90]):

$$\tau_R \approx \frac{3k_B T^{1-\alpha}}{n\chi} \quad (1.12)$$

The time-scale falls as the density increases and the temperature falls, in general, so that eventually it comes to dominate the rate of energy loss from the corona. At later times, as the radiative losses increase, material will begin to drain towards the transition region, causing an enthalpy-driven cooling (Bradshaw & Cargill 2010 [18]). Eventually, the loop will be unable to sustain the losses caused by radiative and enthalpy-driven cooling, causing a catastrophic cooling (Cargill & Bradshaw 2013 [31]).

As the flare cools, the flare becomes brighter in cooler spectral lines. For example, during the Bastille Day flare (Figure 1-8), Aschwanden & Alexander (2001 [7]) showed the cooling evolution of the flare over a period of seven minutes. The light-curves of successively cooler channels peaked one after the other as the flare cooled from 30 to 1 MK, clearly showing the cooling of the plasma. Similarly, Del Zanna et al. (2011 [40]) observed the heating and cooling phases of a small

B-class flare with Hinode-EIS. They observed significantly blue-shifted emission early, which was gradually replaced with red-shifted emission as the flare cooled.

2 Solar Flare Modeling

Numerically modeling solar flares has become an active field of research in the solar community during the last few decades. There are a large number of challenges due to the various physics involved and the many possible assumptions that can be made. In this thesis, flares are modeled using a one-dimensional hydrodynamic treatment, for two fluids (electrons and hydrogen, including both protons and neutral hydrogen) that evolve according to the equations of the conservation of mass, momentum, and energy.

One of the leading theories of the heating of solar flares is the collisional thick-target model, whereby electrons that are accelerated to very high energies stream through the magnetic loop towards the solar surface, depositing all of their energy into the ambient plasma through Coulomb collisions (see Brown 1971 [25], Lin & Hudson 1976 [104]). Figure 2-1 shows the geometry of the so-called standard model of a flare (taken from Benz 2008 [14]).

In this chapter, under the assumption of a thick-target model, the heating function for a beam of electrons depositing their energy through collisions with a hydrogen target is derived. Multiple cases

Figure 2-1: The standard model of a solar flare. Magnetic reconnection drives the release of energy, which accelerates particles to high energies near the top of the flaring loop (the HXR loop-top). The particles stream down the loop towards the chromosphere, where they deposit their energy through Coulomb collisions with the ambient plasma, heating the chromosphere and causing the impulsive HXR burst (the thick-target model). As the chromosphere heats, the pressure rises, which drives plasma back into the corona (chromospheric evaporation) thus raising the temperature and density, which results in the gradual SXR emission. Image taken from Benz (2008 [14]). Note that the bottom should read “chromospheric X-ray foot-point” rather than “coronal.”

of electron distributions are examined, with each distribution taking a power-law form above the so-called cut-off energy, with various forms of the low-energy part of the distribution. First, the hydrodynamic modeling of magnetic loops is explained in detail, for the general case of an isolated, multi-fluid magnetic flux tube (Section 2.1). Then, the equations for different electron distributions are derived (Section 2.2), followed by the heat that would be deposited into the plasma by each beam type (Section 2.3), the bremsstrahlung radiation that would be emitted by each (Section 2.4). Finally, there is a discussion of several of the assumptions made by the model (Section 2.5).

2.1 Hydrodynamic Modeling of Magnetic Loops

The calculations in this work were carried out using the HYDRAD code (Bradshaw & Mason 2003 [22]; Bradshaw & Cargill 2013 [19]), which solves the one-dimensional hydrodynamics equations appropriate to describing the behavior of a two-fluid plasma confined to an isolated magnetic strand. The hydrodynamics equations are as follows:

(i) Conservation of mass

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial s} \quad (2.1)$$

where ρ is the mass density ($\approx nm_i$), t is the time, v is the bulk-flow velocity, and s is the field-aligned spatial coordinate.

(ii) Conservation of momentum

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial(\rho v^2)}{\partial s} - \frac{\partial(p_e + p_i)}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial}{\partial s}\left(\frac{4}{3}\mu_i \frac{\partial v}{\partial s}\right) + \rho g_{\parallel} \quad (2.2)$$

where $p_e = nk_B T_e$ and $p_i = nk_B T_i$ are the electron and ion pressures, respectively, μ_i is the coefficient of viscosity for the ions (and we neglect that of the electrons as $\frac{\mu_e}{\mu_i} \propto \left(\frac{m_e}{m_i}\right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{T_e}{T_i}\right)^{5/2}$ will be small except when the electron temperature is extremely high compared to the ion temperature), and g_{\parallel} is the field-aligned gravitational acceleration.

(iii) Conservation of energy

Electrons:

$$E_e = \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} p_e \quad (2.3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_e}{\partial t} = & -\frac{\partial}{\partial s}[(E_e + p_e)v] + v \frac{\partial p_e}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial}{\partial s}(\kappa_{e0} T_e^{5/2} \frac{\partial T_e}{\partial s}) \\ & + \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} k_B n \nu_{ei} (T_i - T_e) - E_R + E_H \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

where E_e is the electrons' internal energy density, κ_{e0} is the coefficient

of electron thermal conductivity, T_e and T_i are the electron and ion temperatures, γ is the adiabatic index, and ν_{ei} is the electron-ion collision frequency, E_R is the energy lost by radiation per unit volume, and $E_H(s, t)$ is the energy input per unit volume by heating as a function of position and time. The terms on the right-hand side of equation 2.4 represent the input, removal, and redistribution of electron energy by various mechanisms. The first term is the transport of energy along the coronal loop through a bulk flow (a change of enthalpy flux with position). The second term represents the work done by the small electric field induced from a small charge imbalance ($eE = -\frac{1}{n} \frac{\partial p_e}{\partial s}$). The third term represents the transport of energy through thermal conduction (with a correction for the flux-saturated limit). The fourth term is the exchange of energy between the electrons and ions due to inter-species collisions. The fifth term is the energy lost through radiation (line emission and bremsstrahlung). Finally, the last term is the energy input into the coronal loop through some heating mechanism.

Ions:

$$E_i = \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} p_i + \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 \quad (2.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_i}{\partial t} = & -\frac{\partial}{\partial s}[(E_i + p_i)v] - v\frac{\partial p_e}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial}{\partial s}(\kappa_{i0}T_i^{5/2}\frac{\partial T_i}{\partial s}) \\ & + \frac{1}{\gamma - 1}k_B n\nu_{ei}(T_e - T_i) + \frac{\partial}{\partial s}\left(\frac{4}{3}\mu_i v\frac{\partial v}{\partial s}\right) + \rho v g_{\parallel} \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

where E_i is the ion energy density and κ_{i0} is the coefficient of ion thermal conductivity. The terms on the right-hand side of equation 2.6 similarly represent the input, removal, and distribution of ion energy. The first four terms are equivalent to those above. The fifth term represents the work done by viscous stress on the bulk flow, while the last term is the work done by gravity (note that this was neglected for the electrons because their mass density will be smaller by a factor of the mass ratio ≈ 1835).

To calculate the losses by radiation, HYDRAD makes use of the CHIANTI database (Dere *et al.* 1997 [43]) along with the following equations:

$$E_R(X) = n^2(0.83 \times Ab(X) \times \sum_{i=1}^{i=Z+1} \epsilon_i X_i) \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{\partial X_i}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial(X_i v)}{\partial s} + n(I_{i-1}X_{i-1} + R_i X_{i+1} - I_i X_i - R_{i-1}X_i) \quad (2.8)$$

where X denotes a given element (and we need to sum the contributions from the most abundant coronal elements: H, He, C, N, O, Ne, Na, Mg, Al, Si, S, Ar, Ca, Fe, Ni), 0.83 is the proton-to-electron ratio in the corona, $Ab(X)$ is the coronal abundance of element X relative to hydrogen, Z is the atomic number, ϵ_i is the emissivity of all lines from charge state i of element X (where $i = 1$ is neutral) as calculated from CHIANTI, X_i is the population fraction of charge state i , I_i is the ionization rate of charge state i , and R_i is the recombination rate of charge state i . Note that HYDRAD can also use a piece-wise power law fit to the radiative losses if desired (to save calculation time).

Before we specify heating events to study the subsequent evolution of the coronal loop, we must determine an initial loop profile (temperature, density, and velocity along the loop) to use with HYDRAD. We specify the loop geometry: total length, foot-point height, and inclination from the vertical direction (generally assuming semi-circular, although HYDRAD can handle arbitrary geometry through specification of $g_{\parallel}(s)$). The foot-point density and temperature are based on the VAL C model, which is a realistic profile calculated from observed, optically-thick emission lines (Vernazza et al. 1981 [146]). Then, the equations of energy and pressure are integrated from foot-point to foot-

point to determine the pressure and temperature as functions of position throughout the whole loop. At both the foot-points and apex, it is assumed that the conductive flux is zero. From these two values, we can then determine the density as a function of position, and it is assumed that the bulk-flow velocity is initially zero everywhere (hydrostatic equilibrium). Using the hydrodynamic equations and the initial loop profile, we can then specify some heating event(s) $E_H(s, t)$, that perturbs the energy balance, and follow the subsequent loop evolution.

2.2 Electron Distribution Functions

X-ray spectra of solar flares are due to several emission processes: thermal bremsstrahlung, emitted from extremely dense and hot plasma; non-thermal bremsstrahlung, emitted by accelerated particles streaming through the corona; and spectral lines, emitted by highly ionized states of elements. Instruments like RHESSI (Lin et al. 2002 [103]) have given the ability to disentangle the two components of bremsstrahlung to reveal properties of the beam of particles traversing the loop.

The basic idea is simple: given a photon spectrum due to free-free electron-ion emission, the electron spectrum can be derived by inverting the integral for thick-target bremsstrahlung (Equation 2.33).

Brown et al. (2006 [26]), using synthesized electron spectra, study three inversion techniques: matrix inversion by data binning (Johns & Lin 1992 [84, 85]), forward fitting of spectra (Holman et al. 2003 [79]), and regularized matrix inversion (Piana et al. 2003 [127], Kontar et al. 2004 [94]). The authors conclude that, to varying degrees for the different methods, inversion can reproduce large-scale features of electron spectra, although some details are often lost.

Figure 2-2 shows an example of a beam electron distribution. This distribution is composed of two power-laws above and below a value E_c , commonly referred to as the cut-off energy (the reason it's called a cut-off is because one of the commonly assumed distributions has no electrons below that energy, as in Section 2.2.1). The slope of the power-law, in log-log space, is referred to as the spectral index δ above the cut-off (and, if necessary, ϕ below the cut-off). Finally, the height of the distribution is determined by equating the energy flux being carried by the beam, F_0 , with the first moment of the electron distribution, although the height has been normalized to 1 in the diagram.

In order to study heating by a beam of electrons, a heating function and associated bremsstrahlung emissions must be calculated. Thus, several forms of electron distributions are now derived so that heating

Figure 2-2: A sample electron distribution as a function of energy. This distribution is of the shape that will be referred to as a “knee” distribution (meaning an index $\phi = 2$, see Section 2.2.2). This distribution has a low-energy cut-off of 25 keV (marked by the dashed line), a low-energy spectral index ϕ of 2, and a high-energy spectral index δ of 5. The height has been normalized to 1, although this would normally be determined by equating the first moment of the distribution with the energy flux F_0 carried by the beam.

functions and emissions can be calculated within a numerical model.

2.2.1 Sharp Cut-off

First, the electron distribution for a sharp cut-off, *i.e.*, no electrons below the cut-off energy, is derived. This distribution is the most commonly assumed form of an electron beam (Holman et al. 2011 [78]), due to uncertainties below the cut-off. In other words, the electron distribution $\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t)$ is of the form

$$\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) \propto F_0(t) \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } E_0 < E_c \\ \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} & \text{if } E_0 \geq E_c \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

where $F_0(t)$ is the energy flux carried by the beam, δ is the spectral index of the power-law, E_0 is the initial energy of a given electron, and E_c is the cut-off energy. The first moment of this distribution should be equivalent to the energy flux $F_0(t)$, which can be used to find the preceding constants. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^\infty \mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) dE_0 &= \frac{F_0 K}{E_c^{-\delta}} \int_{E_c}^\infty E_0^{1-\delta} dE_0 & (2.10) \\ &= F_0 K \frac{E_c^2}{\delta - 2} \\ &= F_0 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $K = \frac{\delta-2}{E_c^2}$ and the distribution is found to be given by:

$$\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) = \frac{F_0(t)}{E_c^2} (\delta - 2) \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } E_0 < E_c \\ \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} & \text{if } E_0 \geq E_c \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

From this distribution, one can find the average energy of the electrons in the beam (necessary for accurate evaluation of the heating function, see below). Thus, from the definition of an average value:

$$\langle E \rangle = \frac{\int_0^\infty E \mathfrak{F}(E) dE}{\int_0^\infty \mathfrak{F}(E) dE} = \left(\frac{\delta - 1}{\delta - 2} \right) E_c \quad (2.12)$$

2.2.2 Low-energy power-law

Now suppose that the low-energy part of the distribution of electrons is described by a monotonically increasing power-law, that is, for some ϕ :

$$\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) \propto F_0(t) \begin{cases} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^\phi & \text{if } E_0 < E_c \\ \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} & \text{if } E_0 \geq E_c \end{cases} \quad (2.13)$$

Following the same approach as above, one can then integrate the first

moment of this distribution to find:

$$\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) = \frac{F_0(t)}{E_c^2} \frac{(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{\delta + \phi} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^\phi & \text{if } E_0 < E_c \\ \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} & \text{if } E_0 \geq E_c \end{cases} \quad (2.14)$$

Three distributions of interest are then given by the values $\phi = \{0, 2, \delta\}$ (call them the plateau, knee, and symmetric distributions, respectively).

Similarly, the average energy of these distributions can be found:

$$\langle E \rangle = \frac{\int_0^\infty E \mathfrak{F}(E) dE}{\int_0^\infty \mathfrak{F}(E) dE} = \left(\frac{\phi + 1}{\phi + 2}\right) \left(\frac{\delta - 1}{\delta - 2}\right) E_c \quad (2.15)$$

2.3 Heating functions

The heating due to a beam of electrons, for the distributions found above, can now be derived. Assuming that the electrons deposit their energy by Coulomb collisions with an ambient hydrogen target, the analysis of Emslie (1978 [49]) can be used to calculate the heating as a function of position and time along a magnetic loop (assuming a constant cross-sectional area). Then, the heating functions can be used in combination with HYDRAD to run simulations under the assumption of the collisional thick-target model.

2.3.1 Sharp Cut-off

The simplest case is examined first, considered by Emslie 1978 [49]: the sharp cut-off (see also section 2.2.1). Beginning with Equation 34 of Emslie (1978 [49]), the heating for a beam of electrons depositing their energy through Coulomb collisions with a hydrogen target is given by the following integral:

$$H_{sharp} = Kn_H\gamma \int_{E^*}^{\infty} \frac{\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) dE_0}{\left[1 - (2 + \beta/2)\left(\frac{\gamma KN}{\mu_0 E_0^2}\right)\right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \quad (2.16)$$

where N is the column density, μ_0 is the cosine of the initial pitch angle, $K = 2\pi e^4$, $\beta = [2x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda'']/[\Lambda' + x(\Lambda - \Lambda')]$, $\gamma = x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda'$, x is the ionization fraction of hydrogen, and the Λ terms are effective Coulomb logarithms. We first note that the integral needs to be split into two separate cases. As noted by Emslie, electrons with initial energy lower than $E^* = [(2 + \beta/2)(\gamma KN/\mu_0)]^{1/2}$ will not contribute to the integral, although the integral is to be taken over all energies. To begin, the three effective Coulomb logarithms can be evaluated as follows (the analysis is based on Ricchiazzi 1982 [133]).

The first, due to interactions of beam electrons and protons, is

given by (Equation 8 of Emslie 1978 [49]):

$$\Lambda = \ln \frac{m_0 v^3}{\nu e^2} \approx \ln \frac{m_e v^3}{\nu e^2} \approx \ln \frac{\pi^{1/2} m_e^{3/2} v^3}{n_e^{1/2} e^3} \quad (2.17)$$

where m_e is the electron mass, $m_0 = \frac{m_e m_i}{m_e + m_i} \approx m_e$ is the reduced mass of the system, v is the electron velocity, e is the electron charge, and ν is the plasma frequency ($= (\frac{n_e e^2}{\pi m_e})^{1/2}$ for an electron number density n_e).

Taking the average electron energy to be $\langle E \rangle = \frac{1}{2} m_e v^2$, we can rewrite this as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda &= \ln \left[2 \langle E \rangle \left(\frac{2 \langle E \rangle}{m_e} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{\pi m_e}{n_e e^6} \right)^{1/2} \right] \\ &= \ln \frac{2^{3/2} \pi^{1/2}}{e^3} + 1.5 \ln \langle E \rangle - 0.5 \ln n_e \\ &\approx 66.0 + 1.5 \ln \langle E \rangle - 0.5 \ln n_e \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

Note that $\langle E \rangle$ must be in units of erg here.

The second logarithm, due to interactions between beam electrons

and neutral hydrogen, is given by (Equation 12 of Emslie 1978 [49]):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Lambda' &= \ln \frac{m_e v^2}{1.105 \chi_H} \\
 &= \ln \frac{2 \langle E \rangle}{1.105 \chi_H} \\
 &= \ln \frac{2}{1.105 \chi_H} + \ln \langle E \rangle \\
 &\approx 25.1 + \ln \langle E \rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

where $\chi_H = 13.6$ eV is the ionization energy of hydrogen.

Finally, the third effective Coulomb logarithm is (Equation 20 of Emslie 1978 [49])

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Lambda'' &= \ln \frac{v}{c\alpha} \\
 &= \ln \left[\left(\frac{2 \langle E \rangle}{m_e} \right)^{1/2} \frac{1}{c\alpha} \right] \\
 &= \ln \frac{2^{1/2}}{m_e^{1/2} c\alpha} + 0.5 \ln \langle E \rangle \\
 &\approx 12.3 + 0.5 \ln \langle E \rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.20}$$

where α is the fine-structure constant.

Now, following Emslie (1978 [49]), there are two separate cases of the integral: $E_c \leq E^*$ and $E_c > E^*$. Substituting the form of the electron distribution into Emslie's Equation 34, the derivation proceeds

as follows.

(a) $E_c \leq E^*$:

$$H_{sharp} = Kn_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \int_{E^*}^{\infty} \frac{dE_0 E_0^{-(1+\delta)}}{\left[1 - (2 + \beta/2) \left(\frac{\gamma KN}{\mu_0 E_0^2}\right)\right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \quad (2.21)$$

To simplify this integral, we make the substitution $y = (2 + \beta/2) \left(\frac{\gamma KN}{\mu_0 E_0^2}\right) = aE_0^{-2}$, such that $dE_0 = \frac{-dyE_0^3}{2a}$, and thus

$$\begin{aligned} H_{sharp} &= Kn_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \frac{a^{-\delta/2}}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{y^{\delta/2-1} dy}{(1-y)^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \quad (2.22) \\ &= Kn_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \frac{a^{-\delta/2}}{2} \left(\frac{2y^{\delta/2}}{\delta} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{2+\beta}{4+\beta}, \frac{\delta}{2}; \frac{\delta}{2} + 1; y\right) \Big|_0^1 \right) \\ &= Kn_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \frac{a^{-\delta/2}}{\delta} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{2+\beta}{4+\beta}, \frac{\delta}{2}; \frac{\delta}{2} + 1; 1\right) \end{aligned}$$

where ${}_2F_1(a, b; c; z)$ is the Gaussian hypergeometric function. This expression can be simplified through a few identities:

$${}_2F_1(a, b; c; z) = {}_2F_1(b, a; c; z) \quad (2.23)$$

$${}_2F_1(p, 1 - q; c; z) = pz^{-p} B_z(p, q) \quad (2.24)$$

$$B_1(p, q) = B(p, q) \quad (2.25)$$

where $B_z(p, q)$ is the incomplete Beta function and $B(p, q)$ is the com-

plete Beta function. We further define the stopping depth of an electron with energy E_c as $N_c = \frac{\mu_0 E_c^2}{(2+\beta/2)(\gamma K)}$, so that $\frac{a}{E_c^2} = \frac{N}{N_c}$. Combining all of the above, we find:

$$H_{sharp} = \frac{1}{2} K n_H \gamma (\delta - 2) \frac{F_0}{E_c^2} \left(\frac{N}{N_c} \right)^{-\delta/2} B\left(\frac{\delta}{2}, \frac{2}{4 + \beta} \right) \quad (2.26)$$

(b) $E_c > E^*$

In this case, the integral is identical to part (a), except that the lower limit becomes E_c . Thus, in a method parallel to that above, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{sharp} &= K n_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \int_{E_c}^{\infty} \frac{dE_0 E_0^{-(1+\delta)}}{\left[1 - (2 + \beta/2) \left(\frac{\gamma K N}{\mu_0 E_0^2} \right) \right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \quad (2.27) \\ &= K n_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \frac{a^{-\delta/2}}{2} \int_0^{N/N_c} \frac{y^{\delta/2-1} dy}{(1-y)^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \\ &= K n_H \gamma \frac{F_0 (\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}} \frac{a^{-\delta/2}}{2} \left(\frac{2y^{\delta/2}}{\delta} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{2+\beta}{4+\beta}, \frac{\delta}{2}; \frac{\delta}{2} + 1; y \right) \right) \Bigg|_0^{N/N_c} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} K n_H \gamma (\delta - 2) \frac{F_0}{E_c^2} \left(\frac{N}{N_c} \right)^{-\delta/2} B_{\frac{N}{N_c}}\left(\frac{\delta}{2}, \frac{2}{4 + \beta} \right) \end{aligned}$$

We have made use of the fact that $y(E_c) = aE_c^{-2} = \frac{N}{N_c}$. Note that the only difference between this form of the heating function and the previous one is that the Beta function is incomplete.

Before proceeding to the other distributions, it is important to

emphasize this functional form of the heating. Most importantly, the heating is dependent on the column depth of the plasma - as the beam particles stream through more and more material, they are more likely to be stopped and deposit their energy. This is important to emphasize because it implies that the majority of the heating will stream through the low-density corona, depositing their energy as the ambient density rises through the transition region into the chromosphere.

2.3.2 Low-energy Power-law

We now turn to the case of heating due to a beam of electrons with a low-energy power-law (as in section 2.2.2). The derivation is analogous to that of the previous section, beginning by substituting the relevant electron distribution into Equation 34 of Emslie (1978 [49]). Once again, we split into the cases $E_c \leq E^*$ and $E_c > E^*$.

(a) $E_c \leq E^*$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 H &= Kn_H \gamma \frac{F_0(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta}(\delta + \phi)} \int_{E^*}^{\infty} \frac{dE_0 E_0^{-(1+\delta)}}{\left[1 - (2 + \beta/2)\left(\frac{\gamma KN}{\mu_0 E_0^2}\right)\right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \\
 &= Kn_H \gamma \frac{F_0(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{2 E_c^2(\delta + \phi)} \left(\frac{N}{N_c}\right)^{-\delta/2} B\left(\frac{\delta}{2}, \frac{2}{4 + \beta}\right) \quad (2.28)
 \end{aligned}$$

where all of the algebra follows the same path as the previous section.

(b) $E_c > E^*$

In this case, the integral is split into the sum of two parts, an integral ranging from E^* to E_c and one from E_c to infinity. We therefore have the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 H = & K n_H \gamma \frac{F_0(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{E_c^{2-\delta} (\delta + \phi)} \\
 & \times \left[\int_{E^*}^{E_c} \frac{dE_0 E_0^{\phi-1}}{E_c^\phi \left[1 - (2 + \beta/2) \left(\frac{\gamma K N}{\mu_0 E_0^2} \right) \right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \right. \\
 & \left. + \int_{E_c}^{\infty} \frac{dE_0 E_0^{-(1+\delta)}}{E_c^{-\delta} \left[1 - (2 + \beta/2) \left(\frac{\gamma K N}{\mu_0 E_0^2} \right) \right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.29}$$

The second integral is the same as the case for a sharp cut-off, and has the solution $\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{N_c} \right)^{-\delta/2} B_{\frac{N}{N_c}} \left(\frac{\delta}{2}, \frac{2}{4+\beta} \right)$.

The first integral is similarly analytic, with solution $\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{N_c E_c} \right)^{\phi/2} \left[B \left(\frac{-\phi}{2}, \frac{2}{4+\beta} \right) - B_{\frac{N}{N_c}} \left(\frac{-\phi}{2}, \frac{2}{4+\beta} \right) \right]$. Note that the first argument of both beta functions in this solution is negative for electron distributions with $\phi > 0$, and thus the functions take complex values. The imaginary part of each of these functions will be equal, thus the solution remains real-valued. However, for ease of programming, rather than implement complex-valued beta functions, we choose to evaluate this integral with Gauss-Legendre quadrature (see Appendix A). We approximate the

integral thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \int_{E^*}^{E_c} \frac{dE_0 E_0^{\phi-1}}{E_c^\phi \left[1 - (2 + \beta/2) \left(\frac{\gamma KN}{\mu_0 E_0^2}\right)\right]^{\frac{(2+\beta)}{(4+\beta)}}} \quad (2.30) \\
&= \frac{1}{E_c^\phi} \int_{E^*}^{E_c} f(E_0) dE_0 \\
&\approx \frac{1}{E_c^\phi} \frac{E_c - E^*}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m w_i f\left(E_0 = \frac{E_c - E^*}{2} z_i + \frac{E_c + E^*}{2}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

where w_i and z_i are the Gaussian weights and nodes, respectively. This approximation can be used for any order of quadrature m . We can thus evaluate efficiently the heating due to a beam of electrons with a low-energy power law, for any power-law index ϕ .

2.4 Bremsstrahlung Emissions from Electron Beams

X-ray spectra in solar flares are generally dominated by bremsstrahlung emissions. At lower energies, so-called soft X-rays, the emission is primarily composed of thermal bremsstrahlung from extremely hot plasma. At higher energies, or hard X-rays, the emission becomes dominated by non-thermal bremsstrahlung emitted by beam electrons streaming past and colliding with the ambient plasma. In order to synthesize X-ray spectra from the models, therefore, it is necessary to accurately calculate these two sources of emission.

To evaluate the thermal bremsstrahlung emissions, we use Equations 1, 2, and 3 of Culhane & Acton (1970 [36]), derived for solar flares as observed at terrestrial distance. These equations include contributions from both free-free and free-bound emission. We approximate the emission measure by $\int_V n^2 dV \approx n_e n_H A \Delta s$, where A is an estimate of the cross-sectional area based on observations (and assumed to be constant) and Δs is the length of a given loop segment. Making these changes, we have, in units of photons $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{keV}^{-1}$:

$$I_{thermal} = 3.6 \times 10^{-39} \overline{Z^2} k_B^{0.3} T_e^{-0.2} \epsilon^{-1.3} \exp\left(\frac{-\epsilon}{k_B T_e}\right) \quad (2.31)$$

$$\times \left[1 - \left(\frac{\epsilon}{88.0}\right)^{k_B T_e/3}\right]^{-1} n_e n_H A \Delta s$$

where $\overline{Z^2} = 1.4$ is the average charge-squared of ions and ϵ is the emitted photon energy (in keV). Note that this function is only valid for photon energies $1.5 \leq \epsilon \leq 15$ keV (Culhane & Acton 1970 [36]), and is only valid for temperatures below about 20 MK. Outside of this range, we use the following expression, derived by combining Equations 1 and 1a of their paper:

$$I_{thermal} = 3.6 \times 10^{-39} \overline{Z^2} T_e^{-0.5} \epsilon^{-1.0} \exp\left(\frac{-\epsilon}{k_B T_e}\right) n_e n_H A \Delta s \quad (2.32)$$

These functions will give the emitted thermal bremsstrahlung at a given spatial location along the loop at a given time.

Non-thermal bremsstrahlung is more difficult to evaluate. It requires knowledge of the beam electron distribution function and the appropriate cross-section of interactions. Following either Holman et al. (2011 [78]) or Kontar et al. (2011 [93]), thick-target bremsstrahlung observed at terrestrial distance is given in general by (in photons $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{keV}^{-1}$):

$$I_{thick} = \frac{A}{4\pi R^2} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) \nu(\epsilon, E_0) dE_0 \quad (2.33)$$

where $R = 1.496 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}$ (1 AU), A is the loop area (cm^2), $\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t)$ is the electron flux spectrum of injected electrons (as before, although converted to units of electrons $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{keV}^{-1}$), E_0 is the initial electron energy, and ν (below) essentially gives the photon yield for a given electron in the thick-target model (this would be different in a thin-target model):

$$\nu(\epsilon, E_0) = \int_{E_0}^{\epsilon} \frac{n_H v Q(\epsilon, E) dE}{dE/dt} \quad (2.34)$$

for v the electron velocity, $Q(\epsilon, E)$ the cross-section of the interaction

($\text{cm}^2 \text{keV}^{-1}$), and $\frac{dE}{dt}$ the energy lost by the electron per unit time (keV sec^{-1}). Note that ν has units of photons $\text{electron}^{-1} \text{keV}^{-1}$. Following Holman et al. (2011 [78]), we take

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = n_H v \frac{dE}{dN} = n_H v \left(\frac{-2\pi e^4}{E} [x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda'] \right) \quad (2.35)$$

where we now evaluate over the column density, allowing for non-uniform ionization (with variables as defined in previous sections). Note that for unit consistency, e^4 must be in units of $\text{cm}^2 \text{keV}^2$ with E in keV.

Substituting in Equation 2.35 and reversing the order of integration in Equation 2.33:

$$I_{thick} = \frac{A}{8\pi^2 R^2 e^4 (x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda')} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \int_E^{\infty} \mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) dE_0 \quad (2.36)$$

where the inside integral is now analytic, allowing for easier numerical integration regardless of what form of cross-section is chosen. Evaluation of this integral is explained in detail below.

At the energies we are considering, an appropriate choice is the Bethe-Heitler cross-section (Bethe & Heitler 1934 [17], Koch & Motz 1959 [91], Johns & Lin 1992 [84, 85]), with the Elwert correction factor

(Elwert 1939 [48]), given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(\epsilon, E) = & \frac{16\overline{Z^2}r_0^2\alpha}{3} \frac{m_e^2c^4}{\epsilon E(E + 2m_e c^2)} & (2.37) \\
& \times \ln \left[\frac{1 + \left(\frac{(E-\epsilon)(E-\epsilon+2m_e c^2)}{E(E+2m_e c^2)} \right)^{1/2}}{1 - \left(\frac{(E-\epsilon)(E-\epsilon+2m_e c^2)}{E(E+2m_e c^2)} \right)^{1/2}} \right] \\
& \times \frac{[E(E + 2m_e c^2)]^{1/2}[E - \epsilon + m_e c^2]}{[(E - \epsilon)(E - \epsilon + 2m_e c^2)]^{1/2}[E + m_e c^2]} \\
& \times \frac{\left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{2\pi\alpha[E+m_e c^2]}{[E(E+2m_e c^2)]^{1/2}} \right) \right]}{\left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{2\pi\alpha[E-\epsilon+m_e c^2]}{[(E-\epsilon)(E-\epsilon+2m_e c^2)]^{1/2}} \right) \right]}
\end{aligned}$$

with α the fine-structure constant and r_0 the classical electron radius. This can then be numerically integrated to calculate the thick-target emissions with the use of Gauss-Laguerre and Gauss-Legendre quadrature, as appropriate (see Appendix A).

Evaluation of Equation 2.36 is now explained for the various cases of electron beams under consideration.

2.4.1 Sharp cut-off

First, note that the integral must be split into two cases: $\epsilon \geq E_c$ and $\epsilon < E_c$. This is because photons can only be emitted by electrons with greater energy than the photon energy.

In the first case, $\epsilon \geq E_c$, writing $K = 2\pi e^4 (x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda')$, the integral becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{thick} &= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2 K} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \int_E^{\infty} \frac{F_0(t)(\delta-2)}{E_c^2} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} dE_0 \\
&= \frac{A F_0(t)(\delta-2)}{4\pi R^2 K E_c^{(2-\delta)}} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \left(\frac{E^{(1-\delta)}}{\delta-1}\right) \\
&= \frac{A F_0(t)(\delta-2)}{4\pi R^2 K E_c^{(2-\delta)}(\delta-1)} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} E^{(2-\delta)} Q(\epsilon, E) dE \quad (2.38)
\end{aligned}$$

which can be evaluated with Gauss-Laguerre quadrature (see Appendix A), with the cross-section in Equation 2.38.

Similarly, in the case where $\epsilon < E_c$, the integral becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{thick} &= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2 K} \int_{E_c}^{\infty} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \int_E^{\infty} \frac{F_0(t)(\delta-2)}{E_c^2} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} dE_0 \\
&= \frac{A F_0(t)(\delta-2)}{4\pi R^2 K E_c^{(2-\delta)}(\delta-1)} \int_{E_c}^{\infty} E^{(2-\delta)} Q(\epsilon, E) dE \quad (2.39)
\end{aligned}$$

where the only difference between this and the previous equation is the lower limit of the integral (since there are no electrons with energy lower than E_c , the lower limit cannot extend down to the photon energy here). Thus, the thick-target bremsstrahlung due to a beam of electrons with a sharp cut-off can be evaluated rapidly using quadrature (see Appendix A), for any cross-section.

2.4.2 Low-energy power-law

The equations are similar, although a bit more complicated, for the case of a low-energy power-law. Once again, the integral must be split into two cases: $\epsilon \geq E_c$ and $\epsilon < E_c$. Beginning with the case $\epsilon \geq E_c$, the integral becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{thick} &= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2 K} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \int_E^{\infty} \frac{F_0(t)(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{E_c^2(\delta + \phi)} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} dE_0 \\
 &= \frac{A F_0(t)(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{4\pi R^2 K E_c^{(2-\delta)}(\delta + \phi)(\delta - 1)} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} E^{(2-\delta)} Q(\epsilon, E) dE \quad (2.40)
 \end{aligned}$$

which can be evaluated with Gauss-Laguerre quadrature (see Appendix A). In the case that $\epsilon < E_c$, the integral must be split into two parts since photons beneath the cut-off energy can still be produced by electrons with energy greater than it. These two subcases, which must be summed together, are thus $\epsilon \leq E \leq E_c$ and $E_c \leq E < \infty$. In the first

subcase, the integral becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{thick} &= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2 K} \int_{\epsilon}^{E_c} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \\
&\times \left(\frac{F_0(t)(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{E_c^2(\delta + \phi)} \left[\int_E^{E_c} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{\phi} dE_0 + \int_{E_c}^{\infty} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} dE_0 \right] \right) \\
&= \frac{A F_0(t)(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{4\pi R^2 K E_c^{(2-\delta)}(\delta + \phi)} \int_{\epsilon}^{E_c} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \\
&\times \left(E_c \left[\frac{\phi + \delta}{(\phi + 1)(\delta - 1)} \right] - \frac{E^{\phi+1}}{E_c^{\phi}(\phi + 1)} \right) \tag{2.41}
\end{aligned}$$

which, although complicated, can be readily integrated with Gauss-Legendre quadrature (see Appendix A). This must then be summed with the second subcase, for photons emitted by electrons with energy greater than E_c . That integral is then given by

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{thick} &= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2 K} \int_{E_c}^{\infty} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE \int_E^{\infty} \frac{F_0(t)(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{E_c^2(\delta + \phi)} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} dE_0 \\
&= \frac{A F_0(t)(\phi + 2)(\delta - 2)}{4\pi R^2 K E_c^{(2-\delta)}(\delta + \phi)(\delta - 1)} \int_{E_c}^{\infty} E^{(2-\delta)} Q(\epsilon, E) dE \tag{2.42}
\end{aligned}$$

which only differs from Equation 2.40 in the lower limit of the integral. Thus, the bremsstrahlung emissions from a non-thermal beam of electrons can be evaluated readily with these equations, for any given cross-section $Q(\epsilon, E)$, as appropriate.

2.5 Assumptions

In this section, several of the assumptions made by the model are listed. Their reasons and justifications are explained, and comparisons to observational values in real solar flares are given (when applicable).

I. The Model is One-Dimensional

The code HYDRAD and its equations assume that the coronal loops being modeled are one-dimensional, with all the physics being directed parallel to the magnetic field line. To justify this assumption, note that at coronal temperatures ($> 10^6$ K), constituent atoms of the plasma will be ionized (not necessarily fully ionized though). For example, in the corona, at temperatures above $10^{4.6}$ K, hydrogen will be fully ionized, while helium atoms will have lost both electrons at temperatures above $10^{5.2}$ K, while iron retains over half of its electrons at 10^6 K (see Mazzotta *et al.* 1998 [114]). Thus, the particles will be constrained to follow the magnetic field lines, according to the Lorentz force law. Since the corona has a low plasma β value (Figure 1-4), the magnetic field confines the plasma in narrow flux tubes, and there will be little cross-field transport. Further, the thermal conductivity parallel to the magnetic field far exceeds the conductivity perpendicular to the

field (Goedbloed & Poedts 2004 [66]). Thus, it will suffice to consider the particles as constrained to travel in one dimension, along the coronal loop.

Many models in the literature do not make this assumption, attempting to model loops in two or three dimensions (and even zero dimensions!). Each model makes a trade-off in either accuracy of resolution, calculation speed, physics, or some combination of all of these. For example, the EBTEL zero-dimensional model (Klimchuk et al. 2008 [90]; Cargill et al. 2012 [30]) trades spatial resolution and detailed physics for quick calculations that can be performed for thousands of loops, allowing for quick estimates of many parameters. Three-dimensional codes (e.g., Bifrost, Gudiksen et al. 2011 [68]) generally use fixed spatial resolution grids in their models (whereas HYDRAD uses adaptive resolution), which may under-resolve areas such as the transition region. Bradshaw & Cargill (2013 [19]) discuss the importance of spatial resolution in coronal loop models, importantly concluding that under-resolved loops will have much lower densities in the corona.

II. The Cross-Sectional Area of a Coronal Loop

The cross-sectional area of the loops in the model are assumed to be constant across the length of the loop. As noted in the introduc-

tion, some studies have shown that there is little variation of the area along the length of coronal loops (Klimchuk et al. 1992 [89]). Further, Klimchuk (2000 [87]) concludes that the cross-section of loops is approximately uniform on resolvable scales, a result strengthened by Lopez Fuentes et al. (2008 [107]).

III. The Single Loop Model

The loop is modeled with a single loop, and not an arcade of loops. Solar flares are extremely complex to model, requiring a treatment of a full arcade of loops each with their own heating and radiation that needs to be treated in full (Warren & Doschek 2005 [153]; Warren 2006 [151]). Although many flares develop a full arcade of loops, it is not clear how each individual strand is heated or if there is any interconnectivity. Warren (2006 [151]), for example, shows that for heating occurs on individual strands for around 200 seconds, whereas heating for about 20 seconds leads to temperatures and emissions inconsistent with Yohkoh observations.

RHESSI observations of foot-point spectra, from which electron spectra can be derived, are unable to distinguish spatially between loops in flares that form arcades. There are often multiple HXR foot-points, showing that multiple loops are being heated by non-thermal

electrons (Fletcher & Hudson 2002 [61]). For example, the 23 July 2002 flare shows three HXR chromospheric foot-point sources (and a coronal source, Emslie et al. 2003 [51]), showing that multiple loops comprise the flare. The derived electron spectra in this flare differ in all three foot-points (Emslie et al. 2003 [51]), so it is not clear what non-thermal energy would be delivered if a single loop model were used. In Chapter 3, a single loop model of this flare is used with RHESSI-derived parameters for the total flux spectrum (from Holman et al. 2003 [79]), which reproduces the light-curves well, although far from perfectly.

3 The Sensitivity of the *GOES* Flare Classification to the Properties of the Electron Beam

Note that this chapter is based on the publication Reep, Bradshaw, & McAteer (2013 [131]).

Solar flares are commonly classified in terms of their peak Soft X-ray (SXR) flux in the 1-8 Å band, as observed by the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) X-ray flux monitor at terrestrial distance (Garcia 1994 [64]). The largest flares, X-class, have peak fluxes greater than 10^{-4} W m^{-2} , with smaller flares classified by a decrease in peak flux by factors of 10 as M, C, B, and A-class. The flux in this GOES passband is determined primarily by a combination of thermal and non-thermal bremsstrahlung, and is therefore connected intimately with the properties of the beam of accelerated electrons.

A large number of flares (but not all) show the Neupert effect, which states that the fluence of the hard X-rays (HXR) is proportional to the flux of the SXRs, or equivalently, that the HXR flux is proportional to the time derivative of the SXR flux (Neupert 1968 [121]; Dennis & Zarro 1993 [42]; Veronig et al. 2005 [149]). In the thick-target model, the deposition of energy by the electron beam in-

duces the observed HXR bursts, subsequently ablating material into the corona and heating the plasma to produce the more gradual SXR light curves. Lee et al. (1995 [100]) demonstrate that the Neupert effect, combined with this model of chromospheric ablation, should lead to a linear proportionality between the non-thermal energy and the SXR flux; in contradiction to this, Warren & Antiochos (2004 [152]) show that the SXR flux (as seen by GOES) should be proportional to non-thermal energy $E^{1.75}$ (1-8 Å) and $E^{2.24}$ (0.5-4 Å).

In the last decade the Reuven Ramaty High-Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI; Lin et al. 2002 [103]) and more recently the Fermi Gamma-Ray Burst Monitor (GBM; Meegan et al. 2009 [116]) have provided excellent coverage of soft and hard X-ray spectra in flares. The spectra obtained with these instruments can be used to derive the properties of electron beams through various inversion methods (Brown et al. 2003 [27]; Kontar et al. 2011 [93]). The basic method involves inverting the equation relating an observed intensity to parameters of the electron beam (see Equation 2.33) to solve for the mean electron distribution function (see for example, Holman et al. 2003 [79]; Kontar et al. 2003 [92]; Piana et al. 2003 [127]). Brown et al. (2006 [26]) evaluate four different methods of inversion, concluding that all of the

methods recover the general magnitude of a given distribution but have trouble recovering sharp features.

Electron beams are primarily characterized by three parameters: the energy flux of the electrons, the spectral index of the electron distribution, and the low-energy cut-off of that distribution. The primary hindrance in determining the electron distribution accurately is the low-energy cut-off. At low energies, thermal bremsstrahlung masks the non-thermal component, rendering accurate determination of the cut-off difficult (Holman et al. 2011 [78]; Kontar et al. 2011 [93]). Further, most studies assume a simple power-law with a sharp cut-off for the electron distribution, although it is not clear that this model is correct (Saint-Hilaire & Benz 2005 [135]; Holman et al. 2011 [78]).

Numerous models have been developed to study heating processes in solar flares. Nagai (1980 [119]) developed a 1D hydrodynamic model of loops heated by a thermal conduction front to study the formation of SXR emission in flares. Later models, using the heating function derived by Emslie (1978 [49]), explored the hydrodynamic response of the solar atmosphere to a non-thermal beam of electrons (Nagai & Emslie 1984 [120]; MacNeice et al. 1984 [109]; Mariska et al. 1989 [111]). Most of these studies assumed heating lasted for less than a minute,

with fixed beam parameters. However, using results from RHESSI, a model can be developed that combines time-dependent beam properties with an advanced hydrodynamic model to forward model spectra and study the effects of an electron beam on observed spectra directly.

In this chapter, the sensitivity of the GOES classification to the beam properties is examined. A numerical model is used to explore the effect of varying each of the beam parameters on light curves as measured by GOES. In Section 3.1 the electron beam distribution and the specific assumptions made in this chapter are explained, and in Section 3.2 the calculation of bremsstrahlung emissions and the synthesis of GOES light curves from the simulations are described. In Section 3.3 the results of 60 numerical experiments to explore the correlation of GOES classification to each beam parameter derived for two flares observed by RHESSI are then presented.

3.1 Electron Beam and Assumptions

The work presented here has been performed using the HYDRAD code, which solves the hydrodynamic equations for an isolated magnetic flux tube and a multi-fluid plasma Bradshaw & Cargill (2013 [19]). The equations (conservation of mass, momentum, and energy) and assump-

tions are detailed in the appendix of Bradshaw & Cargill (2013 [19]). However, there have been a number of important improvements to the code.

First, the pre-flare atmosphere is now based on the VAL model C of the photosphere and chromosphere (Vernazza et al. 1981 [146]), allowing for more realistic temperature and density profiles in the lower solar atmosphere. The density distribution was recalculated so that hydrostatic equilibrium is consistent with the average particle mass chosen for the model ($m_i = 2.171 \times 10^{-24}$ g), which accounts for the relative abundances of hydrogen, helium, and heavier elements (roughly 90% hydrogen and 10% helium). The initial transition region and corona are derived by integrating the hydrostatic equations from the top of the VAL C atmosphere to the apex of the coronal loop.

Second, the code has been modified to allow for the presence of neutrals in the lower atmosphere. The two fluids in the code are now electrons and hydrogen atoms (which includes ions and neutrals), with trace amounts of electrons due to ionization of heavier elements. The energy equations have been modified in a manner similar to MacNeice et al. (1984 [109]) to include the ionization of hydrogen to account for the effects of neutrals on energy balance between the two fluids (e.g.,

via collisions and thermal conduction of neutrals, Orrall & Zirker 1961 [123]).

Finally, the chromospheric radiative energy balance is now based on the recipe derived by Carlsson & Leenarts (2012 [32]), which accounts for cooling from optically thick lines and continua, heating due to the same processes, and heating due to coronal radiation (back-warming from the hot corona). Their ionization balance is used to calculate the electron number density (n_e), for consistency with this radiation calculation. Figure 3-1 shows the lower atmosphere density and temperature profiles at the start of Run 1. Initially, the hydrogen and electron temperatures are taken to be equal (thermal equilibrium), while the electron density is lower than that of hydrogen since the lower atmosphere is not fully ionized.

The loop geometry is semi-circular, along the field-aligned direction. The initial temperature and density profiles were found by integrating the hydrostatic equations from the chromosphere (VAL model C, Vernazza et al. 1981 [146]) to the apex of the coronal loop (as done, for example, in Aschwanden et al. 2001 [9]). The electron and ion populations were assumed to be in thermal equilibrium at the beginning of simulations. The loops are cool and tenuous, before significant

Figure 3-1: *Left:* The temperature profile in the lower atmosphere at the start of Run 1 (in the field-aligned direction). The hydrogen and electron temperatures were initially equal. *Right:* The density profile in the lower atmosphere at the start of Run 1. Note that in the lower atmosphere, hydrogen is not fully ionized, so that the electron density is lower.

heating drives chromospheric ablation (compare, *e.g.*, MacNeice et al. 1984 [109]; Nagai & Emslie 1984 [120]; Mariska et al. 1989 [111]).

A modified form of the beam heating function derived by Emslie (1978 [49]) has been implemented in HYDRAD. Following Mariska et al. (1989 [111]) and Li (1991 [102]), a low-energy knee is added to the beam electron distribution while keeping the total beam energy constant (also compare the simulations of Warren 2006 [151]). In other words, an electron distribution in the same form as Equation 2.14 is chosen, with $\phi = 2$. As the aforementioned authors note, this form of the electron distribution produces smoother temperature and density variations than a sharp cut-off, without significantly altering the X-ray spectrum (see Sections 3.3 and 3.4 of Holman et al. 2011 [78] for comparisons of different shapes of low-energy cut-offs). The distribution function becomes:

$$\mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) = \frac{4(\delta - 2)F_0(t)}{(\delta + 2)E_c^2} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^2 & \text{if } E_0 \leq E_c \\ \left(\frac{E_0}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} & \text{if } E_0 \geq E_c \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

where δ is the spectral index above the cut-off energy, E_c , and $F_0(t)$ is the energy flux of the beam as a function of time ($\text{erg sec}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$).

The usual caveats apply to this distribution: the number of electrons accelerated is extremely high, there may be instabilities due to Langmuir wave generation, and there may be a return current generated (see Brown & Melrose 1977 [28] for more information). We can then use the equations derived in Section 2.3.2 to calculate the heat input as a function of time and position.

Following the ideas of Hawley & Fisher (1994 [75]), we generalize the heating equation to non-uniform ionization, which is important for recovering spectral breaks in observed spectra. As noted by those authors, the heating rate is fairly insensitive to the quantity β , but it must be constant to integrate Equation 26 of Emslie (1978 [49]). Therefore, we assume that $\beta = 2$ (corresponding to a fully ionized plasma, although we do *not* assume $x = 1$ in general) and integrate. Second, we modify the column depth to take into account the varying ionization structure (an equivalent ionized column depth, $N^*(N) = \int_0^N \frac{\gamma}{\Lambda} dN'$). The heating function in this form is then evaluated numerically as a function of time and position, given the beam parameters.

3.2 Calculating GOES emission

The geostationary satellite system known as GOES has been running since 1974, operated by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). As of this writing, there have been 15 total satellites launched, with 4 currently in operation. The next satellite is scheduled to be launched in early 2016. All of the satellites have an X-ray detector that has been monitoring the solar X-ray flux continuously in two broadband wavelength ranges, designed such that each detector has approximately the same sensitivity as all of the other satellites.

An important element of this work is predicting the GOES class of the model flares and so both thermal and non-thermal bremsstrahlung must be evaluated as a function of time. Note the following important properties of GOES relevant in evaluating this emission. (1) GOES observes in the bands 1-8 Å (1.55 to 12.41 keV) and 0.5-4 Å (3.10 to 24.82 keV), with flares being classified by the peak flux in the former. (2) GOES light curves are not spatially resolved; *i.e.* GOES does not distinguish coronal sources from foot-points. (3) GOES light curves are a summation of thermal and non-thermal bremsstrahlung, as well as background emission. Both thermal and non-thermal bremsstrahlung are evaluated everywhere along the flaring loop as a function of time

and then the emission is summed to construct a light curve in the native units of GOES (W m^{-2}).

To facilitate comparisons to observational data, the response of the GOES instrument must be accounted for in the bremsstrahlung calculations. Hanser & Sellers (1996 [71]) describe the response of the X-ray sensor (XRS) aboard GOES-8 in depth. Note that the sensitivity of the GOES XRS has remained nearly constant for each spacecraft. The response function (given by Equation 1 and Figure 3 of Hanser & Sellers 1996 [71]) is convolved with all bremsstrahlung calculations to improve estimates of GOES classification for the flares studied here.

3.3 Simulations

60 numerical experiments exploring the correlation of the GOES classification to the beam properties were performed. Two flares observed with RHESSI were studied, and the simulations were based on their parameters. The results are split into two sets. The first set is based on beam parameters for the 2002-04-15 M1.2 flare (Figure 3-2 and Table 3.1) derived by Sui et al. (2005 [138]), with a cut-off energy $E_c = 24$ keV, a spectral index $\delta(t)$ ranging between about 6 and 10, and a beam power ranging from approximately 6×10^{25} to 5×10^{27}

erg sec⁻¹ (see Figure 6 of their paper). The second set is based on 2002-07-23 X4.8 flare (Figure 3-3 and Table 3.2) derived by Holman et al. (2003 [79]), with a cut-off $E_c(t)$ ranging from about 18 to 43 keV, spectral index $\delta(t)$ ranging from about 2.5 to 8, and a beam power between 7×10^{26} and 2×10^{29} erg sec⁻¹ (see Figure 3 of their paper). In both cases, the beam parameters were derived from RHESSI observations of the flares. The geometry of the 2002-04-15 flare loop (that is, length and cross-sectional area) is based on the estimate of Veronig & Brown (2004 [148]). The length of the 2002-07-23 flare loop is estimated from the foot-point locations in Emslie et al. (2003 [51]); the area is estimated from Holman et al. (2003 [79]), decreased slightly to 7.0×10^{18} cm² to calibrate the base run (# 31) to the observed GOES classification.

In each group of simulations, one beam parameter is varied per simulation in the following way (holding all other values constant). First, the beam flux $F_0(t)$ is multiplied by a factor of [$\frac{1}{10}$, $\frac{1}{5}$, $\frac{1}{3}$, $\frac{1}{2}$, 2, 3, 5, 10]. Second, the spectral index of the electron distribution $\delta(t)$ is changed by a factor of by [-3, -2, -1, $-\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{2}$, 1, 2, 3] (although δ is limited to a minimum of 2.01 since it must be strictly greater than 2). Finally, the cut-off energy $E_c(t)$ is changed by [-20, -15, -10, -5, 5, 10,

Figure 3-2: The 15 April 2002 M1.2 flare. The left hand side shows the observed GOES flux at the time of the flare, while the right hand side shows a SOHO-EIT 195 Å image taken during the impulsive phase of the flare (23:36 UT). The red circle marks the active region where the flare occurred.

15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 75, 100] keV (limiting E_c to a minimum of 1 keV).

Table 3.1 summarizes the results for the set of simulations concerning the 2002-04-15 flare. Table 3.2 summarizes the results for the set of simulations concerning the 2002-07-23 flare. In both cases, the run number is listed along with the changes in the beam parameters, the GOES class (in both channels), the maximum temperature (in MK), and the maximum apex density (cm^{-3}).

For example, consider Figure 3-4, which shows the results of Run 1. The beam lasts 640 seconds, for a loop of length $2L = 77$ Mm. The

Run #	Flux	$\Delta\delta$	ΔE_c (keV)	GOES Class (1-8 Å)	GOES (0.5-4 Å)	T_{\max} (MK)	$n_{\text{apex,max}}$ (cm^{-3})
1	100%	+0	+0	M1.1	C3.1	27.3	6.3×10^{10}
2	10%	+0	+0	B5.1	B3.4	5.15	2.1×10^9
3	20%	+0	+0	B9.8	B6.7	8.20	5.6×10^9
4	33%	+0	+0	C1.6	C1.1	12.2	1.4×10^{10}
5	50%	+0	+0	C2.5	C1.7	17.2	2.7×10^{10}
6	200%	+0	+0	M4.5	M1.1	36.6	1.1×10^{11}
7	300%	+0	+0	M9.5	M2.5	42.6	1.5×10^{11}
8	500%	+0	+0	X2.4	M7.1	50.1	2.1×10^{11}
9	1000%	+0	+0	X10	X3.4	62.3	3.9×10^{11}
10	100%	-3	+0	C5.6	C4.8	22.2	4.6×10^{10}
11	100%	-2	+0	C7.4	C3.8	24.5	5.5×10^{10}
12	100%	-1	+0	C9.5	C3.3	26.3	6.1×10^{10}
13	100%	$-\frac{1}{2}$	+0	C9.1	C3.3	26.9	6.0×10^{10}
14	100%	$+\frac{1}{2}$	+0	M1.1	C3.1	27.9	6.4×10^{10}
15	100%	+1	+0	M1.2	C3.2	28.0	6.5×10^{10}
16	100%	+2	+0	M1.0	C3.0	27.9	6.3×10^{10}
17	100%	+3	+0	M1.1	C2.9	28.1	6.3×10^{10}
18	100%	+0	-20	C7.8	C1.3	32.2	5.7×10^{10}
19	100%	+0	-15	M1.2	C2.5	32.5	6.8×10^{10}
20	100%	+0	-10	M1.4	C2.9	32.1	7.1×10^{10}
21	100%	+0	-5	M1.3	C3.1	30.3	6.9×10^{10}
22	100%	+0	+5	C5.3	C3.8	22.5	4.8×10^{10}
23	100%	+0	+10	C5.7	C4.6	17.0	3.2×10^{10}
24	100%	+0	+15	C6.0	C5.1	13.2	1.6×10^{10}
25	100%	+0	+20	C6.3	C5.6	10.8	1.1×10^{10}
26	100%	+0	+30	C6.9	C6.5	8.13	5.8×10^9
27	100%	+0	+40	C7.8	C7.6	6.51	3.4×10^9
28	100%	+0	+50	C7.8	C7.9	5.45	2.5×10^9
29	100%	+0	+75	C8.2	C8.6	3.90	1.2×10^9
30	100%	+0	+100	C8.3	C9.1	3.09	9.0×10^8

Table 3.1: The results of simulations for the 2002-04-15 M1.2 flare. Run 1 uses beam parameters taken from Sui et al. (2005 [138]), while each other simulation modifies one beam parameter, as noted.

Run #	Flux	$\Delta\delta$	ΔE_c (keV)	GOES Class (1-8 Å)	GOES (0.5-4 Å)	T_{\max} (MK)	$n_{\text{apex,max}}$ (cm^{-3})
31	100%	+0	+0	X3.6	X1.1	28.0	1.4×10^{11}
32	10%	+0	+0	M1.2	C6.9	6.44	6.0×10^9
33	20%	+0	+0	M2.3	M1.3	11.3	1.8×10^{10}
34	33%	+0	+0	M4.7	M2.1	17.3	4.7×10^{10}
35	50%	+0	+0	M9.3	M3.5	21.7	7.5×10^{10}
36	200%	+0	+0	X14	X5.1	35.7	2.3×10^{11}
37	300%	+0	+0	X32	X8.4	40.6	3.2×10^{11}
38	500%	+0	+0	X80	X21	47.3	4.7×10^{11}
39	1000%	+0	+0	X300	X89	58.3	8.4×10^{11}
40	100%	-3	+0	X2.0	X1.2	23.8	8.1×10^{10}
41	100%	-2	+0	X2.7	X1.1	26.4	1.1×10^{11}
42	100%	-1	+0	X3.2	X1.1	27.3	1.2×10^{11}
43	100%	$-\frac{1}{2}$	+0	X3.4	X1.0	27.6	1.3×10^{11}
44	100%	$+\frac{1}{2}$	+0	X3.6	X1.1	28.2	1.4×10^{11}
45	100%	+1	+0	X3.5	X1.0	28.2	1.4×10^{11}
46	100%	+2	+0	X3.8	X1.0	28.5	1.5×10^{11}
47	100%	+3	+0	X3.7	X1.0	28.5	1.4×10^{11}
48	100%	+0	-20	M6.1	M2.7	18.1	6.4×10^{11}
49	100%	+0	-15	X2.6	M5.3	27.2	1.2×10^{11}
50	100%	+0	-10	X4.0	M8.7	29.9	1.5×10^{11}
51	100%	+0	-5	X3.9	M9.9	29.5	1.5×10^{11}
52	100%	+0	+5	X2.8	X1.0	26.5	1.2×10^{11}
53	100%	+0	+10	X1.5	X1.1	28.2	4.1×10^{10}
54	100%	+0	+15	X1.6	X1.2	15.7	4.3×10^{10}
55	100%	+0	+20	X1.7	X1.4	11.9	2.4×10^{10}
56	100%	+0	+30	X1.8	X1.7	8.26	1.1×10^{10}
57	100%	+0	+40	X2.0	X1.9	6.18	6.4×10^9
58	100%	+0	+50	X2.2	X2.1	5.04	4.3×10^9
59	100%	+0	+75	X2.3	X2.4	3.44	2.2×10^9
60	100%	+0	+100	X2.4	X2.6	2.64	1.5×10^9

Table 3.2: The results of simulations for the 2002-07-23 X4.8 flare. Run 31 uses beam parameters taken from Holman et al. (2003 [79]), while each other simulation modifies one beam parameter, as noted.

Figure 3-3: The 23 July 2002 X4.8 flare. The left hand side shows the observed GOES flux at the time of the flare, while the right hand side shows a SOHO-EIT 195 Å image taken during the impulsive phase of the flare (00:36 UT). The red circle marks the active region where the flare occurred.

upper panels show the electron temperature (reaching a peak of 27.3 MK) and density (with a maximum apex value near $6 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) as functions of position, at different times as indicated. The temperature rises for around 300 seconds, when the beam begins to weaken. There is significant radiative cooling in the chromosphere; in the corona, thermal conduction drives energy losses initially, gradually transitioning to radiative cooling as the density rises and temperature falls. The density in the corona rises due to chromospheric ablation throughout the duration of heating, and the maximum intensity occurs when the heating ceases (a few minutes after it reaches its maximum tempera-

ture). The center left panel similarly shows the heat deposition (which includes background heating). As the loop fills due to chromospheric ablation, the heat deposition occurs higher and higher in the corona as the mean-free path of beam electrons decreases. Although the beam continues for 640 seconds, the beam flux begins to fall around 300 seconds, and thus the heat deposition begins to fall. The center right figure shows the spectrum calculated at one of the footpoints at several selected times. Initially ($t = 150$ sec), the emission is entirely non-thermal bremsstrahlung, but as the loop begins to heat and fill, thermal bremsstrahlung eventually becomes the dominant component of the emission at lower energies (e.g., at 600 seconds, the thermal emission at 1 keV is more than 100 times stronger than the non-thermal emission). Finally, the predicted GOES light curve (with 1-8 Å in red and 0.5-4 Å in blue) is shown at bottom right, with the relative amounts of thermal and non-thermal bremsstrahlung indicated. The light curve (1-8 Å) peaks at $1.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ W m}^{-2}$, corresponding to M1.1, while the 0.5-4 Å component peaks at $3.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ W m}^{-2}$. The actual (background subtracted) GOES light curves, starting at 15 April 2002 23:07 UT, are overlaid for comparison (peaking at M1.1 and C2.0, respectively). The light curve is initially non-thermal bremsstrahlung, but as the loops

heats and fills up, thermal bremsstrahlung increases until it becomes the dominant component in the passband.

Similarly, Figure 3-5 shows the evolution of Run 31. The beam lasts for 1220 seconds, for a loop of length of $2L = 36$ Mm. The predicted light curve in this case peaks at $3.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (X3.6) in the 1-8 Å channel and $1.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in the 0.5-4 Å channel. As before, the temperature rises sharply due to the energy deposition, which then triggers chromospheric ablation. As the loop fills and heats up, the contribution of thermal bremsstrahlung to the light curve rises sharply. In this case, the loop begins to cool and drain before the beam ceases. In both cases, the GOES class is in approximate agreement with the observations. Note that the results are fairly insensitive to the initial density profile. If an initial coronal density of 10^{10} cm^{-3} had been assumed, over a loop length of 16 Mm, only electrons with energy < 12 keV would be stopped in the corona, and thus the majority of energy would still be deposited in the chromosphere (using the estimate of stopping depth from Nagai & Emslie 1984 [120]). Now consider what happens when altering the beam parameters one at a time, to examine their effect on the GOES class.

First, holding all other values constant, the beam flux is multiplied

Figure 3-4: Results for Run 1, beam parameters as given in Figure 6 of Sui et al. (2005 [138]). *Top Left*: Electron temperature vs position, with a select few times overlaid. *Top Right*: Electron density vs position. *Middle Left*: Heat input vs position. *Middle Right*: Predicted X-ray spectra of the flare, integrated over half of the loop. *Bottom*: Predicted GOES light curve, peaking at $1.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (M1.1) in the 1-8 Å channel and $3.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in the 0.5-4 Å channel. The observed GOES light curves, starting at 15 April 2002 23:07 UT, are overlaid (and have been background subtracted).

Figure 3-5: Results for Run 31, beam parameters as given in Figure 3 of Holman et al. (2003 [79]). *Top Left*: Electron temperature vs position, with a select few times overlaid. *Top Right*: Electron density vs position. *Middle Left*: Heat input vs position. *Middle Right*: Predicted X-ray spectra of the flare, integrated over half of the loop. *Bottom*: Predicted GOES light curve, peaking at $3.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (X3.6) in the 1-8 Å channel and $1.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in the 0.5-4 Å channel. The observed GOES light curves, starting at 23 July 2002 00:22 UT, are overlaid (and have been background subtracted).

by $[\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}, 2, 3, 5, 10]$ for both flares (equivalent to multiplying the total non-thermal energy by the same amount). There is a clear correlation between the GOES class and the beam flux (see the first plot in figure 3-6). For Runs 1-9, the GOES class Ψ (in the 1-8 Å channel) is found to be proportional to the beam energy E , such that $\Psi \propto E^\alpha$ for $\alpha = 1.71 \pm 0.084$; for Runs 31-39, an index $\alpha = 1.77 \pm 0.060$ is found. In the 0.5-4 Å channel, a similar trend is seen: for Runs 1-9, $\Psi \propto E^\alpha$ for $\alpha = 1.47 \pm 0.103$ and for Runs 31-39 $\alpha = 1.60 \pm 0.077$. In Runs 2-5 and 32-33 (and 34 in the 0.5-4 Å channel), the loops were not heated enough to produce significant thermal bremsstrahlung, and thus their GOES classes were primarily determined by non-thermal emissions. Note that non-thermal emissions are linearly proportional to the beam flux (Equation 2.33); if a line is fit to just Runs 2-5, the exponent is found to be $\alpha = 0.98 \pm .023$ in the 1-8 Å channel and $\alpha = 1.00 \pm 0.014$ in the 0.5-4 Å channel, confirming that the non-thermal emission is proportional to the mean beam energy. In all the other runs, the peak of the light curves was a combination of thermal and non-thermal emissions, with thermal emissions being indirectly related to the beam flux. If the simulations without thermal emissions are removed and then the correlation is recalculated, the following exponents are found:

$\alpha = 1.94 \pm 0.026$ (1-8 Å) and $\alpha = 2.04 \pm 0.054$ (0.5-4 Å) for Runs 1 and 6-9, and $1.91 \pm .014$ (1-8 Å) for Runs 31 and 34-39 and 1.84 ± 0.050 (0.5-4 Å) for Runs 31 and 35-39. Thus, the maximum GOES class Ψ is related to the total beam energy E , $\Psi \propto E^\alpha$ for $\alpha \approx 1.7$ (1-8 Å) and $\alpha \approx 1.6$ (0.5-4 Å). There are two reasons why the values differ slightly for each flare: different loop lengths and different cut-off energies, both of which affect the amount of heating and thus thermal bremsstrahlung produced.

This result should be compared to that of Warren & Antiochos (2004 [152]), who showed that $\Psi \propto E^{1.75}$ (1-8 Å) and $\Psi \propto E^{2.24}$ (0.5-4 Å) using simple analytic considerations. The present results are in agreement for the 1-8 Å channel, while they are in contrast in the higher energy channel. If the emission were entirely non-thermal, then a linear relationship would be found ($\Psi \propto E$, Equation 2.33), regardless of which channel is being considered. Since the 0.5-4 Å channel is more sensitive to higher energies, it would be expected for it to be closer to linear than the lower energy channel as it would be more sensitive to the non-thermal emissions, and thus the exponent α should be lower. The reason for this contrast is perhaps their use of the hydrostatic scaling laws derived for the corona, whereas the non-thermal emissions will be

primarily at chromospheric depths. It should also be noted that the current result, as well as that of Warren & Antiochos (2004 [152]), is in contrast to what is expected from the Neupert effect. As shown by Lee et al. (1993, 1995 [99, 100]) by using the Neupert effect relation, the maximum flux in the SXR's should be linearly proportional to the energy deposited by the electron beam. Warren & Antiochos (2004 [152]) suggest that this difference is due to the peak SXR flux being dependent upon other flare parameters, which will now be investigated.

Next, holding all the other values constant again, $[-3, -2, -1, -\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, 1, 2, 3]$ is added to the spectral index $\delta(t)$. Varying the spectral index of the electron distribution has only a small effect on the GOES class (see the second plot in Figure 3-6). For Runs 1 and 10-17, with a change of $\delta \pm 3$, the GOES flux (1-8 Å) varies by a factor of 2, and about a factor of 3 in the higher energy channel; for Runs 31 and 40-47, the flux varies by less than a factor of 2 in both channels. In all cases, though, an increase in the spectral index does increase the GOES class slightly in the 1-8 Å channel and decreases it slightly in the 0.5-4 Å channel. The reason is that an increase in the index reduces the proportion of high- to low-energy electrons, so that more energy is deposited higher up in the atmosphere, increasing the temperature and

Figure 3-6: The relations between GOES class and beam parameters. Each simulation (excluding the base case) varies one parameter at a time. *Top*: The correlation between beam flux and GOES class. *Middle*: The correlation between spectral index of beam electrons and GOES class. *Bottom*: The relationship between lower cut-off energy of beam electrons and GOES class.

thus the amount of thermal bremsstrahlung, while slightly reducing the non-thermal emissions. Thus, the channel which is more sensitive to thermal emissions increases slightly, and the channel more sensitive to non-thermal emissions decreases slightly.

The immediate question is whether this result is due to the assumed form of the beam electron distribution (*i.e.* the importance of the low-energy knee electrons). Runs 1, 10-17, 31, and 40-47 were repeated using a sharp low-energy cut-off ($\mathfrak{F}_0(E_0, t) = 0$ for $E_0 < E_c$), but equivalent amount of total beam energy (see Figure 3-7). Although the slopes are larger in this case, they remain small. The conclusion is unaltered: the spectral index only marginally affects the GOES class.

The primary reason that the spectral index minimally affects the GOES flux is because the total beam energy was held constant. Changing the spectral index is equivalent to slightly altering the proportion of high- to low-energy electrons, which in turn affects the mean location of energy deposition. Increasing the index decreases the number of high-energy electrons in the beam, which then causes deposition of energy slightly higher up the loop (and vice versa). Compare Dennis (1985 [41]), who found that the photon spectral index γ is not correlated to the peak HXR flux (and in turn, $\delta = \gamma + 1$, so that the relation holds

Figure 3-7: The change in the beam index versus maximum GOES flux, using a sharp low-energy cut-off instead of a low-energy knee. Compare to the second plot in Figure 3-6, which used a low-energy knee.

for the electron index as well). Also, consider the results of Falewicz et al. (2009 [53]), who found a small positive correlation between the spectral index and the 1-8 Å flux, similar to that of the present work.

The cut-off energy of the electron distribution can alter the GOES class significantly (see the third plot in Figure 3-6). Slight decreases in the cut-off increase the GOES flux, but large decreases will significantly decrease the GOES flux. On the other side, as the cut-off increases more and more, the energy is deposited deeper in the dense lower atmosphere, where there is a greater heat capacity and the energy is radiated away more quickly, leading to less heating, less thermal bremsstrahlung, and thus a lower GOES class in the 1-8 Å channel. In the 0.5-4 Å channel, increases in the cut-off increase the amount of non-thermal bremsstrahlung, so the flux in this channel tends to increase with higher cut-off energies. At extremely high cut-offs, the energy is deposited too low to heat the loop, so no thermal bremsstrahlung will be emitted; however, there will still be non-thermal emissions as the beam traverses the loop, which will be determined primarily by the energy flux in the beam. Eventually, as the cut-off is increased to large enough values, the emission in both channels will be entirely non-thermal bremsstrahlung, to which the higher energy channel is more

sensitive. As the cut-off decreases, more heat is deposited higher up, leading to a higher temperature and more thermal emission. If it decreases too much though, the beam is then essentially composed of thermal electrons, leading to less non-thermal bremsstrahlung emission and a lower GOES class (in both channels).

The cut-off energy is directly related to the location of energy deposition of the beam electrons. Nagai & Emslie (1984 [120]) give the mean stopping column density of an electron with energy E_c as $\approx 10^{17}[E_c \text{ (keV)}]^2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which can then be used to find the location of maximal energy deposition. Figure 3-8 shows the analytic and calculated location of maximal energy deposition as a function of time for Runs 1 and 20 in one half of the loop. In Run 20, it should be noted, the coronal density reached higher values and so the deposition location is in general higher than in Run 1, leading to more heating and more thermal bremsstrahlung, and thus a higher GOES class.

There is also a clear relation between the maximum temperature of a flare and the maximum GOES flux. Figure 3-9 shows the maximum electron temperature versus the maximum GOES flux found in the 60 simulations. There is a clear correlation between the two, although there are two separate trends for each group of 30 simulations. This

Figure 3-8: The location of maximal energy deposition for Runs 1 and 20 (left and right, respectively) in one half of the loop. The predicted curve uses the approximation for the mean stopping column density for an electron of energy E_c (Nagai & Emslie 1984 [120]).

is due to differences in the spectral index. The index was much higher at all times in the M1.2 flare, and thus more energy was deposited higher in the atmosphere, leading to consistently higher temperatures despite lower GOES classes. The spectral index therefore determines whether a flare will be thermally driven or beam dominated. Note, however, that in each case there is a horizontal branch extending to lower temperatures with roughly constant GOES flux. These branches are the cases where there are extremely high cut-off energies, which deposit their energy too low to heat the loop, but still produce roughly constant non-thermal emissions.

These results should be compared to Figure 6 and Equation 6 of Feldman et al. (1996 [54]), who found a similar trend, but significantly

lower temperatures. These lower temperatures result from the fact that they were measuring the temperature at the time of peak emission of the Fe XXV or Ca XIX channels of the Bent Crystal Spectrometer on SMM, which occurs after the time of maximum temperature (the density continues to rise). For example, in Run 1, the maximum temperature was 260 seconds into the flare, while the maximum intensity of the Ca XIX line occurred 500 seconds into the flare, a 4-minute discrepancy, by which time the loop had cooled by 7 MK (see Bradshaw & Klimchuk 2011 [21] for explanation of the forward modeling of spectral lines such as the Ca XIX line).

There is some observational evidence for cold flares, which have detectable GOES emission but low temperatures. For example, Fleishman et al. (2011 [60]) report a C-class flare with a maximum temperature of 6 MK. The authors suggest that the low temperature is due to a weak beam flux, which leads to little heating, so that the GOES emission would then be composed primarily of non-thermal bremsstrahlung. This explanation agrees with these results, where small beam fluxes produce low temperatures but emission detectable by GOES (see the lower left of Figure 3-9). One other possibility, which seems less likely, is that the flare had a large cut-off energy so that the energy was deposited

Figure 3-9: The maximum electron temperature attained in the 60 simulations versus the maximum GOES flux, in each channel. For both flares, there is a clear connection between the temperature and GOES flux in each channel, although the values differ between the two flares because of different loop lengths and cut-off energies. The horizontal branches at low temperatures and relatively high GOES fluxes are the simulations with extremely high cut-off energies, where the energy is deposited too low in the atmosphere to heat the loops.

deep in the chromosphere, once again leading to minimal heating but some emission in the GOES passbands nonetheless (as in the horizontal branches in Figure 3-9).

3.4 Summary & Conclusions

The effects of individual beam heating parameters on the GOES classification of solar flares have been investigated. Using two independent sets of observationally determined parameters, 60 numerical experiments have been performed, from which GOES light curves have been synthesized. Clear trends have been found between the beam parameters and the GOES flux. First, the GOES classification strongly depends on the total beam energy ($\Psi \propto E^\alpha$ with α around 1.7 in the 1-8 Å channel and around 1.6 in the 0.5-4 Å channel). This parameter dominates: the SXR spectrum is primarily determined by the amount of heat deposited in the solar atmosphere. Second, the spectral index of the beam electron distribution does not significantly alter the GOES class (whether the cut-off is sharp or a knee). There is a small positive correlation, though: an increase in δ slightly increases the GOES class. Finally, the cut-off energy, which determines the mean location of energy deposition of the beam, affects the amount of both the ther-

mal and non-thermal bremsstrahlung produced. Thus, changes to the cut-off can either increase or decrease the GOES flux, but it is not a simple relation, unlike the other two parameters.

As noted earlier, the Neupert effect predicts a linear relation between non-thermal energy and SXR flux ($\Psi \propto E$), which is in disagreement with the present results and those of Warren & Antiochos (2004 [152]). It has been shown that the GOES flux strongly depends on the cut-off energy of the electron beam as well. A change in the cut-off energy can alter the relation between non-thermal energy and SXR flux. Consider the case of an extremely high cut-off energy where there is little heating and thus little thermal bremsstrahlung: all the emission will be non-thermal, and thus a linear relation would follow (Equation 2.33). Although it seems unlikely that such extremely high cut-off energies occur, it is clear that the cut-off energy can affect the relation.

The parameters can be constrained as well. For example, Runs 38 and 39 have a GOES class larger than any flare ever observed, and thus can be discarded as unlikely to occur, setting an effective upper limit on the non-thermal energy budget in flares (the largest ever seen with GOES was around X40, Brodrick et al. 2005 [23]). The total

non-thermal energy in the 2002-07-23 flare was 2.6×10^{31} erg (Holman et al. 2003 [79]), so there is an effective upper limit around $\approx 7.5 \times 10^{31}$ erg (for similar cut-off energies). The extremely high cut-off energies used in some of the runs were also unrealistic. For example, Runs 55-60 are X-class flares with maximum temperatures beneath 10 MK, and densities too low to be observed, suggesting that such high cut-offs are not realistic (at least for the entire duration of the flare, there is some evidence that they may reach high cut-offs temporarily; Warmuth et al. 2009 [150]). The SXR spectrum is only one facet of emissions produced by solar flares, though.

In future work, extreme ultraviolet (EUV) spectra can be used to further constrain the model. The properties of EUV lines, such as widths, Doppler shifts, and intensities, can be predicted from the model and directly compared with observations to help pin down signatures of the fundamental driving mechanism of solar flares. For example, Tsurutani et al. (2005 [145]) point out that while the 4 November 2003 flare had the largest GOES flux ever measured, the 28 October 2003 flare was more intense in the EUV. The model developed here needs to be used to explain these differences as well.

4 On the Deposition of Energy by Electron Beams

To understand the physics underpinning the evolution of solar flares, it is necessary to understand the transport of mass, momentum, and energy through the solar atmosphere. At the beginning of a solar flare, energy released from the magnetic field will be partitioned between accelerating particles, heating the plasma *in situ*, and driving bulk motions in the plasma. The accelerated electrons will stream down the magnetic loop(s), depositing their energy into the denser parts of the atmosphere via collisions with the ambient plasma. This energy deposition in turn will drive an increase in the pressure of the chromosphere, causing an ablation of material and energy back into the corona (Antiochos & Sturrock 1978 [3]).

Under the thick-target model, all of the energy in an electron beam is deposited within the magnetic loop. The location of the energy deposition changes as the loop begins to fill due to chromospheric ablation and the material front advances into the corona, thus decreasing the mean-free path of the streaming electrons. As noted before, Nagai & Emslie (1984 [120]) showed that an electron with energy E_c will be stopped at a column density of around $\approx 10^{17}[E_c \text{ (keV)}]^2 \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Since this depth changes in time as the density of the loop changes, and since the beam properties evolve, the location of energy deposition can help to elucidate the dynamics of flaring loops. Note that this model necessarily assumes that the flare is compact and occurring on a single loop, whereas reconnection may drive the formation of many loops (see Section 6.2).

As energy is deposited in the chromosphere, the ablation of material back into the corona raises the density there. The speed at which the material travels has been found to differ significantly depending on the strength of the beam. Fisher et al. (1985 [57, 58, 59]) found that above a beam flux of about 10^{10} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻², the material from the chromosphere will explosively evaporate, *i.e.*, it will drive material up into the corona at a few hundred km sec⁻¹. This explosive evaporation also drives a downwards front towards the chromosphere, more slowly but with much greater mass (termed a chromospheric condensation). Below the explosive threshold, the material will slowly (≈ 30 km sec⁻¹) expand upwards, raising the density of the corona slightly.

However, Fisher et al. (1985 [57, 58, 59]) make a few assumptions that can be removed, or otherwise inspected more closely by the model developed in this work. They assume that the beams last for 5 seconds,

with a fixed energy flux, a fixed spectral index (4), and a fixed cut-off energy (20 keV), and they use a sharp cut-off distribution for the beam (Equation 2.11). It is not clear how consistent their results are for different values of the cut-off energy or for time-dependent values. One striking feature of Fisher et al.'s choice of values is that there is an abundance of very large electron energies, with none at energies below 20 keV. In many observed flares, however, there are accelerated electrons at energies as low as a few keV (e.g., O'Flannagain et al. 2013 [122]), so that their results would not apply.

With the advent of the RHESSI satellite (Lin et al. 2002 [103]), it has become routine to use observed bremsstrahlung emissions to derive the non-thermal electron distribution function from observations of solar flares (Brown et al. 2006 [26]). These electron spectra (e.g., Holman et al. 2003 [79]) can range in energy from a few keV to well over a few hundred keV. Because they are described by a power-law in general (with a negative slope), there will be significantly more low-energy electrons than high-energy electrons in the distribution.

It is interesting to consider the relative importance of high energy electrons versus low energy electrons in the heating of solar flares. In the extremely high energy limit, the stopping depth can reach deep into

the solar atmosphere, where the energy deposited will be radiated away almost immediately, or, due to the large heat capacity, the electrons will make only a negligible contribution to the total thermal energy of the plasma. In the previous chapter, for example, it was shown that having a cut-off energy of greater than 100 keV leads to essentially no rise in temperature in a flare. This implies that sufficiently high energy electrons contribute little to flare heating, and that low energy electrons dominate the energy deposition. The stopping depth of electrons is a simple function of energy (Emslie 1978 [49]), so that by knowing the range of electrons that dominate the heating, the primary location of energy deposition, and thus the source of mass up-flows, can be determined. In this chapter, the importance of electron energy on the dynamics of the flaring atmosphere is examined directly.

To do this, heating due to isoenergetic electron beams has been examined in depth. The idea is straightforward: if all the electrons in a beam are approximately the same energy, their stopping depth will be approximately equal. Any changes in the atmosphere's response can be attributed directly to electrons of that energy, and then contrasted with beams of different electron energy. In Section 4.1, the conditions for an isoenergetic beam are derived, which then form the basis of the

simulations in the rest of the chapter. In Section 4.2, simulations are performed to examine the atmospheric response to different isoenergetic beams. In Section 4.3, the importance of electron number flux is briefly examined. In Section 4.4, the threshold of explosive evaporation is examined at different cut-off energies. The main results are summarized in Section 4.5.

4.1 Isoenergetic Electron Beams

Consider the case where an electron beam consists of electrons at nearly the same energy E_c . Then, the vast majority of the energy will be deposited at the same location (same column depth). By examining many isoenergetic cases at different energies, the contributions of different parts observationally measured beams to the dynamics of a flare can be examined in detail.

For these isoenergetic beams, rather than use a delta function, a symmetric distribution is assumed (Equation 2.14 with $\phi = \delta$). The distribution function has a maximum at $E_0 = E_c$, dropping off as a power-law to either side of the maximum. Assuming that $x\%$ of electrons have energy within $\pm\Delta E$ of the maximum, the condition would

be:

$$\left(\frac{E_c + \Delta E}{E_c}\right)^{-\delta} = \frac{100 - x}{100} \quad (4.1)$$

Suppose the desired tolerance is that 99% of electrons are within this energy range. Then, the following condition must hold for 99% of electrons to have an energy within $\pm\Delta E$ of E_c :

$$\left(\frac{E_c}{E_c + \Delta E}\right)^{\delta} = \frac{1}{100} \quad (4.2)$$

Solving, the spectral index δ must meet the following condition for the beam to be approximately isoenergetic:

$$\delta = \frac{-2}{\log_{10}\left(\frac{E_c}{E_c + \Delta E}\right)} \quad (4.3)$$

For example, for a cut-off energy of 5 keV, a spectral index $\delta = 13.7$ is required for 99% of electrons to have energy within ± 2 keV of E_c (using Equation 2.15, the average energy is 5.08 keV). The numerator and the value ΔE can be altered to match the desired tolerance threshold to be called isoenergetic.

These equations are then combined with the previously derived heating functions and bremsstrahlung emission calculations (Chapter 2). Numerical simulations can then be run, and the dynamical response

of the solar atmosphere and its radiative emission can be examined in detail.

4.2 Isoenergetic Beam Simulations

Numerical experiments have been performed to examine in detail the response of the atmosphere to isoenergetic beams, to determine the importance of electrons at different energies. Table 4.1 shows the details of 24 simulations, with maximum beam fluxes below (10^9 erg sec^{-1} cm^{-2}), at (10^{10} erg sec^{-1} cm^{-2}), and above (10^{11} erg sec^{-1} cm^{-2}) the explosive evaporation threshold of Fisher et al. (1985b [58]). Each simulation assumes a cut-off energy E_c of [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50] keV, with spectral indices then derived from Equation 4.3 with a tolerance of ± 2 keV in all cases. The simulations were performed on loops of length $2L = 50$ Mm, with cross-sectional areas $A = 7.8 \times 10^{16}$ cm^2 . The beams lasted for 300 seconds, assuming a symmetric triangular time profile.

Consider the atmospheric response of Runs 9, 12 and 16, which had cut-off energies of 5, 20, and 50 keV, respectively. Figure 4-1 shows the electron densities (top row), electron temperatures (middle row), and bulk velocities (bottom row) in the three simulations for

Run #	E_c (keV)	$F_{0,max}$ (erg sec ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	δ	GOES Class (1-8 Å)	v_{max} (km sec ⁻¹)	T_{max} (MK)	$n_{apex,max}$ (cm ⁻³)
1	5	1.00×10^9	13.7	B1.7	338.1	13.3	9.2×10^9
2	10	1.00×10^9	25.3	C2.4	457.8	11.5	1.0×10^{10}
3	15	1.00×10^9	36.8	M1.0	157.7	4.5	2.1×10^9
4	20	1.00×10^9	48.3	M2.4	104.9	3.3	1.2×10^9
5	25	1.00×10^9	59.8	M3.4	72.1	2.6	9.1×10^8
6	30	1.00×10^9	71.4	M7.0	52.4	2.1	7.4×10^8
7	40	1.00×10^9	94.4	X1.4	38.0	1.6	6.1×10^8
8	50	1.00×10^9	117.4	X2.4	27.8	1.3	5.4×10^8
9	5	1.00×10^{10}	13.7	C1.7	576.3	26.2	5.6×10^{10}
10	10	1.00×10^{10}	25.3	M2.2	729.5	25.8	5.7×10^{10}
11	15	1.00×10^{10}	36.8	M8.0	837.2	24.7	6.1×10^{10}
12	20	1.00×10^{10}	48.3	X1.9	753.3	22.3	5.0×10^{10}
13	25	1.00×10^{10}	59.8	X3.9	601.4	17.8	5.2×10^{10}
14	30	1.00×10^{10}	71.4	X5.7	341.1	12.4	3.8×10^{10}
15	40	1.00×10^{10}	94.4	X13	195.2	5.6	3.2×10^9
16	50	1.00×10^{10}	117.4	X21	146.0	4.2	2.0×10^9
17	5	1.00×10^{11}	13.7	M2.1	965.3	47.6	1.6×10^{11}
18	10	1.00×10^{11}	25.3	X1.8	1057	52.6	2.8×10^{11}
19	15	1.00×10^{11}	36.8	X6.5	1121	51.8	3.2×10^{11}
20	20	1.00×10^{11}	48.3	X15	1204	51.1	3.1×10^{11}
21	25	1.00×10^{11}	59.8	X27	968.2	50.0	3.2×10^{11}
22	30	1.00×10^{11}	71.4	X42	1043	48.9	3.2×10^{11}
23	40	1.00×10^{11}	94.4	X84	880.5	47.0	3.2×10^{11}
24	50	1.00×10^{11}	117.4	X140	872.7	44.5	3.3×10^{11}

Table 4.1: The results of 24 simulations of isoenergetic electron beams. The first 8 simulations were performed with a maximum energy flux F_0 value of 10^9 erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻², so that they are beneath the explosive evaporation threshold, the second 8 are at the threshold, while the final 8 simulations are well above the threshold. The GOES intensities are listed (W m⁻²), along with the the maximum bulk flow velocity (km sec⁻¹), maximum electron temperature (MK), and maximum apex electron density (cm⁻³).

comparison. Comparing the density and velocity profiles shows that Run 9 (first column) quickly develops very strong upflows of material in under 30 seconds, even though the maximum of the beam flux occurs at 150 seconds. Essentially, although most of the energy is deposited in the chromosphere, a significant fraction of electrons are depositing their energy in the corona (see Figure 4-3, below), which quickly raises the temperature above 10 MK and drives a strong thermal conduction front. The combination of chromospheric energy deposition and the conduction front causes a large, explosive ablation of material back into the chromosphere, leading to velocities up to 576 km sec^{-1} . Compare this with Run 12 (middle column), which had much less coronal energy deposition, and thus does not heat up as quickly. Instead, the electrons in this simulation heat the chromosphere directly, so that evaporation starts later than in Run 9 (although it reaches higher velocities). At later times, as the corona fills, the electrons no longer stream directly through, so that they start depositing their energy *in situ*. Finally, consider Run 16 (right column), with a cut-off of 50 keV, so that the electrons travel essentially collisionlessly through the corona at all times in the simulation. The result is that there is no heating in the corona, and because higher energy electrons deposit their energy deeper down,

Figure 4-1: The electron density (top row), electron temperature (middle row), and bulk flow velocity (bottom row) in Runs 9 (left column), 12 (middle column), and 16 (right column). The simulations had equal energy fluxes, at the explosive threshold of Fisher et al. (1985a [57]), and cut-off energies of 5, 20, and 50 keV, respectively.

the heat capacity is significantly higher so that there will be a much smaller pressure increase. There is very little ablation of material, and the density and temperature only rise slightly from their initial values.

Figure 4-2 similarly compares Runs 17, 20, and 24. At the end of the heating, the three simulations have similar densities (just over 10^{11} cm⁻³ at the apex) and similar temperatures (≈ 50 MK). In Run

17, as with Run 9, large upflows develop in under 30 seconds, quickly raising the coronal density and temperature. The coronal temperature quickly rises above 10 MK, driving a thermal conduction front down, which combined with the chromospheric energy deposition, drives a very strong ablation of material. The heating becomes more and more localized to the apex (see Figure 4-3), as the flows slow and the density reaches its peak. In Run 20, the energy is primarily deposited in the chromosphere, which drives an explosive evaporation upwards. Although the flows take more time to develop than in Run 17, they carry a similar amount of material into the corona, filling and heating it drastically. Finally, in Run 24, the behavior is completely different from Run 16. Now, the heat flux deposited in the chromosphere is large compared to the thermal energy at that depth and the excess energy cannot be radiated away fast enough, so that the pressure rises immensely (note the chromospheric temperature spikes at 60 seconds). The flows in this simulation begin around 60 seconds into the simulation, quickly raising the coronal density nearly three orders of magnitude thereafter.

To elucidate the differences between the beams and the resultant atmospheric response, consider the energy deposition in the simulations. Figure 4-3 shows the energy deposition in 9 of the simulations:

Figure 4-2: The electron density (top row), electron temperature (middle row), and bulk flow velocity (bottom row) in Runs 17 (left column), 20 (middle column), and 24 (right column). The simulations had equal energy fluxes, above the explosive threshold of Fisher et al. (1985a [57]), and cut-off energies of 5, 20, and 50 keV, respectively.

Runs 1, 4, 8 (top, left to right), 9, 12, and 16 (center, left to right), and 17, 20, and 24 (bottom, left to right). A few properties are readily apparent in these beams. First of all, the lower the cut-off energy, the more the energy deposition becomes localized near the apex. This is in agreement with the predictions of Nagai & Emslie (1984 [120]), and clearly shows that the highest energy electrons will stream through the corona. Secondly, the higher the beam flux, the more localized the energy deposition will become as the corona becomes denser and the mean free paths of electrons shorten. Compare the energy deposition in Runs 1, 9 and 17, which quickly become localized near the apex of the loop, although Run 1 is more spread out spatially at all times than Run 9, which is more spread out than Run 17. Note that, even though Run 1 is supposed to be below the explosive evaporation threshold of Fisher et al. (1985 [57]), the evaporation here is actually explosive. Since the electrons are low energy, a significant amount of their energy will be deposited in the corona, which will drive a thermal conduction front, further increasing the chromospheric pressure. These results indicate the threshold is a function of cut-off energy, which will be examined later in this chapter.

There are significant differences for the three groups of simulations.

Figure 4-3: Energy deposition as a function of time and position in 6 of the simulations. At top, Runs 1, 4, 8, with a maximal beam flux of $10^9 \text{ erg sec}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and cut-off energies of 5, 20, 50 keV, respectively. At center, Runs 9, 12, 16, with a maximal beam flux of $10^{10} \text{ erg sec}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and cut-off energies of 5, 20, 50 keV, respectively. At bottom, Runs 17, 20, 24, with a maximal beam flux of $10^{11} \text{ erg sec}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and cut-off energies of 5, 20, 50 keV, respectively.

For those simulations below the explosive evaporation threshold, both the temperature and density are strongly dependent on the energy E_c . Figure 4-4 shows the apex electron temperature, apex electron density, and maximal bulk flow velocity as functions of time for Runs 1-8. In Runs 1 and 2, the bulk flows develop in a short amount of time, and reach velocities of a few hundred km sec^{-1} , while in the other runs, the flows are much slower. Runs 1 and 2 accordingly reach much higher densities than the other six runs. The up-flowing material in Runs 1 and 2 brings a significant enthalpy flux into the corona, leading to increased coronal heating, compared to the Runs 3-8.

Similarly, Figure 4-4 shows the apex electron temperature, apex electron density, and maximal bulk flow velocity as functions of time for Runs 9-16. It is clear that lower energy electrons, which deposit their energy higher up in the loop, cause a larger increase in temperature, which then drives a stronger evaporation front and leads to higher densities. Higher energy electrons deposit their energy deeper in the chromosphere, where the ambient density is much larger and therefore has a larger heat capacity and stronger radiative losses. Thus, the higher energy electrons will not cause as sharp a rise in temperature in the coronal part of the loop. In addition, the time it takes for significant

Figure 4-4: How the temperature, density, and bulk flow velocity vary for Runs 1-8 in Table 4.1. *Top Left:* The apex electron density in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Top Right:* The apex electron temperature in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Bottom:* The maximum of the bulk flow velocity as a function of time (for the first 300 seconds).

flows to develop is strongly dependent on the cut-off energy. There is a clear trend showing that lower energy electrons cause upflows to develop faster than higher energy electrons (note the times of peak velocity in the plot). There are two possible reasons. First, it could be that higher energy electrons are stopped lower in chromosphere where the heat capacity is higher, and so more total energy needs to be deposited before the pressure rises enough to drive ablation into the corona. It is also possible that because lower energy electrons heat lower density plasma, which has less inertia, so that the flows develop sooner. At very late times (≈ 1200 sec), the loops in Runs 9-14 catastrophically cool, as they become unable to sustain the cooling through radiation and enthalpy losses (Cargill & Bradshaw 2013 [31]).

The results are completely different in the case where the energy flux F_0 of the beam is above the explosive evaporation threshold (Runs 9-16). Figure 4-6 similarly shows the apex electron density and apex electron temperature as functions of time for these simulations. In this case, the densities and temperature are very nearly equal in all 8 simulations (in fact, the lowest temperature and density are from Run 9 which has the lowest energy electrons). Because the energy flux is extremely large, there is enough energy to heat the chromosphere and cause a

Figure 4-5: How the temperature, density, and bulk flow velocity vary for Runs 9-16 in Table 4.1. *Top Left:* The apex electron density in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Top Right:* The apex electron temperature in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Bottom:* The maximum of the bulk flow velocity as a function of time (for the first 300 seconds).

large rise in the pressure, which then drives an evaporation front, even for the high energy electrons that are stopped much deeper in the chromosphere. As with the previous diagram, lower energy electrons cause upflows to develop sooner than higher energy electrons (once again, compare the times at which the velocity peaks for each cut-off energy). Similarly to the previous case, at around 900 seconds, the loops in all 8 simulations catastrophically cool and collapse (Cargill & Bradshaw 2013 [31]).

These results suggest important conclusions. First, for beams above the explosive evaporation threshold, the final state of the atmosphere is not strongly dependent on the electron energy. In Runs 17-24, the maximum apex densities and temperatures are nearly identical. Below the evaporation threshold, however, lower energy electrons are more efficient at heating the corona, leading to higher maximum temperatures. Second, lower energy electrons which deposit their energy higher in the atmosphere drive ablation into the corona sooner than higher energy electrons. They do not necessarily, however, drive upflows with higher velocities. Finally, the explosive evaporation threshold found by Fisher et al. (1985a [57]) is dependent on the cut-off energy, a point that they note in their paper but do not examine in detail (they assume

Figure 4-6: How the temperature, density, and bulk flow velocity vary for Runs 17-24 in Table 4.1. *Top Left:* The apex electron density in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Top Right:* The apex electron temperature in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Bottom:* The maximum of the bulk flow velocity as a function of time (for the first 300 seconds).

a constant 20 keV). The results here suggest that the threshold could be lower for lower energy cut-offs (see Section 4.4).

4.3 Isoenergetic Beams with a Constant Number Flux

There is an additional possibility worth considering: to what extent does the number of electrons in the beam matter? In the previous examples, beams with cut-off energies E_1 and E_2 such that $E_1 > E_2$, with equal total energy will have different numbers of electrons. In this case, the second beam will have a larger number of lower energy electrons and the first beam will have a smaller number of higher energy electrons. Since beams composed of lower energy electrons appear to heat loops more efficiently, then what role does the electron number flux play? This question is examined here.

To begin, the necessary conditions for two beams to have equal number fluxes are derived. Assume that there are two isoenergetic beams, each of different electron energy E_1 and E_2 , such that $E_1 > E_2$. The number flux \mathcal{N} in each is given by the zeroth moment of the

distribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{N} &= \int_0^\infty \mathfrak{F}_0(E_0, t) dE_0 \\
&= \frac{F_0}{E_c^2} \frac{(\delta + 2)(\delta - 2)}{2\delta} \left[\int_0^{E_c} \frac{E_0^\delta dE_0}{E_c^\delta} + \int_{E_c}^\infty \frac{E_0^{-\delta} dE_0}{E_c^{-\delta}} \right] \\
&= \frac{F_0}{E_c} \frac{(\delta + 2)(\delta - 2)}{(\delta + 1)(\delta - 1)} \tag{4.4}
\end{aligned}$$

Then, equate \mathcal{N}_1 with \mathcal{N}_2 so that the two beams have the same number of electrons. Note that since $E_1 \neq E_2$, the spectral index of each differs as well.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{N}_1 &= \mathcal{N}_2 \\
\frac{F_1}{E_1} \frac{(\delta_1 + 2)(\delta_1 - 2)}{(\delta_1 + 1)(\delta_1 - 1)} &= \frac{F_2}{E_2} \frac{(\delta_2 + 2)(\delta_2 - 2)}{(\delta_2 + 1)(\delta_2 - 1)} \tag{4.5}
\end{aligned}$$

where the underscores 1 and 2 refer to each separate beam. The condition for equal number flux is thus found to be:

$$F_1 = F_2 \frac{E_1}{E_2} \frac{(\delta_2 + 2)(\delta_2 - 2)}{(\delta_2 + 1)(\delta_2 - 1)} \frac{(\delta_1 + 1)(\delta_1 - 1)}{(\delta_1 + 2)(\delta_1 - 2)} \tag{4.6}$$

Therefore, given an energy flux for an isoenergetic beam (of cut-off E_1 and index δ_1), the energy flux carried by a different isoenergetic beam (of cut-off E_2 and index δ_2) can then be determined such that they have

an equal number of electrons. To explore the importance of number flux on the dynamics of flaring loops, simulations have been performed using these equations to determine the electron beam properties.

8 simulations have carried out and Table 4.2 displays the key results. Each simulation is assumed to be an isoenergetic beam with 99% of its electrons within ± 2 keV of a cut-off energy [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50] keV. The spectral indices are therefore determined by Equation 4.3.

In the previous section, it was found that the final state of the atmosphere does not depend strongly on electron energy if the energy flux is above the explosive evaporation threshold. So, the first simulation, with a cut-off energy of 5 keV, is assumed to have a maximal beam flux $F_0 = 10^{10}$ erg cm⁻² sec⁻¹, which is the canonical explosive evaporation threshold (see Fisher et al. 1985b [58]). The simulations were done on loops of length $2L = 50$ Mm, with a cross-sectional area $A = 7.8 \times 10^{16}$ cm².

Figure 4-7 shows the evolution of the density, temperature, and bulk flow velocity as a function of time in the 8 simulations. The top left hand side of the figure shows the apex electron density in each simulation, while the top right hand side shows the apex electron tem-

Run #	E_c (keV)	$F_{0,max}$ (erg sec ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	δ	GOES Class (1-8 Å)	v_{max} (km sec ⁻¹)	T_{max} (MK)	$n_{apex,max}$ (cm ⁻³)
1	5	1.00×10^{10}	13.7	C1.7	576.3	26.2	5.65×10^{10}
2	10	1.98×10^{10}	25.3	M3.9	825.0	31.8	9.87×10^{10}
3	15	2.96×10^{10}	36.8	X3.2	938.7	35.3	1.34×10^{11}
4	20	3.94×10^{10}	48.3	X6.4	918.6	37.2	1.62×10^{11}
5	25	4.92×10^{10}	59.8	X14	985.5	39.4	1.92×10^{11}
6	30	5.91×10^{10}	71.4	X27	982.7	39.7	2.09×10^{11}
7	40	7.87×10^{10}	94.4	X66	913.9	43.1	2.66×10^{11}
8	50	9.84×10^{10}	117.4	X150	850.3	43.5	3.20×10^{11}

Table 4.2: Eight simulations assuming an equal number flux \mathcal{N} of electrons for isoenergetic beams at energies $E_c = [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50]$ keV. The simulations were done on loops of length $2L = 50$ Mm, with a cross-sectional area $A = 7.8 \times 10^{16}$ cm². The spectral indices δ were calculated using Equation 4.3 and the energy fluxes were then calculated using Equation 4.6, so that the beams have the same number of electrons.

perature (both are near, although not always at, the apex of the loop), and the bottom shows the maximum of the bulk flow velocity. Several things are readily apparent. Lower energy beams heat and evaporate material earlier, but the loops do not become as dense or hot, and they drain more slowly than those subject to higher energy beams.

The explanation for this behavior is straightforward: the total beam energy primarily determines the response of the atmosphere. Lower energy electrons are more efficient at heating the loops since their energy is deposited higher in the atmosphere where the energy deposited is substantial compared to the local thermal energy and less of the energy will be radiated away immediately (as seen in the previous section). However, if the number of high and low energy electrons is equal, the high energy electrons will ultimately cause a stronger up-

Figure 4-7: How the temperature, density, and bulk flow velocity vary for the simulations in Table 4.2. *Top Left:* The minimum of the electron density in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Top Right:* The maximum of the electron temperature in the 8 simulations as a function of time. *Bottom:* The maximum of the bulk flow velocity as a function of time (for the first 300 seconds).

Figure 4-8: The maximal electron temperatures and apex electron densities in the 8 simulations in this section as a function of the beam flux. Although the number flux is the same, the beam flux is not, and it is clear that the atmospheric response is driven by the total input energy.

flow of material and a sharper rise in the temperature despite being deposited deeper in the atmosphere since they carry more total energy. Figure 4-8 shows the maximal temperatures, densities, and bulk flow velocities in the simulations, plotted as a function of the beam flux. In both cases, there is a clear and strong correlation.

For 8 beams, with equal number of electrons at different electron energies, there are significant differences between the post-flare atmo-

sphere. Compare this result with the previous section, where it was found (Runs 17-24, for example) that the post-flare density and temperature are not strongly dependent on the electron energy above the explosive evaporation threshold. Finally, compare Run 8 of this section with Runs 23 and 24 of the previous section. The number fluxes (Equation 4.4), respectively, are 1.23×10^{18} , 1.24×10^{18} , and 1.56×10^{18} $\text{e}^- \text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ at their peaks. Despite the different number fluxes, the maximal bulk flow velocities, temperatures, and densities are all very similar. The conclusion that can be drawn is that the number flux is unimportant compared to the energy flux carried by the beam.

In the limit of very large electron energies, however, this result would not hold. For example, if the electrons had an extremely large energy, *e.g.*, 1 MeV, they would stop at a column density of around 10^{23}cm^{-2} (Nagai & Emslie 1984 [120]). This column density corresponds to a photospheric depth, where the local thermal energy is too high for there to be significant heating from the electrons without an unrealistically high energy flux.

4.4 On the Explosive Evaporation Threshold

Explosive evaporation of material from the chromosphere into the corona occurs when heating of the chromosphere to coronal temperatures causes a sharp rise in the pressure there, driving a strong flow of material upwards (and a slower front downwards in a related process called chromospheric condensation). Fisher et al. (1985a,b,c [57, 58, 59]) found, using numerical simulations, that beam fluxes above about 10^{10} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻² drive explosive evaporation, with velocities exceeding a few hundred km sec⁻¹. Below that threshold, the chromosphere will not be heated to coronal temperatures, and the majority of the material that evaporates is from the transition region and a thin layer at the top of the chromosphere. The flows will be gentle, on the order of tens of km sec⁻¹.

Many observations over the years have confirmed the existence of explosive evaporation and significantly blue-shifted material in flares (Antonucci et al. 1982 [5]; Antonucci & Dennis 1983 [4]; Doschek 1990 [44]; Milligan & Dennis 2009 [118]; Milligan 2011 [117]; Doschek et al. 2013 [46]). Further, these observations have shown that the hottest plasma travels faster than cooler plasma, with a clear relation between velocity and temperature (e.g., Milligan & Dennis 2009 [118]).

However, the original work of Fisher et al. did not examine the dependences on the stopping depth of electrons. In particular, they assume a cut-off energy of 20 keV in all of their simulations, although they acknowledge briefly that this value will change the threshold. They assume a beam that lasts for 5 seconds, with a constant beam flux, constant spectral index δ of 4, and constant cut-off energy of 20 keV. In this section, the dependence of the explosive evaporation threshold on the cut-off energy is examined. They derive their threshold by equating the radiative loss rate at the top of the chromosphere with the heat deposition, such that if the heating exceeds the losses, the pressure will rise and drive evaporation. However, since the radiative loss rate varies with depth (as the density increases), this threshold must be a function of the cut-off energy.

Using isoenergetic beams, a large number of simulations have been performed to examine this threshold as a function of the cut-off energy. Similar to the work of Fisher et al. (1985a [57]), a beam duration of 5 seconds is assumed with a *constant* beam flux and constant spectral index (unlike in Section 4.2 where the beam flux varied as a function of time). The cut-off energy is varied between [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 50] keV, with spectral indices derived from Equation 4.3. The beam

flux is then varied between $[10^8, 5 \times 10^8, 10^9, 5 \times 10^9, 10^{10}, 5 \times 10^{10}, 10^{11}]$ erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻². Table 4.3 shows the parameters of the simulations performed, along with the maximum bulk flow velocities (km sec⁻¹), maximum electron temperatures (MK), and maximum apex electron densities (cm⁻³) that were attained.

Several things can be learned from these simulations. First, it is clear from both the maximal velocities and densities that the explosive evaporation threshold depends strongly on the energy of the electrons. For example, at a beam flux of 10^{10} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻², it is obvious that 5 keV electrons will drive explosive evaporation, but 50 keV electrons will hardly drive any upflow at all. The reason is once again the location of energy deposition: 5 keV electrons will deposit a large amount of their energy in the transition region and top of the chromosphere, while 50 keV electrons will travel much deeper where the heat capacity is higher, the inertia is greater, and the radiation is stronger. Thus, in order to drive strong evaporation in the case of a high energy cut-off, more energy must be carried by high energy electrons.

Figure 4-9 shows the temperatures (MK), densities (cm⁻³), and velocities (km sec⁻¹) attained in these simulations as a function of cut-off energy, for the various beam fluxes in Table 4.3. First, consider the

Run #	E_c (keV)	F_0 (erg sec ⁻¹ cm ⁻²)	δ	v_{\max} (km sec ⁻¹)	T_{\max} (MK)	$n_{\text{apex,max}}$ (cm ⁻³)
1	5	1.00×10^8	13.7	63.6	1.06	6.11×10^8
2	5	5.00×10^8	13.7	255	2.69	2.18×10^9
3	5	1.00×10^9	13.7	342	4.60	3.13×10^9
4	5	5.00×10^9	13.7	596	12.1	5.42×10^9
5	5	1.00×10^{10}	13.7	737	15.5	7.93×10^9
6	5	5.00×10^{10}	13.7	1220	28.6	1.90×10^{10}
7	10	1.00×10^9	25.3	84.5	1.60	7.80×10^8
8	10	5.00×10^9	25.3	577	5.16	5.61×10^9
9	10	1.00×10^{10}	25.3	759	8.52	8.11×10^9
10	10	5.00×10^{10}	25.3	1210	20.4	1.92×10^{10}
11	15	1.00×10^9	36.8	40.0	1.11	5.12×10^8
12	15	5.00×10^9	36.8	146	2.74	1.14×10^9
13	15	1.00×10^{10}	36.8	538	4.72	1.09×10^{10}
14	15	5.00×10^{10}	36.8	1190	14.6	2.07×10^{10}
15	20	1.00×10^9	48.3	21.8	0.93	4.24×10^8
16	20	5.00×10^9	48.3	97.3	1.85	7.34×10^8
17	20	1.00×10^{10}	48.3	199	3.00	1.68×10^9
18	20	5.00×10^{10}	48.3	1070	10.7	2.81×10^{10}
19	25	1.00×10^9	59.8	19.8	0.85	3.91×10^8
20	25	5.00×10^9	59.8	67.7	1.43	6.37×10^8
21	25	1.00×10^{10}	59.8	113	2.17	1.05×10^9
22	25	5.00×10^{10}	59.8	886	8.90	3.84×10^{10}
23	30	1.00×10^9	71.4	17.5	0.81	3.75×10^8
24	30	5.00×10^9	71.4	49.4	1.21	5.54×10^8
25	30	1.00×10^{10}	71.4	88.3	1.71	7.68×10^8
26	30	5.00×10^{10}	71.4	667	6.26	3.39×10^{10}
27	40	1.00×10^9	94.4	15.7	0.76	3.63×10^8
28	40	5.00×10^9	94.4	26.3	0.98	4.59×10^8
29	40	1.00×10^{10}	94.4	54.2	1.26	5.78×10^8
30	40	5.00×10^{10}	94.4	198	3.49	1.91×10^9
31	40	1.00×10^{11}	94.4	573	6.29	9.03×10^{10}
32	50	1.00×10^{10}	117.4	36.5	1.04	4.92×10^8
33	50	5.00×10^{10}	117.4	136	2.53	1.17×10^9
34	50	1.00×10^{11}	117.4	328	4.16	7.94×10^9

Table 4.3: Simulations across a range of cut-off energies (5-50 keV), for a range of beam fluxes (10^8 - 10^{11} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻²), assuming isoenergetic beams. The maximum velocities, electron temperatures, and electron apex densities are shown.

temperature plot. At every beam flux, lower cut-off energies (i.e., lower electron energies) lead to monotonically higher temperatures attained in the simulations. This once again confirms the notion that lower energy electrons are more efficient at heating flaring loops.

The density plot shows something different. At a given beam flux (e.g., 5×10^{10} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻²), the simulations with the highest energy electrons become only slightly denser than the initial conditions ($\approx 4 \times 10^8$ cm⁻³), while the others increase in density by over 2 orders of magnitude (in this case, beams with electron energy < 40 keV). However, note that for all of the simulations below this threshold, the maximal apex density is approximately the same ($\approx 2 \times 10^{10}$ cm⁻³). Since the total non-thermal energy content was the same in each simulation, this suggests that the amount of upflowing material does not depend strongly on the cut-off energy, below that limit.

Finally, consider the velocity plot, where a similar trend is found. At a given beam flux, the highest velocities are attained by beams with the lowest energy electrons, in general. However, as with the density case, below a certain threshold, the velocities are approximately equal. For example, at 5×10^{10} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻², the maximal velocities at 5, 10, 15 keV cut-offs are all around 1200 km sec⁻¹. By considering the

Figure 4-9: The maximal density, temperature, and bulk flow velocity attained in each simulation in Table 4.3, as a function of cut-off energy and beam flux (different colors, as labeled). *Top:* The maximal electron temperature in each simulation. At every beam flux, lower energy electrons lead to higher temperatures. *Middle:* The maximal electron density at the apex of the loop. *Bottom:* The maximal bulk flow velocity in each simulation.

pressure balances in the chromosphere, Fisher et al. (1985b [58]) derive the maximum speed attained by explosive evaporation to be around $2.35 c_s$ (the sound speed). Assuming an ideal gas, this gives:

$$2.35c_s = 2.35\sqrt{\frac{\gamma k_B T}{m_i}} \approx (2.76 \times 10^4) T^{0.5} [\text{cm sec}^{-1}] \quad (4.7)$$

for γ the adiabatic index ($\frac{5}{3}$), k_B the Boltzmann constant, and m_i the ion mass (assumed to be hydrogen). For example, in the case of Run 6, for a temperature of around 20 MK, the speed works out to around 1170 km sec⁻¹. Similarly, for Run 9, at a temperature of about 8 MK, the equation gives a speed of 780 km sec⁻¹. In general, the results in Table 4.3 are in agreement with the speed derived by Fisher et al. (1985b [58]), regardless of the cut-off energy (or, equivalently here, electron energy).

These results confirm the existence of two regimes of underlying physics: gentle and explosive evaporation. In the explosive evaporation case, the amount of material and velocity at which that material is transported through the solar atmosphere strongly depend on both the beam flux and the cut-off energy. The maximal velocity of upflowing material is around $2.35c_s$, as derived by Fisher et al. (1985b [58]). However, the threshold between gentle and explosive evaporation *does*

Figure 4-10: The energy flux threshold for explosive evaporation as a function of the cut-off energy. At each cut-off energy, the upper and lower limits attained by the simulations in Table 4.3 are plotted. A linear fit in log-log space to the average of the limits has been over-plotted, for comparison.

depend on the cut-off energy and can be estimated from these results.

By fitting a line in log-log space to the average of the upper and lower limits of the threshold, the following relation is found:

$$\log_{10} F = 6.99 + 2.43 \log_{10} E_c \quad (4.8)$$

Figure 4-10 shows the upper and lower limits obtained by the simulations in this section, listed in Table 4.3, along with the fit to the data.

4.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, the deposition of energy in the solar atmosphere by non-thermal electrons as the driving mechanism for solar flares has been examined. In order to study the transport of mass, momentum, and energy through the solar atmosphere, knowledge of the properties of the energy deposition and the detailed response of the atmosphere are crucial. Observations have revealed accelerated electrons ranging in energy from a few keV to well over 100 keV (e.g., Holman et al. 2003 [79]; Warmuth et al. 2009 [150]; Ireland et al. 2013 [82]). How the atmosphere responds to heating by an electron beam depends strongly on the properties of the beam, and thus upon the electrons that compose the beam. To this end, isoenergetic beams (that is, beams composed of electrons all at the same energy) have been used to understand the importance of electrons at different energies.

After deriving the necessary equations to model isoenergetic beams, simulations were carried out assuming otherwise realistic parameters. The electron beams were assumed to last for 5 minutes, with the energy pulse rising and falling for 150 seconds, reaching a peak energy flux consistent with observed quantities. The cut-off energies composed a wide-range of energies, from 5 to 50 keV, well within observed bounds.

The loops were assumed to be 50 Mm in length, consistent with measurements of active region structures.

These simulations show several important features of electron beam heating:

1. Above the explosive evaporation threshold, the response of the atmosphere does not strongly depend on the electron energy. Although properties of the impulsive phase may still differ, during the gradual phase the densities and temperatures in the corona are fairly independent of the electron energy.
2. Below the explosive evaporation threshold, lower energy electrons are significantly more efficient at heating the atmosphere. Because their energy will be deposited higher up (towards the top of the chromosphere and transition region) than higher energy electrons, the deposited energy is comparable to the local thermal energy and less of the energy is lost through the efficient radiation deeper in the chromosphere.
3. Lower energy electrons drive up-flows sooner than higher energy electrons, although not necessarily with higher velocities. This may be because the higher coronal heating drives a thermal conduction front, in addition to the chromospheric energy deposition, or because the lower

density material has less inertia.

Since isoenergetic beams at different electron energies will carry different numbers of electrons, the importance of number flux was briefly examined. It was found that the number flux is unimportant compared to the total energy being carried by the beam. The energy flux carried by the beam dominates the response of the atmosphere, regardless of the number of electrons in that beam.

Finally, the results of Section 4.2 indicated that the explosive evaporation threshold depends upon the cut-off energy of the beam. Physically, since higher energy electrons deposit their energy deeper down (due to having a much longer mean-free path) where the heat capacity and radiative losses are much higher, a beam with a higher cut-off energy will require significantly more total energy to drive explosive evaporation. As explained by Fisher et al. (1985a,b,c [57, 58, 59]), explosive evaporation is driven by a local over-pressure in the chromosphere, which forces material both upwards into the corona (evaporation) as well as deeper in the chromosphere (condensation).

Accordingly, in Section 4.4 many simulations, using parameters similar to the investigations of Fisher et al. (1985a [57]) were performed. The simulations ranged from cut-off energies of 5 to 50 keV and beam

fluxes from 10^8 to 10^{11} erg sec $^{-1}$ cm $^{-2}$. These demonstrated important implications for heating driven by a thick-target model.

1. The results clearly indicate that the threshold for explosive evaporation varies strongly with cut-off energy (Figure 4-10). Lower energy electrons require significantly less energy to drive explosive evaporation, due to depositing energy higher in the atmosphere, which is assisted by thermal conduction.

2. Electrons around 5 keV can drive explosive evaporation with very little total non-thermal energy. In observed microflares, X-ray brightenings with energy release about 10^{-6} times that of a large flare (Hannah et al. 2011 [70]), observations point to cut-off energies below 7 keV (Phillips 2004 [126]). Even with non-thermal energies significantly smaller than solar flares, this leads to the possibility that explosive evaporation could occur in these microflares. For example, Chifor et al. (2008 [34]) found recurring EUV jets associated with microflares, with speeds up to 150 km sec $^{-1}$, which they attributed to chromospheric evaporation due to recurring magnetic reconnection.

3. The velocity of up-flowing material depends strongly upon both the cut-off energy and the beam flux. However, above the explosive evaporation threshold, the speed of up-flows is limited to $2.35c_s$ (Fisher

et al. 1985b [58]), which holds regardless of the cut-off or flux. The simulation results were found to be in good agreement with this speed.

4. The amount of up-flowing material depends strongly upon both the cut-off energy and the beam flux. Similarly to the velocity case, the amount of material transported through the solar atmosphere is limited once the beam is well above the explosive threshold, because the material is transported by the flows.

There are still many features of energy deposition by electron beams that need to be examined in detail. It is necessary to understand the dependence of material flow speeds on the loop length, the duration of heating, the shape of the beam pulse, and the pitch angle distribution of the electrons. A wider range of simulations can explore all of these features directly and systematically. The insight provided here, however, will allow for clearer interpretation of the physics underpinning the heating and evolution of observed flares. In particular, we will gain a deeper understanding of the beam properties, the transport of mass, momentum, and energy through the solar atmosphere, and the interplay between the heating mechanisms and the atmospheric response.

5 X-ray Source Heights in a Solar Flare

The work in this chapter has been done in collaboration with Dr. Gordon Holman (NASA GSFC).

5.1 Introduction

Solar flares are driven by a sudden, explosive release of energy previously stored in the magnetic field, commonly attributed to magnetic reconnection. Once the energy is released, however, it is not clear how it is partitioned between thermal energy (*in situ* heating) and kinetic energy (particle acceleration). There are two competing theories that individually can explain many (but not all) of the observed features of solar flares. In one theory, the collisional thick-target model, accelerated electrons are primarily responsible for driving chromospheric evaporation. In the other, thermal conduction, following *in situ* heating of the corona, is the mechanism responsible for filling the post-flare loop. In this chapter, the predictions made by each of these models are tested against observations of X-ray source height evolution in a small C-class flare observed with RHESSI.

Sui et al. (2006 [139]) reported an observational measurement of

X-ray source heights in a C-class flare observed with RHESSI. They studied the 28 November, 2002 C1.1 flare (04:35 UT), which occurred near the south-east limb of the Sun (see Figure 5-1). In the 3-6 keV energy channel, the source initially was determined to be high in the corona, traveling downwards towards the chromosphere, before rising back into the corona. Based on RHESSI images and light-curves in multiple energy channels, the authors conclude that the sources were dominated by non-thermal emission. The motion was explained as being due to electrons precipitating downwards (causing the source to travel downwards in the atmosphere), which then drove chromospheric evaporation that brought the source back towards the corona.

O'Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) furthered the initial work on this flare, measuring source heights in three different X-ray energy bands with RHESSI (3-6 keV, 6-8 keV, and 8-10 keV). The sources in all three energy bands were observed to fall from coronal heights towards the chromosphere in the early impulsive phase, before rising back up towards the apex of the loop at later times. The authors then test this observation against the collisional thick-target model. The sources appear to move down, possibly as the beam interacts with plasma of increasing density. As an ablating material front rises into the corona,

Figure 5-1: The 28 November 2002 (04:35 UT) C1.1 flare. The left hand side shows the observed GOES flux at the time of the flare, while the right hand side shows a SOHO-EIT 195 Å image taken during the impulsive phase of the flare (04:36 UT). The red circle marks the active region where the flare occurred.

the SXR source moves up, while the HXR bands move up as the propagating beam interacts with the advancing front. The authors conclude that the observations of the source height motions are in good agreement with the predictions of the model.

There is another possibility: the loop is heated *in situ* near its apex, driving a thermal conduction front through the corona towards the footpoints, heating material to very high temperatures as it propagates. In this way, the X-ray sources might also be expected to follow a trend towards the chromosphere, and then rise back up into the corona as

heated material returns from the lower atmosphere.

In this Chapter, the observational measurements of RHESSI source heights are tested against both heating mechanisms using a hydrodynamic model. Numerical experiments of the flare are performed using the thick-target model, the thermal conduction model, and a hybrid model which includes both types of heating. From the simulations, X-ray spectra are calculated as a function of time and position in the model, and height measurements are synthesized for the various RHESSI energy bands with the same techniques used to derive the observed heights. The synthesized heights are then compared to the observations of O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]), to contrast the predictions of the different heating mechanisms and to determine which, if any, are consistent with the observed motions of the sources.

In Section 5.2, the methodology and numerical modeling is briefly discussed, and the method by which heights are calculated is explained in Section 5.3. In Section 5.4, the results of a large number of simulations of the flare using the different heating mechanisms are presented. Finally, in Section 5.5, the results are summarized and interpreted.

5.2 Numerical Modeling

The numerical simulations were performed with the HYDRAD code (Bradshaw & Cargill 2013 [19]). The equations and assumptions are explained in Chapter 2. As detailed in Chapter 3, HYDRAD now uses a more realistic chromosphere, based on the VAL C model (Verzazza et al. 1981 [146]), with a non-uniform ionization structure. The loops are assumed to be semi-circular, along the field-aligned direction, with a constant cross-sectional area. The initial temperature and density profiles are found by integrating the hydrostatic equations from the chromosphere to the apex of the coronal loop. Initially, it is assumed that the electron and ion populations are in thermal equilibrium, before significant heating events occur.

To compare and contrast the different heating mechanisms, simulations have been performed with various forms of energy input. Some simulations are performed assuming the thick-target model, with two different electron distributions (the knee and sharp distributions, Equations 2.14 and 2.11, respectively).

Simulations are also run with a thermal conduction model, wherein the heat is deposited *in situ* in the corona, causing a thermal conduction

Figure 5-2: The volumetric heating rate as a function of time in Run 13 (below). The heat in that run was deposited over 1 Mm centered at the apex of the loop. The total energy deposited in the loop was 7.5×10^{28} erg.

front to propagate towards the chromosphere. We assume the heating profiles are triangular in time (not necessarily symmetric), with the energy deposited over a length of [1, 10, 30] Mm. For example, Figure 5-2 shows the volumetric heating rate as a function of time for Run 9 (below), which has a rise time of 10 seconds and a decay time of 50 seconds. The energy in that simulation was deposited over a distance of 1 Mm centered at the apex of the loop.

We finally run simulations that combine the two heating models: they have both an electron beam and in situ heating. All of these

simulations assumed an electron beam of the form in Equation 2.14, and *in situ* heating parameters as listed in Table 5.1.

5.3 Source Height Calculations

X-ray emissions are calculated in the same way as described in detail in Chapters 2 and 3. Both thermal bremsstrahlung and thick-target bremsstrahlung produced by the electron beam are included in this calculation. The emission is calculated all along the flaring loop, at all periods in time.

RHESSI source heights are calculated in a similar manner to the observations of O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]), as follows (see Figure 5-3 for an example of the method). In common with those authors, all flux below 30% of the brightest emission is removed to isolate true sources from background emission. Emission is ignored entirely if the maximum is below 10^{-2} erg sec⁻¹ cm⁻² keV⁻¹ as RHESSI is not able to detect such small intensities. The emission is integrated over 8 seconds (except the first height calculation which was integrated over 4 seconds), with each height determined at a 4 second cadence (which means there is an overlap between adjacent points). The emission is calculated in three energy channels: 3-6 keV, 6-8 keV, and 8-10 keV.

Figure 5-3: A diagram to illustrate how the RHESSI source heights are calculated. The data is from Run 2 in Section 5.4.1, at 28 and 60 seconds into the simulation. First, the X-ray emission is evaluated using the bremsstrahlung equations all along the loop, at the simulation's resolution (X marks). Next, the emission is binned into pixels of about 2 arcseconds, corresponding to RHESSI's angular resolution (diamonds). Then, the emission is integrated over 8 seconds (squares). Finally, all emission below 30% of the maximum of the energy band is removed (triangles). From the remaining emission, the source heights are then calculated using a weighted average within half of the loop length of the maximum.

In the numerical model, the X-ray emissions are calculated at the spatial resolution of the code, which is much finer than RHESSI. To correct for this, the grid cells are binned onto a coarser, uniform grid of 2 arcsecond cells, which is approximately RHESSI’s pixel size. In this case, the flare occurred at the eastern limb of the disk, so projection effects are small (compare, for example, the methodology of Bradshaw & Klimchuk 2011 [21], which calculates emission assuming the loop is at disk center).

The source height is then calculated as the weighted average of emission within half the length of the loop from the maximum. If there are two sources deep in the chromosphere (i.e., two foot-point sources only), the height is calculated along the first half of the loop. Note that O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) use the word “height” to refer to the field-aligned coordinate. For the sake of consistency, the word “height” in this chapter is used the same way.

5.4 Results

All of the simulations were performed for a loop of length $2L = 30$ Mm (which was estimated from the observed loop), with a cross-sectional area $A = 2.6 \times 10^{17}$ cm² (estimated from the RHESSI sources

in O’Flannagain et al. 2013 [122]). In the simulations with a thick-target component, the time-dependent spectral index δ found in Figure 1a of O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) is used. The GOES emission is synthesized to compare with the observed flare as a first step, and estimates more than a factor of 2 from observed values are thrown out. Note that the observed flare, after background subtraction, had a GOES flux of B3.7 (1-8 Å) and A4.7 (0.5-4 Å).

5.4.1 Low Density Corona

It is not clear what the initial coronal density of the flaring loop was. Observations show that the flare occurred in an active region at the Eastern limb of the Sun (Figure 5-1), but there are no measurements of the pre-flare density or temperature. As a starting point, the initial conditions of the loop are found by integrating the hydrostatic equations from foot-point to foot-point, assuming no significant pre-heating, so that the energy in the initial loop is negligible compared to the energy released during the flare. This results in an initial coronal density of around 10^8 cm^{-3} and temperature around 0.8 MK. Figure 5-4 shows the initial temperature and density along the loop.

28 simulations have been performed with these initial conditions.

Figure 5-4: The initial temperature and density profiles for the simulations in this section. These are calculated by integrating the hydrostatic equations from foot-point to foot-point. Note that the electron and ion temperatures are initially assumed to be equal (thermal equilibrium), although lower in the atmosphere the densities are unequal since hydrogen will not be fully ionized at chromospheric temperatures.

The key details are listed in Table 5.1. All 28 simulations are in approximate agreement with the observed GOES flux, and we have thrown out other simulations with predicted fluxes too far from the observed values. The first ten simulations adopted a thick-target model, five with a knee distribution (Equation 2.14) and five with a sharp cut-off (Equation 2.11). All ten simulations featured a beam that lasted for 100 seconds, with a 50 second rise and 50 second decay time. The total non-thermal energy was varied in these runs to best approximate the GOES class. The cut-off energy was varied between [1, 3, 5, 7, 9] keV, since the observational value was largely uncertain (O’Flannagain et al. 2013 [122] note that the non-thermal emission extends down to RHESSI’s observational limit of 3 keV). Note that the spectral index δ was time-dependent, so that the electron beam changes in time (*i.e.*, the spectrum varies between hard and soft).

The next 12 simulations adopted *in situ* coronal heating, over a length scale of [1, 10, 30] Mm centered at the loop apex, for durations of [25, 50, 60, 100] seconds. The time profiles of heating were triangular, with equal rise and decay times (except the 60 second heating profiles which had a 10 second rise and 50 second decay time, which better matched the GOES flux).

The final 6 simulations were hybrid models, with both thick-target and in situ heating components. All of the thick-target components adopted a knee distribution, with durations and spectral index as before. The duration of the thick-target and thermal heating components were both assumed to be 100 seconds.

In Table 5.1, the following are listed: the run number, along with the heating type, total non-thermal energy E_{NT} (erg), total thermal energy E_{Th} (erg), the duration of non-thermal heating T_{NT} (sec), duration of thermal heating T_{Th} (sec), the length over which in situ heating was deposited (Mm, if applicable), the cut-off energy (keV), and finally the synthesized emission in the two GOES channels (W m^{-2}).

Consider Run 2, which was heated with a non-thermal electron beam, in the form of Equation 2.14, carrying total non-thermal energy 8.0×10^{28} erg (corresponding to a maximum beam flux of 4.62×10^9 erg $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$). The cut-off energy was assumed to be 3 keV. Figure 5-5 shows the (electron) density and temperature as a function of position and time, the synthesized GOES light-curve (overlaid on the observed one), the synthesized RHESSI light-curves, the X-ray emission in the three channels of interest (3-6, 6-8, and 8-10 keV) as a function of position and time, and finally the calculated heights of the sources

Run	Type	E_{NT} (erg)	E_{Th} (erg)	T_{NT} (sec)	T_{Th} (sec)	Heat L (Mm)	E_c keV	1-8 Å (W m ⁻²)	0.5-4 Å (W m ⁻²)
1	Knee	3.0×10^{29}	0.0	100	0	-	1	B1.9	A2.1
2	Knee	8.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	3	B2.5	A2.4
3	Knee	6.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	5	B2.4	A2.7
4	Knee	6.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	7	B3.5	A4.7
5	Knee	5.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	9	B3.8	A6.0
6	Sharp	3.0×10^{29}	0.0	100	0	-	1	B3.1	A3.7
7	Sharp	8.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	3	B3.7	A4.2
8	Sharp	5.6×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	5	B2.9	A3.6
9	Sharp	5.6×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	7	B4.1	A6.2
10	Sharp	5.6×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	9	B5.4	A9.3
11	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	25	1	-	B4.0	A4.8
12	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	50	1	-	B5.2	A7.4
13	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	60 (10-50)	1	-	B4.9	A6.0
14	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	100	1	-	B4.6	A5.8
15	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	25	10	-	B2.8	A2.7
16	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	50	10	-	B3.5	A4.2
17	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	60 (10-50)	10	-	B3.3	A3.5
18	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	100	10	-	B3.1	A3.3
19	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	25	30	-	B3.5	A3.6
20	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	50	30	-	B4.6	A5.7
21	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	60 (10-50)	30	-	B4.2	A4.5
22	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	100	30	-	B4.0	A4.3
23	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	7	B4.7	A5.5
24	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	10	7	B6.3	A7.5
25	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	7.0×10^{28}	100	100	30	7	B5.6	A6.5
26	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B2.1	A2.1
27	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	10	1	B2.9	A3.0
28	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	7.0×10^{28}	100	100	30	1	B2.5	A2.3

Table 5.1: The results of flare simulations with a low initial coronal density, using three different types of heating: a collisional thick-target model, a thermal conduction front model, and a mixture of the two models. The total non-thermal energy E_{NT} and thermal energy E_{Th} contents are listed, along with the duration of heating for each (and the rise and fall time of heating, if not symmetric). For the thermal and mixed models, the length over which the energy was deposited is listed (centered around the loop apex). The cut-off energy, if applicable, is listed (keV). Finally, the calculated intensity in the two GOES channels are listed.

(overlaid on the observed values).

The GOES light-curve is in approximate agreement with the observed one, in terms of the maximum flux and cooling time. The predicted RHESSI source heights show that the emission in the three wavebands of interest begins low in the atmosphere, due to non-thermal emission as electrons collide with the dense chromosphere and deposit their energy. As the chromosphere heats up, material begins to evaporate into the corona, where the increase in temperature and density causes a rise in thermal emission (compare the temperature and density plots). Since the apex is the hottest part of the loop at late times and since the density is approximately constant across the corona, the emission is brightest at the apex (and roughly symmetric about it), so that the source heights are calculated to be there during the cooling phase.

Note, however, that in all three channels the emission is initially in the chromosphere. In other words, there is no downwards motion at the beginning of the simulation, unlike the observed flare. The reason for this is two-fold. First, the corona is initially very tenuous, so that its column density is very small, and even low energy electrons stream through the loop without depositing their energy. Second, since there

Figure 5-5: The results for Run 2, heated by a beam of electrons with a total energy of 8.0×10^{28} erg. *Top Left:* The electron density vs position along the loop, with several times overlotted. *Top Right:* The electron temperature versus position along the loop. *Middle Left:* The synthesized GOES light-curve, with the observed (background-subtracted) light-curve overlaid. *Middle Right:* The synthesized RHESSI light-curves, for 5 different bands. *Bottom left:* The X-ray emission in the 3 bands as a function of position, with several times overlaid (where emission below 30% of the maximum has been removed). *Bottom Right:* The calculated source heights for the three energy bands (3-6, 6-8, 8-10 keV), with the observed heights overlaid (see also Figure 2 of O’Flanagan et al. 2013 [122]).

is no preheating and no early coronal energy deposition, there is essentially no thermal emission at early times. Thus, the heating properties described by Run 2 are inconsistent with the observations.

Next, consider Run 14, heated *in situ* over 1 Mm centered at the apex of the loop for 100 seconds, for a total of 7.5×10^{28} erg of energy. Figure 5-6 similarly shows the density, temperature, GOES and RHESSI light-curves, X-ray emission, and calculated source heights as functions of time.

The heat is deposited over the top 1 Mm of the loop, which quickly drives a thermal conduction front down the loop towards the lower atmosphere. Around the transition region/chromosphere boundary, the energy dissipates, causing the top layers to to boil off, which drives a gentle upflow of material. Initially, the emission coincides with the thermal conduction front, quickly falling lower in the atmosphere (but distinctly above the chromosphere). As the density and temperature rise, thermal emission spreads across the coronal part of the loop as the material front travels towards the apex.

Note that in this simulation, all three sources are predicted to travel downwards (although faster than the observations). In the 3-6 keV channel, the emission stays peaked lower in the atmosphere, before

Figure 5-6: The results for Run 14, heated *in situ* over 1 Mm near the apex of the loop with a total energy of 7.5×10^{28} erg. *Top Left:* The electron density vs position along the loop, with several times overplotted. *Top Right:* The electron temperature versus position along the loop. *Middle Left:* The synthesized GOES light-curve, with the observed (background-subtracted) light-curve overlaid. *Middle Right:* The synthesized RHESSI light-curves, for 5 different bands. *Bottom left:* The X-ray emission in the 3 bands as a function of position, with several times overlaid (where emission below 30% of the maximum has been removed). *Bottom Right:* The calculated source heights for the three energy bands (3-6, 6-8, 8-10 keV), with the observed heights overlaid (see also Figure 2 of O’Flannagain et al. 2013 [122]).

the corona significantly heats up and fills, and only begins to rise after about 40 seconds. However, the sources in the 6-8 and 8-10 keV channels rise back up almost immediately after 20 seconds (along with the rise in density - see the top left plot). As the corona fills, the emission becomes centered around the apex once again in all three channels. However, because the higher energy sources rise far too quickly, this model is also inconsistent with the observations.

In the case of Run 14, the sources rise extremely quickly to the apex of the loop (see the bottom of Figure 5-6), while they rise more slowly in Run 2, at approximately the same time as the observed sources (Figure 5-5). There is a similar pattern in the rest of the simulations, where sources in the loops that are heated in situ rise extremely quickly to the apex (Figure 5-7), whereas the thick-target and hybrid models are more closely aligned with the observed timescales (Figure 5-8), although they do not show the falling observed falling motion. The hybrid models are very similar to the thick-target models.

To summarize, it would appear that **none** of the models are consistent with the observations (Figures 5-7 and 5-8). In the thick-target models, the sources do not show downwards motion towards the chromosphere, with emissions initially located in the chromosphere (this

Figure 5-7: The source heights calculated for the thermal models in the low density case, Runs 11-22, from left to right and from top to bottom. The observed values from O'Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) are overlaid in each plot.

Figure 5-8: The source heights calculated for Runs 1-3 and 6-8 (thick-target, top two rows) and Runs 23-28 (hybrid models, bottom two rows), from left to right and from top to bottom. The observed values from O'Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) are overlaid in each plot. Runs 4, 5, 9 and 10 have been omitted; they are similar to the above.

result does not depend on the assumed electron distribution - both the knee and sharp distributions are similar). The mean-free path of the electrons are all significantly longer than the length of the loop, so that they stream collisionlessly before reaching the high-density chromosphere. Note that a non-uniform pitch angle distribution and strong scattering of electrons could change the dynamics. In the thermal models, the high energy sources tend to rise far too quickly compared to the observed values, if they even fall at all. The hybrid models do not fare much better, with most not displaying any downward source motion.

One possible reason for the failure of these models is the initial temperature and density profiles chosen for the runs. Low temperatures and densities are characteristic of regions subject to weak heating (*e.g.*, the quiet Sun). However, as the flare was located in an active region, it is likely that the plasma was subject to significant pre-heating (*e.g.*, perhaps via nanoflares) that caused an initial increase in the temperature and density (Holman 2014, private communication). O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) estimate that the initial coronal density needs to be closer to 10^{10} cm^{-3} for consistency with the thick-target model.

If the initial loop were denser, the column density would be higher, so that more electrons would be stopped in the corona and perhaps the

sources would then be observed to travel downwards in the thick-target model. Similarly, if the density and temperature were higher in the corona, there would be more thermal emission ($\propto n^2$), so that the sources in the thermal models might be timed more consistently with the observations. This possibility is tested in the following section.

5.4.2 High Density Corona

The initial density and temperature profiles are recalculated to be consistent with average active region core temperatures and densities, as well as the density found by O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]). Figure 5-9 shows the newly calculated initial loop profile, with a coronal temperature around 3 MK and density around 10^{10} cm^{-3} .

As in the previous section, numerous simulations have been performed using a thick-target model, a thermal model, and a hybrid model that combines both of these. The parameters of the new simulations are listed in Table 5.2. Ten simulations have been performed with a thick-target model, five adopting a knee distribution and five adopting a sharp cut-off, where the cut-off energy was varied between [1, 3, 5, 7, 9] keV and the beam flux was varied to match the GOES flux. Twelve simulations were performed using coronal *in situ* heating, with the same

Figure 5-9: The initial temperature and density profiles for the simulations in this section. These are calculated by integrating the hydrostatic equations from foot-point to foot-point, assuming that the loop has been subject to coronal heating prior to the flare. Note that the electron and ion temperatures are initially assumed to be equal (thermal equilibrium), although lower in the atmosphere the densities are unequal since hydrogen will not be fully ionized at chromospheric temperatures. Also note the higher densities, compared to the previous section.

parameters as the previous section. Finally, sixteen hybrid simulations have been performed, varying both the thermal and non-thermal energies, the cut-off energy, and the length over which the thermal energy is deposited. As before, simulations in which the predicted GOES emission is drastically different from the observed emission have been discounted.

As before, let us first consider one of the thick-target models, Run 2, where the only difference between this and Run 2 in the previous section are the initial conditions. The loop was heated for 100 seconds, by a beam carrying a total energy of 8.0×10^{28} erg and a cut-off energy of 3 keV. Figure 5-10 shows the temperature and density as functions of time, the GOES and RHESSI light-curves, the RHESSI sources at several times (with emission below 30% of the maximum removed), and the calculated RHESSI source heights.

In this case, the simulation shows very similar results to the simulation in the previous section. Looking at the density profile, it is clear that chromospheric evaporation is relatively weak, so the corona does not get much denser than 10^{11} cm^{-3} or so. Even though the initial coronal density was raised by nearly 2 orders of magnitude, the electrons stream through towards the chromosphere with little bremsstrahlung

Run	Type	E_{NT} (erg)	E_{Th} (erg)	T_{NT} (sec)	T_{Th} (sec)	Heat L (Mm)	E_c keV	1-8 Å (W m ⁻²)	0.5-4 Å (W m ⁻²)
1	Knee	3.0×10^{29}	0.0	100	0	-	1	B2.2	A2.0
2	Knee	8.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	3	B3.0	A2.7
3	Knee	6.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	5	B3.5	A3.8
4	Knee	6.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	7	B4.9	A6.4
5	Knee	5.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	9	B5.3	A7.8
6	Sharp	3.0×10^{29}	0.0	100	0	-	1	B4.0	A4.7
7	Sharp	8.0×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	3	B4.1	A4.1
8	Sharp	5.6×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	5	B3.8	A4.4
9	Sharp	5.6×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	7	B5.3	A7.5
10	Sharp	5.6×10^{28}	0.0	100	0	-	9	B5.2	A8.6
11	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	25	1	-	B4.5	A5.4
12	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	50	1	-	B4.9	A6.9
13	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	60 (10-50)	1	-	B4.7	A5.8
14	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	100	1	-	B5.8	A7.1
15	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	25	10	-	B5.7	A7.1
16	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	50	10	-	B5.2	A6.1
17	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	60 (10-50)	10	-	B5.1	A5.9
18	Thermal	0.0	7.5×10^{28}	0	100	10	-	B4.0	A3.9
19	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	25	30	-	B6.7	A8.5
20	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	50	30	-	B6.2	A7.7
21	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	60 (10-50)	30	-	B6.1	A7.2
22	Thermal	0.0	2.0×10^{29}	0	100	30	-	B4.9	A4.9
23	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	7	B6.3	A7.1
24	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	10	7	B5.4	A5.9
25	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	7.0×10^{28}	100	100	30	7	B7.0	A7.8
26	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	2.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B2.5	A2.3
27	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	3.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B4.1	A4.5
28	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	4.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B6.0	A7.4
29	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	3.0×10^{28}	100	100	10	1	B2.9	A2.5
30	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	6.0×10^{28}	100	100	30	1	B1.7	A1.3
31	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	4.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B5.4	A6.4
32	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	3.0×10^{29}	100	100	10	1	B3.6	A3.8
33	Mixed	5.0×10^{28}	5.0×10^{29}	100	100	30	1	B1.5	A1.2
34	Mixed	7.5×10^{28}	2.5×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B3.0	A3.0
35	Mixed	7.5×10^{28}	2.0×10^{29}	100	100	10	1	B2.2	A2.0
36	Mixed	7.5×10^{28}	5.0×10^{29}	100	100	30	1	B1.7	A1.5
37	Mixed	2.5×10^{28}	3.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	1	B3.2	A3.3
38	Mixed	1.0×10^{29}	5.0×10^{28}	100	100	1	3	B1.6	A2.4

Table 5.2: The results of various simulations of the flare with a high initial coronal density, using three different types of heating: a collisional thick-target model, a thermal conduction front model, and a mixture of the two models. The total non-thermal energy E_{NT} and thermal energy E_{Th} contents are listed, along with the duration of heating for each (and the rise and fall time of heating, if not symmetric). For the thermal and mixed models, the length over which the energy was deposited is listed (centered around the loop apex). The cut-off energy, if applicable, is listed (keV). Finally, the calculated intensity in the two GOES channels are listed.

Figure 5-10: The results for Run 2, in the high density case, heated by a beam of electrons with a total energy of 8.0×10^{28} erg. *Top Left:* The electron density vs position along the loop, with several times overplotted. *Top Right:* The electron temperature versus position along the loop. *Middle Left:* The synthesized GOES light-curve, with the observed (background-subtracted) light-curve overlaid. *Middle Right:* The synthesized RHESSI light-curves, for 5 different bands. *Bottom left:* The X-ray emission in the 3 bands as a function of position, with several times overlaid (where emission below 30% of the maximum has been removed). *Bottom Right:* The calculated source heights for the three energy bands (3-6, 6-8, 8-10 keV), with the observed heights overlaid (see also Figure 2 of O’Flannagain et al. 2013 [122]).

emitted higher up in the loop. The result is that, initially, the X-ray sources are found to be deep in the atmosphere (essentially chromospheric depths). As heated material fills the corona, thermal emission comes to dominate at later times, so that in all three channels, the sources rise to the apex of the loop.

Next, consider a thermal heating model, Run 14. This model has the same parameters as in the previous section, except that the initial coronal density is significantly higher. Figure 5-11 shows the density, temperature, GOES and RHESSI light-curves, X-ray emission, and calculated source heights as functions of time.

In this case, the thermal emission becomes detectable almost immediately, centered around the apex of the loop. As the thermal conduction front propagates downwards, the thermal emission in the lowest energy channel begins to fall. However, the fall is significantly less drastic in the higher energy channels. The source emission in the 3-6 keV channel begins to rise as material from the chromosphere gently evaporates. In this lower energy channel, the rise and fall times correspond very well with the observed sources. However, the morphology of the higher energy sources does not agree so well with the observations.

Unlike the previous set of runs, however, some of the hybrid models

Figure 5-11: The results for Run 14, in the high density case, heated in situ over 1 Mm near the apex of the loop with a total energy of 7.5×10^{28} erg. *Top Left:* The electron density vs position along the loop, with several times overplotted. *Top Right:* The electron temperature versus position along the loop. *Middle Left:* The synthesized GOES light-curve, with the observed (background-subtracted) light-curve overlaid. *Middle Right:* The synthesized RHESSI light-curves, for 5 different bands. *Bottom left:* The X-ray emission in the 3 bands as a function of position, with several times overlaid (where emission below 30% of the maximum has been removed). *Bottom Right:* The calculated source heights for the three energy bands (3-6, 6-8, 8-10 keV), with the observed heights overlaid (see also Figure 2 of O’Flannagain et al. 2013 [122]).

do show features that correspond closely to the observations. Consider Run 28, which was heated with an electron beam carrying 10^{29} erg of energy and a cut-off energy of 1 keV, and was also heated *in situ* over 1 Mm near the apex with a thermal energy release of 4.0×10^{28} erg. Figure 5-12 shows the density, temperature, GOES and RHESSI light-curves, X-ray emission, and calculated source heights as functions of time.

In this simulation, the loop is heated at three different points: the two foot-points and the apex. Initially, because the pre-heating has already caused an increase in the coronal density and temperature, thermal emission develops very quickly in the corona, centered around the apex. At the same time, the foot-points are heated by the streaming electrons, which cause a gentle evaporation upwards into the corona. In the 3-6 keV channel, thermal bremsstrahlung dominates at all times. In the higher energy channels, the non-thermal bremsstrahlung contributes significantly to the total emission at early times so that the sources are found in the chromosphere, until the coronal part of the loop is heated to well above 10 MK, driving strong thermal emission, causing the sources to rise into the corona. After the emission in the corona thermalizes, the front propagates downwards at around 30 seconds,

Figure 5-12: The results for Run 28, in the high density case, heated both through a thick-target model with a non-thermal energy of 10^{29} erg and in situ over 1 Mm near the apex of the loop with a thermal energy of 4.0×10^{28} erg. *Top Left*: The electron density vs position along the loop, with several times overplotted. *Top Right*: The electron temperature versus position along the loop. *Middle Left*: The synthesized GOES light-curve, with the observed (background-subtracted) light-curve overlaid. *Middle Right*: The synthesized RHESSI light-curves, for 5 different bands. *Bottom left*: The X-ray emission in the 3 bands as a function of position, with several times overlaid (where emission below 30% of the maximum has been removed). *Bottom Right*: The calculated source heights for the three energy bands (3-6, 6-8, 8-10 keV), with the observed heights overlaid (see also Figure 2 of O’Flannagain et al. 2013 [122]).

causing all three channels to fall to the lower corona. This emission then propagates upwards in all three channels at around 50 seconds, as chromospheric evaporation carries more material into the corona. In all three channels, the falling and rising motion is predicted from the model, although they rise slightly more quickly than the observations.

The thermal simulations in this section all fail to reproduce the source height motion (Figure 5-13, and compare to Figure 5-7). Runs 14, 18, and 22 (100 seconds of heating) are fair matches in the low-energy 3-6 keV channel, in that they rise and fall at about the same time and to a similar depth as the observations. However, the higher energy sources essentially remain at the apex throughout the simulations. The other thermal models are all badly mistimed in their predicted source motions compared to the observations. This is due to the variation of the heating duration: the 3-6 keV source travels downwards at the peak of the heating (e.g., for a duration of 25 seconds, the source falls around 12.5 seconds into the simulation).

Consider the thick-target models now (Figure 5-14). As in the low density case, there is essentially no downward motion detected in any of the three energy channels. In other words, even though the column density is significantly higher compared to the previous section, the

Figure 5-13: The source heights calculated for the thermal models in the high density case, Runs 11-22, from left to right and from top to bottom. The observed values from O'Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) are overlaid in each plot.

Figure 5-14: The source heights calculated for Runs 1-3 and 6-8 (thick-target model in the high density case), from left to right and top to bottom. The observed values from O'Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) are overlaid in each plot. Runs 4, 5, 9, and 10 have been omitted; they are similar to the above.

mean-free path of the electrons is still long enough that many electrons stream through the corona and produce non-thermal bremsstrahlung in the chromosphere before thermal emission begins to dominate. At later times, thermal emission dominates and the sources rise to the apex of the loop in all three channels.

Finally, consider the hybrid simulations that contain both thermal and thick-target heating. Figure 5-15 shows the source heights calculated for 12 of the hybrid simulations. The first image in the figure, Run 23, had a cut-off energy of 7 keV, and is essentially the same as the thick-target models in that there is no downwards motion from the

corona initially (Runs 24 and 25 are similar and have been omitted from the figure). Similarly, the sources in Run 38, the last image in the figure with a cut-off energy of 3 keV, form in the chromosphere. The best agreement is found for the models assuming a cut-off energy of 1 keV.

To varying extents, Runs 27, 28, 31, and 32 all show upward and downward source motion in all three energy bands, at times that are fairly consistent with the observations. Based on the depths to which the sources fall, Runs 27 and 28 are perhaps the most consistent with the observations. Both of these simulations had an electron beam carrying about 10^{29} erg of energy and a cut-off of 1 keV, and were heated in situ over 1 Mm near the apex of the loop simultaneously for 100 seconds.

5.5 Summary and Conclusions

A large number of simulations of the C1.1 flare of 28 November, 2002 (04:35 UT) have been run. Using a low-density atmosphere initially (i.e., assuming no significant pre-heating), 6 simulations were performed under the assumption of a thick-target model, where the heating is due to a beam of electrons depositing their energy through

Figure 5-15: The source heights calculated for the hybrid models in the high density case, Runs 23, 26-34, 37, and 38, from left to right and from top to bottom. The observed values from O'Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) are overlaid in each plot.

Coulomb collisions with the ambient atmosphere. 12 simulations were performed under the assumption of *in situ* coronal heating, distributed across length scales of [1, 10, 30] Mm, for various durations of heating. 6 simulations which combine the two types of heating have also been run. All 24 simulations were found to be in approximate agreement with the observed GOES light-curves, although there are significant differences between the predicted motions of the RHESSI source heights and their observed morphology.

In the thick-target models, the energy carried by the electron beam is deposited directly in the chromosphere because the electrons have mean-free paths longer than the half-length of the loop. The sources begin to rise as heated chromospheric material evaporates into the corona. The result is that the emission is initially completely non-thermal, located at the foot-points, and begins to rise into the corona tracing the progress of the material front, and ultimately becoming fully thermal. The source heights calculated based on the thick-target models thus begin at the chromosphere, and rise into the corona as the emission thermalizes. However, in the case of *in situ* heating, the energy is deposited directly into the corona, which very quickly drives a thermal conduction front (the conduction timescale $\tau_c \propto nT^{-5/2}$ is very small

initially). The source heights fall to the lower part of the corona quickly and then begin to rise gradually as the coronal density increases.

In all of these models, however, the calculated source heights are inconsistent with the observed source heights calculated by O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) in the RHESSI energy bands of 3-6, 6-8, and 8-10 keV. In the thick-target case, the sources do not descend the loop as observed, while in the thermal models the emission thermalizes too quickly and the sources rise to the apex almost immediately. The hybrid models are similar to the thick-target case.

However, under the assumption that the plasma has undergone significant preheating to temperatures and densities consistent with active region core values, the simulations were performed again. In this case, the thick-target models showed no improvement, while in the thermal models the 3-6 keV source motions are more consistent with the observations, although the higher energy sources are not. The hybrid models, however, do fare better overall here: all three sources in four of the simulations (Runs 27, 28, 31, and 32) are calculated to travel downwards and upwards in a manner consistent with the observations.

Saint-Hilaire & Benz observationally found with RHESSI and GOES that the non-thermal and thermal energy budgets in 9 flares

ranging in class from C6 to M8 were the same order of magnitude, although there is often more non-thermal than thermal energy (Saint-Hilaire & Benz 2005 [135]). Emslie et al. similarly studied the energy budget in two X-class flares, finding that the thermal and non-thermal energies were nearly equal in one that was long-lived, while the thermal energy was nearly 10 times smaller than the non-thermal energy in one that was very impulsive (Emslie et al. 2004, 2005 [52, 50]). Comparing these observations with the hybrid models, a few conclusions can be drawn. First, although the sources predicted in Run 32 show the approximate morphology that was observed, the thermal energy in that simulation is about 6 times higher than the non-thermal energy, so that it does not appear to be compatible with observed energy partitions. Runs 27, 28, and 31, however, are comprised of 23%, 29%, and 44% thermal energy, respectively, which is in the range of observations.

Runs 27, 28, and 31 have a few commonalities: they have a cut-off energy of 1 keV, they have thermal energy $> 3 \times 10^{28}$ erg, and the *in situ* heating was strongly confined to 1 Mm at the apex of the loop. However, Runs 26 and 34 have similar parameters, but their predicted source heights do not compare favorably with the observed ones. The only difference between Runs 26, 27, and 28 is the thermal energy

content, so that the only possibility is that Run 26 did not have enough thermal energy. On the other hand, Run 34 has 25% thermal energy content, which is intermediate to Runs 27 and 28 (23% and 28%), and its total energy (10^{29} erg) is intermediate to Runs 27 and 31 (1.3×10^{29} and 9×10^{28} erg). This suggests that for a weaker beam (*e.g.* Run 31), there will be a higher proportion of thermal energy than with stronger beams. In other words, if the reconnection process is more efficient at accelerating particles in a given flare, there will be less energy released *in situ*. Compare the results of Emslie et al. (2004, 2005 [52, 50]) who found that a more impulsive flare contained significantly less thermal energy content (see their Table 1 in Emslie et al. 2005 [50]).

There are a number of caveats here. First, in these simulations the cut-off energy is extremely low (1 keV). Both Sui et al. (2006 [139]) and O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) note that the non-thermal emission in this flare extends down to the threshold of RHESSI’s detection (about 3 keV), so that while this cut-off energy is low, it is not implausible. Second, the loop must have been preheated for consistency with the observations. However, the initial coronal density used in the simulations here ($\approx 10^{10}$ cm⁻³) is consistent with the findings of O’Flannagain et al. (see their Figure 5) and with the general properties of flaring active

regions.

As noted by O’Flannagain et al., pitch angle diffusion of the electron beam could also be an important factor in the observed heights. In other words, the electron distribution could have a high pitch angle (*e.g.*, perpendicular to the field line), which gradually becomes more isotropic, allowing a greater proportion of accelerated electrons to propagate further and further down the loop in time. Winter et al. (2011 [154]) provide strong, although not conclusive, evidence that pitch angle diffusion could drive the observed source heights. This possibility needs to be examined in more depth.

There are important conclusions from this work.

1. The results favor a heating scenario in which magnetic energy is distributed between thermal (*in situ* heating) and kinetic energy (particle acceleration). Either model by itself produces source height motions that are not consistent with the observations.
2. The *in situ* heating component is confined near the apex. In the simulations where the thermal heating was more spread out (*e.g.*, Runs 29 and 30 in Figure 5-15), the emission does not descend the loop and instead is initially located deeper in the atmosphere.

3. When an electron beam carries more energy, that is, when the reconnection process is more efficiently accelerating particles, there will be less energy released *in situ*. Compare the observations of Emslie et al. (2004, 2005 [52, 50]).

By combining the observational results of O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]) with detailed hydrodynamic simulations, the method by which energy is released in a flare has been examined in detail. The flare was exceptional in that it occurred at the limb and was clearly observed with RHESSI, which was at its peak sensitivity then. If similar observations are performed for other flares, this method can be repeated to further study the energy release and test the model.

6 Conclusions

6.1 Summary

This dissertation has examined in depth the processes which drive solar flares. Particular emphasis was placed on the thick-target model of solar flares, wherein a beam of highly energetic electrons accelerated from the reconnection region stream down a magnetic loop, depositing their energy through Coulomb collisions with the ambient plasma (Brown 1971 [25]). By combining the thick-target model with a one-dimensional hydrodynamic model of magnetic loops, many features of solar flares have been studied in depth. It is vital to understand the transport of mass, momentum, and energy in all phases of a solar flare to understand many of their observed properties, ranging across the entire electromagnetic spectrum.

In Chapter 2, the hydrodynamic modeling of the solar atmosphere and the thick-target model were described. The one-dimensional hydrodynamic equations for a two-fluid system acting parallel to magnetic field lines were introduced (the conservation of mass, momentum, and energy for electrons and ions). Then, electron distributions were derived, to be injected into the loops as heating terms, in two different

forms. From these distributions, the heating functions due to the electron beams were derived (following the equations of Emslie 1978 [49]), which can then be used as the heating term in the electron energy equation as a realistic flare heating function. Then, bremsstrahlung emissions that would be emitted by the cascading particles were derived, for use in forward modeling to calculate X-ray emissions from simulations. Finally, several assumptions were detailed about the limitations of the model and possible ways to improve the model.

In Chapter 3, the quantitative relations between the parameters of the electron beam and X-ray emissions detected by GOES were examined in detail, using this model. It was found that the GOES flux Ψ depends super-linearly on the energy flux F_0 carried by the beam in each channel: $\Psi \propto F_0^{1.7}$ (1-8 Å) and $\Psi \propto F_0^{1.6}$ (0.5-4 Å). This result agrees with Warren & Antiochos (2004 [152]) in the low energy channel ($\propto F_0^{1.75}$), but disagrees in the high energy channel ($\propto F_0^{2.24}$), and completely disagrees with the predictions of Lee et al. (1993, 1995 [99, 100]) in both channels, who suggest that both should be linearly proportional. The other studies were based on simple analytical treatments, though, and both of which made assumptions that may not be valid in flares.

It was also found that the GOES flux does not strongly depend upon the beam spectral index δ . The reason is that changing δ only slightly alters the proportion of high-to-low energy electrons, whereas the emissions are primarily determined by the energy that the beam is carrying. Observationally, Dennis (1985 [41]) found no correlation between the HXR flux and photon spectral index (and thus electron spectral index). Further, the result is confirmed by Falewicz et al. (2009 [53]), who performed a similar study. Finally, the GOES flux was found to strongly depend on the electron cut-off energy, although non-linearly. Increasing the cut-off energy to very high limits sends the electrons deep into the chromosphere, which has a significantly higher heat capacity. Decreasing the cut-off energy, however, tends to increase the heating in the loop and thus increase the thermal emissions that are seen by GOES.

In Chapter 4, the deposition of energy by an electron beam was examined in more detail. By using beams of isoenergetic electrons, the location of energy deposition becomes equal for all of the electrons in the beam, and so changes in the atmospheric response due to different energy electrons can be studied. It was found that lower energy electrons are significantly more efficient at heating the atmosphere than

higher energy electrons, since they deposit their energy in regions with a lower heat capacity and less radiative energy loss. However, if the beam flux is above the explosive evaporation threshold, then the response of the atmosphere does not strongly depend on electron energy. Further, lower energy electrons will drive up-flows of material sooner than higher energy electrons.

Since the difference between explosive and gentle evaporation leads to radically different post-flare atmospheres, the threshold which divides these two cases was examined. It was found that this threshold is strongly dependent on the cut-off energy of the beam, with lower energy electrons requiring significantly less energy to drive explosive up-flows of material. The amount of material and the velocity at which the material evaporates depend on both the cut-off energy and the energy flux of the beam (although the speed is limited in the explosive case, as shown by Fisher et al. 1985b [58]).

In Chapter 5, an observation of X-ray source heights was examined in detail. RHESSI observations of a small, C-class flare on the limb had shown, during the impulsive phase, motion of X-ray sources traveling down from the apex towards the chromosphere and then rising back towards the apex. This flare was modeled using a thick-target model,

a thermal model, and a hybrid model combining both types of heating. Initially, the loop was assumed to occur on a low-density loop, with initial conditions consistent with no pre-heating. However, none of the models were able to reproduce the observed source motion.

The density of the loop was then assumed to be significantly higher (close to 10^{10} cm^{-3}), as if the loop had been preheated, consistent with densities in the core of an active region. In this case, the thick-target model predicted sources that did not travel down the loop, while the thermal conduction model did not show the higher energy sources traveling downwards, in general. However, several of the hybrid models showed both the downward and upward motion, in approximately the correct time interval, as the observed X-ray sources. The results favor a scenario where energy is partitioned between thermal and kinetic energy. The results also suggest that if the reconnection process efficiently accelerates electrons, there will be less energy deposited *in situ*. However, the possibility of pitch angle diffusion of the electron beam still needs to be examined as a possible explanation of the X-ray source motion.

6.2 Future Work

There are a number of improvements to the model that can be performed, as well as deeper investigations of the properties of solar flares that can be examined. In this section, several improvements to the model are explained and then some points of this work that requires more detailed study is mentioned.

As mentioned in Chapter 2, there are a number of assumptions made by the model that, while often justified, can be removed to improve the model. First, solar flares often form large-scale arcades of loops, especially in the largest flares. As reconnection proceeds, the X-point moves outwards and upwards, forming longer loops that are each being heated. In this work, it was always assumed that the flares being examined occurred on a single loop that was disconnected from any other loops (i.e., no cross-field conduction and no interconnectivity). Even maintaining the assumptions that the loops are individual structures that share no interconnectivity, an arcade of loops can be modeled by combining simulations of many individual loops.

Warren & Doschek (2005 [153]) and Warren (2006 [151]), for example, studied the modeling of multi-threaded solar flares. However,

their conclusions both point to difficulties in reproducing temperatures and emissions that are consistent with observation. It is unclear, for example, how long an individual loop should be heated, if that heat is distributed evenly among multiple loops, or even if multiple loops are being heated simultaneously. Unfortunately, RHESSI cannot distinguish loops on a fine scale (Lin et al. 2002 [103]), so that measured electron beams might be partitioned among multiple loops in a given flare.

In future work, it will be important to implement a multi-threaded model in some way. Many of the features of solar flares are not accurately reproduced by a single loop model (*e.g.* emission measures), so that modeling a full arcade is important to accurately reproduce them. For example, consider the 15 April 2002 flare modeled in Chapter 3. By assuming that it consists of 32 loops heated for 20 seconds each, where the X-point travels outwards at about 10 km sec^{-1} so that successive loops are longer, an arcade simulation has been performed. Figure 6-1 shows the GOES emission then calculated by summing up the emission of each loop. In this case, the emission is once again approximately correct compared to the observed during the impulsive phase, while the gradual phase emission has been extended compared to the single loop

Figure 6-1: The GOES emission calculated for the 15 April 2002 M1.2 flare, calculated using an arcade of 32 loops, each heated for 20 seconds. The parameters were otherwise identical to the single loop model used in Chapter 3.

model (although still woefully short of the observed gradual phase).

While not perfect, this shows that solar flares can be modeled with an arcade of loops. There are still many problems, though. An arcade of loops takes significantly more computational time, it is not clear how each loop is heated, and the dynamics of each individual loop must be considered to fully understand the flare.

At the end of Chapter 5, it was noted that pitch angle diffusion of the electron beam could possibly explain the observed source heights of O’Flannagain et al. (2013 [122]). This possibility is not accounted

for in the calculations of thick-target bremsstrahlung. Following Emslie (1978 [49]), as the electrons stream down the loop, they not only lose energy, but they scatter to higher and higher pitch angles. Equation 30 of that paper gives for the cosine of the pitch-angle $\cos \theta = \mu$ evolving as it travels down a column density N :

$$\mu = \mu_0 \left[1 - \left(2 + \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \frac{\gamma K N}{\mu_0 E_0^2} \right]^{\beta/(4+\beta)} \quad (6.1)$$

where μ_0 is the cosine of the initial pitch angle of an electron, and the other values are as defined in Section 2.3.

Equation 2.33 was combined with Equation 2.35 to give the thick-target bremsstrahlung emissions for a given beam. However, this substitution makes an assumption that the cosine of the pitch angle is 1 (*i.e.* field-aligned) at all times, as is done commonly in the published literature (Holman et al. 2011 [78]; Kontar et al. 2011 [93]). Equation 2.35 should actually be written:

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = n_H v \frac{dE}{dN} = n_H v \left(\frac{-2\pi e^4}{\mu E} \left[x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda' \right] \right) \quad (6.2)$$

where μ is not necessarily 1. Compare Equation 24a of Emslie (1978 [49]). Thus, substituting these equations into the thick-target bremsstrahlung

equation,

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{thick} &= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) \left[\int_{E_0}^{\epsilon} \frac{n_{Hv} Q(\epsilon, E) dE}{dE/dt} \right] dE_0 \quad (6.3) \\
&= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) \left[\int_{E_0}^{\epsilon} \frac{\mu E Q(\epsilon, E) dE}{-2\pi e^4 [x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda']} \right] dE_0 \\
&= \frac{A}{4\pi R^2} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \mathfrak{F}(E_0, t) \times \\
&\quad \left[\int_{E_0}^{\epsilon} \frac{\mu_0 \left[1 - \left(2 + \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \frac{\gamma KN}{\mu_0 E_0^2} \right]^{\beta/(4+\beta)} E Q(\epsilon, E) dE}{-2\pi e^4 [x\Lambda + (1-x)\Lambda']} \right] dE_0
\end{aligned}$$

Because the pitch angle depends on the initial electron energy E_0 , this additional term is not simply a constant multiplicative term, and so this integral must be evaluated accordingly. In future work, this term will be included in the equations so that bremsstrahlung emissions will be evaluated more accurately. Alternatively, the transport of electrons can be modeled using a more sophisticated kinetic treatment using the Fokker-Planck equations that more properly accounts for pitch angle (*e.g.* Jeffrey et al. 2014 [83]).

It would also be worthwhile to apply this model towards a better understanding of microflares. Observationally, microflares have much in common with full-scale solar flares. Thermal and non-thermal X-ray emission are both present in flares and microflares (Hannah et al.

2008 [69]), with non-thermal emission extending well beyond 30 keV in microflares (Lin et al. 1984 [106]). Both flares and microflares occur on loops of similar size (Krucker et al. 2002 [96]), and both are generally confined to active regions (Christe et al. 2008 [35]).

However, these phenomena also have significant differences. The first obvious difference is that the scale of energy release is orders of magnitude different in flares, microflares, and nanoflares (Hannah et al. 2011 [70]). Many authors have devoted significant attention to the natural question that follows: since flares occur far less often than microflares (and presumably nanoflares), is there a correlation between energy release and rate of occurrence? Many studies have found that this occurrence distribution follows a power-law, with an index of around 2 (for summaries, see Hudson 1991 [81] and Hannah et al. 2011 [70]). Another difference is in the strength of the Neupert effect (an empirical correlation between the HXR fluence and SXR flux, Dennis & Zarro 1993 [42]): for microflares, there is significantly more spread in the correlation (Veronig et al. 2002 [147]; Battaglia et al. 2005 [13]). One possible explanation is that the particle acceleration processes in flares are less efficient in smaller events (evidenced by the fact that the spectral index of accelerated electrons is higher in microflares, Bromund

et al. 1995 [24]; Krucker & Lin 2008 [98]; Hannah et al. 2008 [69]), resulting in a weaker HXR burst (although Hannah et al. 2011 [70] note that it might be an instrumental effect). The results of Chapter 5 also indicate that perhaps in microflares that therefore there would be more coronal *in situ* energy deposition.

The model developed in this work could be used to directly study many of these processes in microflares. How the accelerated electrons drive microflare emissions and heating is still an open question. Based on the observational similarities, it seems viable that microflares may also be driven by an electron beam, depositing their energy in the lower atmosphere. As shown in Chapter 4, even low energy electrons are capable of driving explosive evaporation, which would lead to a strong coronal brightening that could be observationally detected. By using this model to simulate microflare events, X-ray emission as might be observed by GOES and RHESSI and spectral line emission that could be observed with Hinode-EIS, SDO-AIA, and IRIS could be synthesized to test the thick-target model in microflares against observations.

A Appendix: Gaussian Quadrature

In this appendix, the theory of Gaussian quadrature is briefly discussed. Quadrature is a method that allows for simple and fast approximation of definite integrals. For example, consider the simple integral:

$$\int_0^1 x^2 dx = \frac{x^3}{3} \Big|_0^1 = \frac{1}{3} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Suppose that the integral's solution was not readily known. To evaluate the integral then, how should one proceed? The method of Riemann sums would give an estimate, e.g.:

$$\int_0^1 x^2 dx \approx \sum_1^N f(x_i) \Delta x \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where the interval is divided into N sections for a function $f(x) = x^2$. For example, if $N = 3$, then we find for a left-handed Riemann sum:

$$\int_0^1 x^2 dx \approx 0^2 * \frac{1}{3} + \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^2 * \frac{1}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 * \frac{1}{3} = \frac{5}{27} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

As the number N increases, the sum will asymptotically approach the analytic solution. In this example, for $N = 10$ and $N = 100$, the sum would evaluate to about 0.285 and 0.3284, respectively, slowly

approaching the true value of $\frac{1}{3}$.

Unfortunately, this method is cumbersome and slow, and only slowly approaches the true solution. Gaussian quadrature uses a sum with far fewer terms to approximate the integral extremely quickly. For $N = 2$ (two-point quadrature), the method can be derived by assuming an approximation as follows.

$$\int_{-1}^1 f(x) dx \approx w_1 f(x_1) + w_2 f(x_2) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Using this equation, one then assumes this works exactly for a polynomial of order $N + 1$, $f(x) = A + Bx + Cx^2 + Dx^3$, so that

$$\int_{-1}^1 A + Bx + Cx^2 + Dx^3 dx = w_1 \left(A + Bx_1 + Cx_1^2 + Dx_1^3 \right) + w_2 \left(A + Bx_2 + Cx_2^2 + Dx_2^3 \right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Evaluating the integral and solving gives the solutions $w_1 = w_2 = 1$ and $x_1 = -x_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$. The values w_i are referred to as the Gaussian weights, and the points x_i are called the Gaussian nodes. For example,

returning to the original example:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_0^1 x^2 dx &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 x^2 dx \\
 &\approx \frac{1}{2} \times \left(1 \times \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^2 + 1 \times \left(\frac{-1}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^2 \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.6}$$

This gives the *exact* answer using only two points (and would for any polynomial integral of order less than 3).

This method of quadrature is referred to as Gauss-Legendre quadrature, with strict limits of the integral $[-1,1]$. Any integral evaluated over an interval $[a,b]$ (where a and b are finite) can be transformed so that its interval becomes $[-1,1]$. In the above example, the integral was transformed using symmetry, but more generally one can use u -substitution to transform the limits of the integral:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \frac{b-a}{2} \int_{-1}^1 f\left(\frac{b-a}{2}u + \frac{a+b}{2}\right) du \tag{A.7}$$

For some integrals, however, 2 points are insufficient for accurate evaluation. The general formula for Gauss-Legendre quadrature is given

by:

$$\int_{-1}^1 f(x) dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^N w_i f(x_i) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where N can be as large as needed. The nodes x_i are the i -th root of the N -th order Legendre polynomial (hence the name Gauss-Legendre), and the weights are calculated from these. Thus, for any definite (continuous) integral over a finite, closed interval, Gauss-Legendre quadrature provides a fast and accurate numerical evaluation.

However, in some of the work presented in Chapter 2, the integrals were over a semi-infinite interval (an infinite upper limit, e.g., Equation 2.38). In this case, Riemann sums or similar techniques would require immense amounts of calculation time to approximate the answer (and would require an upper limit at which to stop evaluation). However, there is another Gaussian quadrature scheme that offers accurate evaluation without sacrificing significant calculation time. To deal with these integrals, Gauss-Laguerre quadrature is used. In this method, integrals of the following form are approximated thusly:

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} f(x) dx \approx \sum_{i=1}^N w_i f(x_i) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The exponential function e^{-x} in this integral is referred to as the

weighting function (in Gauss-Legendre quadrature, the weighting function is simply 1). The nodes x_i in this case are the i -th roots of the N -th order Laguerre polynomials (again, hence the name) and the weights are again calculated from the nodes.

In this case, note that the limits of the integral are $[0, \infty)$ and that there must be an exponential function in the integral. The original functions must be suitably transformed to use this scheme.

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